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Comparative methods for studying adaptive traits of fungal
symbionts

*Komparativní metody pro studium adaptivních znaků houbových
symbiontů*

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Doctoral Thesis / *Disertační práce*

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Declaration

Hereby, I declare that I have written the present Ph.D. thesis independently, using the listed references. The papers that form part of the thesis are co-authored and author contributions are stated in the respective section. I have not used any part of this thesis to gain any other academic title.

Prohlášení

Prohlašuji, že jsem tuto disertační práci vypracovala nezávisle s použitím citované literatury. Publikace, které jsou součástí této práce mají spoluautory. Příspěvky jednotlivých autorů jsou uvedeny v příslušné sekci. Žádná část této práce nebyla použita pro získání jiného akademického titulu.

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Abstract

The kingdom Fungi encompasses an estimated 2.2 to 6.2 million species that occupy diverse environments, including aquatic, extremely dry, and hot or frosty habitats all over the world. To cope with adverse environmental conditions, fungi have developed numerous adaptations and life strategies, including symbiosis with other organisms, ranging from close, reciprocally beneficial (mutualistic) associations to severe pathogenic infestations. These interactions have an enormous impact on ecosystem functioning, with implications for agriculture and human health. For this reason, understanding the mechanisms enabling the successful development of fungal interactions is necessary for their efficient management. Recent advances in different 'omics' approaches have enabled us to compare species responses to the environment in a more complex way than before and to gain deeper insights into the adaptive mechanisms underlying specific life strategies.

My thesis is divided into four main sections. In the first section, I sum up findings about adaptations of fungal symbionts of plants and animals. Then, I introduce two fungal genera, *Geosmithia* and *Pseudogymnoascus*, to which I applied comparative methods for tracking adaptive traits. The ecological diversity of the genus *Geosmithia* allows to trace adaptive traits of obligatory fungal symbionts of ambrosia beetles and the phytopathogen *G. morbida*, which causes diebacks of walnut trees (*Juglans* spp.) in the USA. The genus *Pseudogymnoascus* includes the severe pathogen of bats *P. destructans*, which is decimating bat populations in North America. In the second section, I summarize the main results of my original publications, which are presented in the third section of the thesis. The fourth section is a synthesis of findings stemming from the presented publications and their discussion in a broader context.

The main result of my thesis is that specialization to a niche with limited nutrient sources has led to the narrowing of metabolic pathways of *Geosmithia* and *Pseudogymnoascus* species no matter if the fungus is a pathogen or mutualist. For the first time, fungal genome size was linked with cell volume and subsequently with the ecology of fungi. It suggests that genome size itself, independently on gene content, directly influences the ecology of fungus species. For now, only sparse information is available about the significance of genome size in fungal ecology, so further studies will show how genome size manifests itself in the fungal world.

Keywords: fungi, symbiosis, pathogen, mutualist, comparative methods, adaptations, genome size, enzymes, *Geosmithia*, *Pseudogymnoascus*

Abstrakt

Říše Fungi odhadem zahrnuje 2,2 až 6,2 milionů druhů, které obývají různorodá prostředí, včetně vodních ekosystémů, extrémně suchých a teplých či mrazivých habitatů po celém světě. Houby vyvinuly rozmanité adaptace a životní strategie, které jim umožňují vypořádat se s nepříznivými podmínkami prostředí. Mezi ně patří i symbióza s jinými organismy, ať už jde o úzkou oboustranně prospěšnou (mutualistickou) asociaci nebo závažné patogenní napadení. Tyto interakce mají nesmírný vliv na fungování ekosystému nevyjímaje zemědělství a lidské zdraví. Pochopení mechanismů umožňujících ustanovení houbových interakcí je nezbytné pro jejich efektivní řízení. Rozvoj rozličných "omics" přístupů nám umožňuje komplexněji než kdy dřív porovnávat odpovědi druhů na podmínky prostředí a získávat tak hlubší vhled do adaptivních mechanismů ležícími za specifickými životními strategiemi.

Má disertační práce je rozdělena do čtyř hlavních částí. V první části shrnuji poznatky o adaptacích houbových symbiontů rostlin a živočichů. Dále představuji dva houbové rody, *Geosmithia* a *Pseudogymnoascus*, u kterých jsem použila komparativní přístupy k nalezení adaptivních znaků. Ekologická diverzita v rodě *Geosmithia* mi umožnila studium adaptivních znaků hub žijících v obligátní symbióze s ambrosiovými brouky a fytopatogenu *G. morbida*, který způsobuje úhyn ořešáků (*Juglans* spp.) v USA. Rod *Pseudogymnoascus* zahrnuje významného patogena netopýrů, *P. destructans*, který decimuje populace netopýrů v Severní Americe. V druhé sekci shrnuji hlavní výsledky mých publikací, které jsou začleněny do třetí části mé práce. Čtvrtá sekce je syntézou poznatků pramenících z prezentovaných publikací a jejich diskuzí v širším kontextu.

Hlavním výsledkem mé práce je poznatek, že specializace druhů hub v rodech *Geosmithia* a *Pseudogymnoascus* na specifickou niku s omezenými zdroji živin vede k zúžení jejich metabolických drah, přičemž nezáleží na tom, jestli je houba patogen nebo mutualista. Poprvé byla velikost genomu hub spojena s objemem buněk a následně i s jejich ekologií. Je tedy možné, že velikost genomu sama osobě nezávisle na přítomných genech přímo ovlivňuje ekologii hub. Prozatím máme k dispozici jen kusé informace o vlivu velikosti genomu hub na jejich ekologii. Další studie ukáží, jak se velikost genomu projevuje ve světě hub.

Klíčová slova: houby, symbióza, patogen, mutualista, komparativní metody, adaptace, velikost genomu, enzymy, *Geosmithia*, *Pseudogymnoascus*

1. Introduction

Identifying adaptive traits is a paramount goal for biologists seeking to understand the evolution of species. Widening of the present niche or even seizing of a new niche through the acquisition of adaptive novelties enables species to enhance their chance of surviving in an evolutionary perspective. The Fungi kingdom comprises an estimated 2.2 to 6.2 million species (Blackwell 2011; Hawksworth and Lücking 2017; Baldrian, Větrovský et al. 2021). They have developed numerous adaptations, which enable them to survive in extreme abiotic conditions, colonize various substrates and interact with a diverse array of organisms. These interactions range from close reciprocally beneficial (mutualistic) symbioses to severe pathogenic infestations.

Diverse approaches to delineating adaptive traits have been devised. The last few decades have been greatly impacted by development of high-throughput methods, referred to as ‘omics’, which enable us to study the adaptive responses in their true complexity. Omics allow us to gain a huge amount of data in a relatively short time and to compare adaptive traits among organisms in detail. Omics approaches can be applied both to environmental communities and to individual organisms growing under *in situ* or under *in vitro* conditions. In general, we can study them at the level of DNA (genomics), RNA (transcriptomics), proteins (proteomics) or diverse primary and secondary metabolites (metabolomics; Fig. 1). However, the acquired data are often hard to interpret because of incomplete knowledge about gene, protein, or metabolite functions. At the same time, the output data should be interpreted in the context of species morphology and known ecology.

Genomic data bring various levels of information pertaining to gene identity and content, genome complexity and total nuclear DNA content, which can be useful in the study of species identity, evolution, diversity, and biogeography (Muggia, Ametrano et al. 2020). It was recognized early on that organismal complexity is not correlated with genome size (Mirsky and Ris 1951) and that non-coding DNA can constitute a large part of the genome. Bennett (1971) has proposed that the phenotype of an organism is not just a product of genes, but is also influenced by nuclear genome size. Flow cytometry has made it possible to estimate the genome sizes of a large number of species (Doležel, Greilhuber et al. 2007; Bleichrodt and Read 2019; Beaudreau, Massamba-N’Siala et al. 2021; Čertnerová and Galbraith 2021) and subsequently correlate genome sizes with organismal traits. It is now well known that genome size has a huge impact on organismal morphology, development, and life strategy, as it is positively correlated with cell size and negatively correlated with the cell division and growth rates in eukaryotes (Veselská and Kolařík 2015; Hultgren, Jeffery et al. 2018; Pellicer, Hidalgo et al. 2018; Simonin and Roddy 2018). Genomics provides the total genetic potential and gives a global view on the size and architecture of genomes, shedding light on evolutionary pressures involved in organismal adaptive evolution. Whole genome sequencing depicts genes under positive or balancing selection, unique genes, or gene losses. These genes and processes are then considered essential for life strategies of organisms studied. Nowadays, there are thousands of published fungal genomes, bringing about possibilities to search for general trends in fungal evolution by using comparative genomics. However, one great limitation of genomics is the often uncertain or unknown function of identified genes, which in turn also hinders functional analyses of the transcriptome and proteome.

Analysis of the transcriptome gives information about all mRNA (transcribed DNA) present in tissues. Thus, unlike genomic studies, transcriptomic analyses picture current processes in organisms. However, not every mRNA molecule is translated into a protein, and even so, proteins are modified after translation (e.g., by phosphorylation or glycosylation), which alters their function. If experiments

cannot be conducted under natural conditions, special care should be focused on the setting of *in vitro* conditions in which fungi grow, as they greatly alter gene transcription. Finally, yet importantly, there are some methodical problems connected with the isolation of high-quality mRNA, particularly from bacterial communities, which is necessary for sequencing.

One step further from transcriptomics is proteomics, which is the large-scale study of proteins. Proteins are the final products of gene expression and thus provide a much more detailed idea of the ongoing processes in cells being studied. One DNA entry can be transcribed into multiple different mRNA molecules, which in turn results in the synthesis of many different proteins. This implies an immense complexity of samples analyzed by proteomics. The proportion and number of individual proteins vary greatly over time. It reflects the rate of transcription of a given gene, the rate of protein synthesis, and the rate of its subsequent degradation. Traditionally, proteins are separated mostly by multi-dimensional gel electrophoresis and then analyzed using tandem mass spectrometry. Recent advances in chromatography have enabled gel-free approaches via sensitive high-throughput liquid chromatograph-mass spectrometer instrumentation, which allows to investigate complex protein samples (Muggia, Ametrano et al. 2020). As enzymes constitute the majority of all proteins expressed, various tools besides proteomics are available for studies of enzymatic activity, for example colorimetric or fluorogenic methods (e.g., Druzhinina, Schmoll et al. 2006; Licht and Biedermann 2012; Yang, Tedersoo et al. 2020). In these cases, we compare real biological functions of respective genes, but we are limited by our imagination about potential selective pressures.

Figure 1. Overview of omics approaches with their respective pros and cons.

Metabolomics deals with the study of metabolites. These can be classified as primary (associated with growth, development, and reproduction, e.g., hormones) or secondary (associated with an organismal responses to environmental conditions, e.g., antibiotics, melanin). Metabolomics, therefore, indicates the current physiological state of an organism. Every organism produces a number of different metabolites (e.g., lipids, carbohydrates, nucleotides, amino acids, vitamins), so it is not possible to analyze all the metabolites present by one method. Therefore, multiple analytical approaches are applied to extract, detect, and identify them.

Each of the presented approaches has its benefits and limitations (Fig. 1), and each provides complementary information to the others. Therefore, their combination can yield a more comprehensive and deeper idea of the evolution and adaptation of organisms.

The main goal of my dissertation was to use comparative methods to look for adaptive traits of fungal symbionts and pathogens. In the following chapters, I therefore present some adaptations of fungi that have been revealed using some of the comparative approaches outlined above.

1.1. Fungal-plant symbiosis

1.1.1. Mutualism

Mycorrhiza is the most common and studied type of symbiosis between plants and fungi. It is assumed that mycorrhiza greatly contributed to the evolution of terrestrial plants (Humphreys, Franks et al. 2010). It also has huge impact on nutrient cycling in soil and protects plants against biotic and abiotic stress. Mycorrhiza is a type of nutritional symbiosis in which mycorrhizal fungi mediate inorganic nutrients to plants, while plants provide carbonaceous compounds to fungi. Depending on the way fungi colonize plant roots, we distinguish different types of mycorrhizae (Fig. 2). While ectomycorrhizal fungi colonize the outer surface of the plasma membrane (apoplast) or intercellular spaces of the root epidermis, endomycorrhizal fungi enter plant cells (symplast), where they form characteristic hyphal structures.

The most common type of endomycorrhiza is arbuscular mycorrhiza, which is the fundamental symbiotic association of most land plants. Orchideoid or ericoid mycorrhiza is another type of endomycorrhiza that occurs in plants of the families Orchidaceae and Ericaceae, respectively. Although ectomycorrhizal and arbuscular fungi belong to very distant phylogenetic groups, their similar ecology has led to similar adaptations. The most prominent is an increase in genome size through the proliferation of mobile genetic elements (MGE; Figure 3, Table 1), which promotes the accelerated evolution of signaling proteins and small secreted proteins (Martin, Aerts et al. 2008; Martin, Kohler et al. 2010; Tisserant, Malbreil et al. 2013; Sun, Chen et al. 2019). These proteins are essential for tuning the communication between the plant and the fungus and adjusting mutual metabolism. Adaptive gene losses have occurred in the evolution of ectomycorrhizal and arbuscular fungi. Notable is the absence of genes involved in plant cell wall degradation (PCWDE) and the reduction in secondary metabolite production, by which the fungi probably try to minimize the risk of effector formation that could trigger the plant immune response (Tisserant, Malbreil et al. 2013). By contrast, ericoid mycorrhiza-producing fungi also grow outside this symbiosis as endophytes or saprotrophs. These fungi have retained genes for PCWDE (Perotto, Daghino et al. 2018), supporting adaptive loss of PCWDE genes in arbuscular and ectomycorrhizal fungi.

Figure 2. Schematic representation of some essential genomic features of mycorrhizal fungi, adopted from (Perotto, Daghino et al. 2018). In the root, mycorrhizal fungi are compared with endophytes (fungi that grow asymptotically inside plant tissues). Two leaf pathogens, both Leotiomycetes, are shown to illustrate examples of biotrophic pathogens (*Blumeria graminis*) and necrotrophic/hemibiotrophic pathogens (*Botrytis cinerea*). Green and red arrows indicate high or low abundance, respectively, for carbohydrate-active enzymes (CAZymes, including plant cell wall degrading enzymes), secondary metabolism, and effector encoding genes for each ecological strategy. ERMF – ericoid mycorrhizal fungi, ORMF – orchid mycorrhizal fungi, AMF – arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi, ECMF – ectomycorrhizal fungi.

1.1.2. Phytopathogens

Fungi are some of the most devastating plant pathogens, and they have developed myriad strategies of pathogenesis. They are divided into three groups: biotrophs, necrotrophs, and hemibiotrophs. Biotrophs penetrate plant cells with specialized hyphae and obtain nutrients from living plant tissues. Conversely, necrotrophs damage and kill host tissues by toxins and enzymes and then use necrotized tissue for nutrition. Hemibiotrophs grow for some time in plant tissues without damaging them and then switch to a necrotrophic lifestyle. The genomes of plant pathogens, especially biotrophic ones, are often larger than genomes of related saprotrophic species (Fig. 3, Table 1). Similarly to mycorrhizal fungi, genome enlargement is associated with MGE proliferation, which can occupy more than half of the genome (Spanu, Abbott et al. 2010). These elements allow the rapid adaptive evolution of genes important for virulence. They are rich in genes encoding small secreted proteins and effectors that manipulate host metabolism and mediate fungal-plant communication. In pathogenic species of the genera *Fusarium* (Ma, van der Does et al. 2010) or *Mycosphaerella* (Goodwin, Ben M'Barek et al. 2011), MGEs are localized on specific chromosomes. This ensures that they do not interfere with the functions of core genes, which are necessary for fungal survival. Another strategy is to divide the genome into two regions, the so-called 'two-speed' genome (Dong, Raffaele et al. 2015). One region, quite conservative, contains genes necessary for survival, while the rest is rich in MGE and genes encoding proteins important for virulence. At the same time, plants are evolving resistance genes against these effectors, leading to a lasting arms race or trench warfare evolution (Möller and Stukenbrock 2017). Whereas the arms race scenario leads to the acquisition of new advantageous alleles through positive selection, the trench warfare scenario supports the maintenance of different alleles in order to respond to diverse conditions by balancing selection.

Figure 3. Genome sizes and proportions of repetitive sequences in genomes of plant pathogens and mutualists. References are available in Table 1. Mean values of genome sizes for Ascomycota (37 Mb) and Basidiomycota (46.5 Mb) were taken from (Mohanta and Bae 2015). A more detailed analysis, focused on mycorrhizal fungi, can be found in (Miyachi, Kiss et al. 2020).

Table 1. Proportional content of transposable elements in genomes of plant pathogens and mutualists.

Fungal species	Order	Ecology	GS (Mb)	TE (%)	Ref.
<i>Aureobasidium pullulans</i>	Dothideomycetes	Sapro	26.0	1.0	(Gostinčar, Ohm et al. 2014)
<i>Mycosphaerella graminicola</i>	Dothideomycetes	Hemi	40.0	18.6	Goodwin, Ben M'Barek et al. (2011)
<i>Cenococcum geophilum</i>	Dothideomycetes	Myco	178.0	81.0	(Peter, Kohler et al. 2016)
<i>Leptosphaeria maculans</i>	Dothideomycetes	Hemi	45.1	34.2	(Rouxel, Grandaubert et al. 2011)
<i>Stagonospora nodorum</i>	Dothideomycetes	Necro	37.2	4.5	(Hane, Lowe et al. 2007)
<i>Blumeria graminis</i>	Leotiomycetes	Bio	120.0	64.0	(Spanu, Abbott et al. 2010)
<i>Erysiphe necator</i>	Leotiomycetes	Bio	125.0	63.0	(Jones, Riaz et al. 2014)
<i>Golovinomyces cichoracearum</i>	Leotiomycetes	Bio	222.0	59.8	(Wu, Ma et al. 2018)
<i>Oidium neolycopersici</i>	Leotiomycetes	Bio	120.0	39.1	(Wu, Ma et al. 2018)
<i>Podosphaera xanthii</i>	Leotiomycetes	Bio	142.0	76.2	(Polonio, Díaz-Martínez et al. 2021)
<i>Botrytis cinerea</i>	Leotiomycetes	Necro	42.3	0.9	(Amselem, Cuomo et al. 2011)
<i>Sclerotinia sclerotiorum</i>	Leotiomycetes	Necro	38.3	7.0	(Amselem, Cuomo et al. 2011)
<i>Fusarium oxysporum</i>	Sordariomycetes	Hemi	59.9	36.0	(Ma, van der Does et al. 2010)
<i>Geosmithia morbida</i>	Sordariomycetes	Necro	26.4	0.8	(Aggarwal, Westbrook et al. 2016)
<i>Neonectria ditissima</i>	Sordariomycetes	Necro	48.0	11.7	(Gómez-Cortecero, Harrison et al. 2015)
<i>Ophiostoma novo-ulmi</i>	Sordariomycetes	Necro	32.0	3.4	(Forgetta, Leveque et al. 2013)
<i>O. piceae</i>	Sordariomycetes	Sapro	32.8	3.8	(Haridas, Wang et al. 2013)
<i>Grosmannia clavigera</i>	Sordariomycetes	Necro	29.6	10.4	(DiGuistini, Wang et al. 2011)
<i>Raffaelea lauricola</i>	Sordariomycetes	Necro	35.4	12.7	(Ibarra Caballero, Jeon et al. 2019)
<i>R. aquacate</i>	Sordariomycetes	Sapro	35.2	5.8	(Ibarra Caballero, Jeon et al. 2019)
<i>R. quercivora</i>	Sordariomycetes	Necro	26.4	7.0	(Ibarra Caballero, Jeon et al. 2019)

<i>R. quercusmongolicae</i>	Sordariomycetes	Necro	27.0	4.0	(Ibarra Caballero, Jeon et al. 2019)
<i>Morchella importuna</i>	Pezizomycetes	Sapro	48.0	8.5	(Murat, Payen et al. 2018)
<i>Tuber melanosporum</i>	Pezizomycetes	Myco	125.0	58.0	(Martin, Kohler et al. 2010)
<i>Choiromyces venosus</i>	Pezizomycetes	Myco	124.0	53.0	(Murat, Payen et al. 2018)
<i>Ascobolus immersus</i>	Pezizomycetes	Sapro	60.0	3.5	(Murat, Payen et al. 2018)
<i>Laccaria bicolor</i>	Agaricomycetes	Myco	65.0	21.0	(Martin, Aerts et al. 2008)
<i>Coprinopsis cinerea</i>	Agaricomycetes	Sapro	31.0	2.5	(Stajich, Wilke et al. 2010)
<i>Melampsora lini</i>	Pucciniomycetes	Bio	189.0	45.0	(Nemri, Saunders et al. 2014)
<i>Hemileia vastatrix</i>	Pucciniomycetes	Bio	550.0	43.0	(Porto, Caixeta et al. 2019)
<i>Puccinia graminis</i>	Pucciniomycetes	Bio	89.0	45.0	(Duplessis, Cuomo et al. 2011)
<i>Diversispora epigaea</i>	Glomeromycetes	Myco	147.0	43.6	(Sun, Chen et al. 2019)
<i>Rhizophagus irregularis</i>	Glomeromycetes	Myco	153.0	36.0	(Tisserant, Malbreil et al. 2013)
<i>Gigaspora rosea</i>	Glomeromycetes	Myco	569.0	63.0	(Morin, Miyauchi et al. 2019)

Genome sizes (GS) and proportional amounts of transposable elements (TE) in genomes of fungal saprotrophs (Sapro), necrotrophs (Necro), biotrophs (Bio), hemibiotrophs (Hemi) and mycorrhizal fungi (Myco).

A similarly increased arsenal of small secreted proteins can be found in pathogenic fungi associated with subcortical insects. Some of them are able to cause the death of a healthy tree on their own, without the presence of a beetle. Perhaps the best known of these is *Ophistoma novo-ulmi* causing Dutch elm disease (DED). Other phytopathogenic fungi are *Grosmannia clavigera*, *Leptographium longiclavatum* attacking *Pinus concorta* subsp. *latifolia* (both transmitted by the beetle *Dendroctonus ponderosae*), *Geosmithia morbida* causing the death of the black walnut *Juglans nigra* (Tisserat, Cranshaw et al. 2009) and the ambrosial fungi *Raffaelea lauricola* (Fraedrich and Aghayeva 2008) causing laurel tylosis and the oak pathogen *Raffaelea quercus-mongolicae* (Jeon, Kim et al. 2017).

Important in pathogenesis are genes involved in the fight against oxidative stress or the detoxification of plant tissues and those having protective functions (DiGuistini, Wang et al. 2011; Comeau, Dufour et al. 2015; Schuelke, Wu et al. 2017). Virulence factors known to date include the production of cerato-ulmin, peptidases degrading plant defense products, and cytochromes (Comeau, Dufour et al. 2015). During pathogenesis, cerato-ulmin seals intercellular openings or interacts with the parenchyma, causing increased respiration. The most important proteases include oligopeptidases, which degrade long proteins, and plant defense peptides; and peptidases, which degrade terminal proline peptides. Proline- / hydroxyproline-rich proteins play an important role in

plant defense against mechanical and phytopathogenic threats (Comeau, Dufour et al. 2015). Important cytochromes of the CYP450 system include those that degrade phytoalexins (compounds mediating plant defense against microorganisms), such as pisatin demethylases, or mycotoxins such as sterigmatocystin and aflatoxins. However, *O. novo-ulmi* is resistant to plant terpenes, namely α - and β -pinene and limonene, during the hyphal phase. Furthermore, limonene stimulates its mycelial growth and the formation of the synnema (Hubbes 1975). Genomes of pathogenic ambrosial fungi (Jeon, Kim et al. 2017; Ibarra Caballero, Jeon et al. 2019) contain a large number of enzymes from the CAZymes group; however, their function may not be associated with the decomposition of plant tissues, but with their detoxification (Ibarra Caballero, Jeon et al. 2019). Decomposition of pectin is an important factor in the pathogenesis of *Hymenoscyphus fraxineus*, which causes the death of ash buds and the drying of leaves (Stenlid, Elfstrand et al. 2017).

1.2. Fungal-animal symbiosis

1.2.1. Mutualism

Fungi are a nutritional supplement for many animals. However, some groups of insects, especially ants of the tribe Attini, termites of the subfamily Macrotermitinae and ambrosia beetles of the subfamily Scolytinae and Platypodinae, have developed active fungal cultivation. These groups of insects are nutritionally dependent on their fungal crop, so the association is obligatory. In ants and termites, fungus cultivation has developed only once (Aanen, Eggleton et al. 2002; Schultz and Brady 2008). Ambrosia beetles, on the other hand, arose independently at least ten times over the course of evolution (Jordal and Cognato 2012; Johnson, McKenna et al. 2018) and are the oldest known group of farming insects (Vanderpool, Bracewell et al. 2017). The coincident timing of the radiation of ambrosia beetles and ophiostomatoid fungi suggests their co-diversification, which is in turn linked to the diversification of eudicots (Vanderpool, Bracewell et al. 2017). In all groups of domesticated fungi, we find morphological changes associated with the nutritional nature of symbiosis (Fig. 4). Ants of the genus *Atta* grow the fungus *Leucocoprinus gongylophorus*. This fungus accumulates nutrients at the swollen ends of hyphae (gongylidia), on which the ants feed. Similarly, termite-associated fungi of the genus *Termitomyces* form nutrient-rich nodules. Ambrosia fungi belong to various phylogenetic groups, most often of the orders Ophiostomatales, Microascales, Hypocreales (Massoumi Alamouti, Tsui et al. 2009), yet they have converged towards a similar phenotype in the form of a yeast-like growth phase and a palisade of hyphae with terminal globular conidia that the beetle grazes on (Batra 1967).

However, there are differences in the cultivation of fungus crops. Whereas fungal symbionts of Attini and Macrotermitinae ants grow in 'fungus gardens' prepared by insects, ambrosia fungi grow from beetle galleries directly into plant tissues, acquiring nutrients independently of beetles. This difference in fungal cultivation by insects is well reflected in fungal enzymatic profiles. Whereas the enzymatic profile of fungal symbionts of ants is driven by their co-evolution leading to their enzymatic specialization on substrates present in fungal gardens (De Fine Licht, Schiøtt et al. 2010; Nygaard, Hu et al. 2016), the enzymatic profile of ambrosia fungi is not shaped by symbioses and is rather similar to that found in closely related non-ambrosial species (Huang, Skelton et al. 2018; Veselská, Skelton et al. 2019). Similarly, lipid and small metabolites spectra of ambrosia fungi are shaped by their phylogeny rather than by convergent evolution (Veselská, Skelton et al. 2019; Huang, Skelton et al. 2020). Beetles usually transfer fungi to new galleries located inside the tree in mycangia (Batra 1966; Kostovcik,

Bateman et al. 2015; Li, Bateman et al. 2017), which ensures specificity of the symbiosis between the ambrosia fungus and the beetle. Mycangia have a variety of morphologies, from simple cuticle folds to complex sac-like structures (Six 2003; Stone, Nebeker et al. 2007), which has recently been studied in detail using computed tomography (Li, Ruan et al. 2018; Jiang, Kinoshita et al. 2019). The morphology of mycangia appears to influence the specificity of the symbiosis. Ambrosia beetles with large and complex mycangia are more selective with regard to their symbionts and host smaller fungal diversity than ambrosia beetles with small and less complex mycangia (Joseph and Keyhani 2021). Mycangia protect the fungus from adverse conditions when a beetle flies over a new tree or during a diapause. At the same time, they can have a selective function. They contain glands that produce fatty acids, phospholipids, sterols, and amino acids that support the growth of the associated fungus (Norris 1979; Stone, Nebeker et al. 2007; Skelton, Johnson et al. 2019; Joseph and Keyhani 2021). Selectivity can even work at a very fine level of selection of a suitable haplotype within one fungal species (Bracewell and Six 2015). The fungus is then passively inoculated from the fecal pellets and mycangia by the movement of the founding female (Biedermann, Klepzig et al. 2009). Some ambrosia beetles have stopped carrying ambrosia fungi and instead tunnel into galleries of other ambrosia beetles and steal their fungi (Hulcr and Cognato 2010). Not much is known about the physiology of ambrosia fungi. The fungus provides the beetle with nutrients necessary for its development, such as sterol, without which the beetle is unable to complete its life cycle (Clayton 1964; Kok 1979). Enzymatic studies show that ambrosia fungi from the orders Ophiostomatales and Microascales are not able to degrade lignocellulose (Licht and Biedermann 2012; Veselská, Skelton et al. 2019; Ibarra-Juarez, Burton et al. 2020). Lignocellulolytic activity is known in the ambrosia fungus *Flavodon ambrosius* (Polyporales), which is associated with a wider range of ambrosia beetles *Ambrosiodmus* and *Ambrosiophylus* worldwide, making it the widest distribution among ambrosia beetles (Kasson, Wickert et al. 2016; Li, Bateman et al. 2017). Most ambrosia beetles live in dead wood and are therefore not pathogenic. However, there are exceptions, such as *Xyleborus glabratus* carrying the aggressive fungus *Raffaelea lauricola*, which devastates plants of the family Lauraceae (Fraedrich and Aghayeva 2008), or the ambrosia beetles from the genus *Euwallacea* associated with the ambrosia fungus *Fusarium euwallaceae*, which decimates plants in the USA and threatens the avocado production (Ibarra-Laclette, Sánchez-Rangel et al. 2017).

Nutritional symbiosis has also developed in a variety of other subcortical insects, such as some phloem feeding bark beetles (Scolytinae). These beetles primarily feed on plant tissues, but fungi are an important additional source of nutrients for them (Harrington 2005; Hofstetter, Dinkins-Bookwalter et al. 2015). The bark beetles of this subfamily live in symbiosis mainly with ascomycetal fungi belonging to the orders Ophiostomatales: *Ophiostoma*, *Grosmannia*, *Ceratocystiopsis*, and Microascales: *Endoconidiophora*, *Ceratocystis*. While the order Ophiostomatales occurs mainly on conifers, Microascales infests broadleaf trees (Six 2013). The fungi are mainly transmitted on the exoskeleton of beetles, so it is an ectosymbiosis with vertical transmission. However, horizontal transfer within neighboring galleries is also possible. For this reason, it is not clear to what extent mutual co-evolution and co-diversification take place. Associated ophiostomatoid fungi form sticky masses of spores that adhere better to the surface of the beetle body, minimizing losses during transfer to a new substrate (Harrington 2005). Similarly, spores of *Ceratocystis* spp. cannot disperse in water, but they disperse very well in resin, which apparently helps them to inoculate the phloem of conifers (Whitney and Blauel 1972). Some species of bark beetles, for example, various *Dendroctonus* species,

have also developed mycangia for fungal transmission; it is assumed that this is a transition state between phloemophagous and ambrosia beetles. The basidiomycete *Entomocorticium* species associated with *Dendroctonus* species have adapted to symbiosis by probably irreversible flattening of the sterigmata and loss of forcible discharge of spores. As a result, spores accumulate in a thick layer which is grazed by beetles (Hsiau and Harrington 2003).

Figure 4. Fungus-farming insects. Fungus garden of Attini ants of the species *Mycocepurus smithii* (1A) and gongylidia formed by its fungus (1B), adopted from Masiulionis, Rabeling et al. (2014). Macrotermite fungus garden of *Macrotermes bellicosus* with white fungal nodules (2A, 2B) and fruit bodies of *Termitomyces reticulatus* connected to the termite nest (2C), adopted from Boddy (2016). Gallery of ambrosia beetle found in *Microcorthylus* sp. (3A) and terminal globose conidia of the fungus *Geosmithia microcorthyli* on which beetles feed (3B), adopted from Kolařík and Kirkendall (2010).

1.2.2. Dermatophytes

Dermatophyte fungi cause superficial mycoses and only occasionally grow into the deeper layers of the skin. These fungi are members of the order Onygenales and the most common species belong to the genera *Trichophyton*, *Nannizzia*, *Paraphyton*, *Microsporum* and *Arthroderma* (de Hoog, Dukik et al. 2017). Chinnapun (2015) divides the development of skin colonization by a dermatophyte fungus into three phases: adhesion, invasion, and development of the host's immune response (Fig. 5). In the first phase, the spores adhere to the skin by means of adhesins, mannan-containing glycoproteins (Ferreira-Nozawa, Nozawa et al. 2003), which interact with galactose and mannose residues of skin epithelial cells, and with secreted proteases from the subtilisin family. In the second phase, the skin is invaded mainly by keratinase. The skin surface has a pH of about 4.7, which is the result of endogenous processes in the skin and also the presence of associated microorganisms having a defensive function (Matousek and Campbell 2002). An acidic pH is optimal for the enzymes involved in the initial phase of dermatophyte colonization. Later, the pH of the environment increases as the fungus produces ammonia, which allows the activity of other enzymes and the subsequent destruction of host cells (Martinez-Rossi, Peres et al. 2017). Other important enzymes are proteases (endopeptidases, exopeptidases, secreted proteases), lipases, cellulases, and enzymes that are part of the glyoxylate cycle (Achtermann and White 2011). The glyoxylate cycle is important for survival within the host and especially within phagocytes. However, most of these proteases were not upregulated

when the fungus was inoculated directly on to the host's skin *in vivo*. By contrast, secondary metabolites were upregulated. These included antibiotics, which competitively favor the fungus over other skin microorganisms. Other proposed virulence factors are melanization, the formation of arthroconidia (Achtermann and White 2011), upregulation of heat shock proteins (Martinez-Rossi, Jacob et al. 2016), and the creation of a thick biofilm, which protects the fungus from stressors and allows it to cooperate with other microbes (Martinez-Rossi, Peres et al. 2017). During the third phase, the host's immune response develops and the fungus tries to avoid detection by the immune system (Martinez, Oliver et al. 2012), for example, by cell wall remodeling.

Figure 5. Three distinct sub-stages of superficial infection, in which the extent of tissue damage and host response is determined primarily: adhesion (ad hoc, induced); invasion (induced endocytosis, active penetration); damage (deep invasion, destructive activity, inter-epithelial invasion). During stages 1 and 3, the strategies for local nutrient acquisition (an essential process for pathogen infection) adapt to changing environments; adopted from (Hube, Hay et al. 2015).

1.2.3. Ready-made pathogens

Significant fungal pathogens (*Blastomyces dermatitidis*, *Coccidioides* spp., *Cryptococcus neoformans*, and *Histoplasma capsulatum*) that can cause systemic diseases, can survive and reproduce outside the host (Smyth, Schlesinger et al. 2013). For this reason, they are called 'ready-made pathogens' or 'environmental pathogenic fungi'. They use so-called 'dual-use' virulence factors in disease development. Such virulence factors primarily serve the fungus during saprotrophic growth; however, the fungus can also utilize them during the pathogenic phase. These factors include melanin synthesis, the ability to switch between yeast and hyphal growth, and especially the production of phospholipase, protease, and urease (Casadevall, Steenbergen et al. 2003; Muggia, Ametrano et al. 2020). In addition to nutrient uptake, ureases have various functions during pathogenesis (e.g., alkalization of the environment) (Cox, Mukherjee et al. 2000; Olszewski, Noverr et al. 2004; Vylkova and Lorenz 2014; Vylkova 2017). Phospholipases break down one or more ester bonds in glycerophospholipids, releasing free fatty acids, thereby destabilizing cell membranes.

1.3. Main hypothesis and aims

The main hypothesis of my thesis is that species with a similar ecological strategy are exposed to similar selection pressures, making it possible to find a similar adaptive response. After separating the influence of phylogenetic relatedness, it is possible to reveal adaptations typical of individual ecological groups.

Aims:

1. Identify the selection pressures and adaptations associated with a given ecology of fungi.
2. Compare the results obtained from my comparative studies with available data from genome sequencing or transcriptome analysis.
3. By comparing the obtained data with the available literature, suggest whether more generally valid trends can be observed in the evolution of the pathogens and mutualists studied.

Two model genera of fungi, *Geosmithia* (Hypocreales) and *Pseudogymnoascus* (Incertae sedis, Pseudoeurotiaceae), were selected. In both genera, significant ecological transitions happened over the course of evolution. These genera comprise species that are free-living or tightly associated with their hosts as mutualists or pathogens. In both model genera, partial hypotheses and goals were set, which elaborate the main hypothesis and goals of this dissertation. These partial goals are stated at the ends of the following sections that introduce both fungal genera studied (sections 1.3.1. and 1.3.2.).

1.3.1. The genus *Geosmithia*

The genus *Geosmithia* (Hypocreales, Sordariomycetes, Ascomycota) includes fungi associated with subcortical insects (Scolytinae and Bostrichidae) (Kolařík, Hulcr et al. 2017). *Geosmithia* conidia are hydrophobic but not sticky, which is a typical adaptation in insect-associated fungi such as entomopathogens (*Beauveria*, *Metarhizium*, *Lecanicillium*) or ophiostomatoid fungi (Ophiostomatales, Microascales). Despite the absence of this adaptation, the genus *Geosmithia* is a very widespread and abundant symbiont of subcortical insects (Kolařík, Hulcr et al. 2017). *Geosmithia* species are typical associates of bark beetles that feed on hardwoods and on plants from the juniper family (Juniperaceae). For the pine tree family (Pinaceae), they are often associated with vectors feeding on thin branches, whereas ophiostomatal fungi are typically found on vectors preferring tree trunks or thicker branches, (Kolařík and Jankowiak 2013). The reason for the different niche preferences of these two groups of fungi is unknown. Species of the genus *Geosmithia* have different degrees of vector specificity. Many species are generalists with a wide range of vectors, invading a wide range of plant families, and sometimes living also as endophytes or soil or plant saprotrophs (McPherson, Erbilgin et al. 2013). Others are specialists restricted to beetles associated only with trees of the family Pinaceae (Kolařík and Jankowiak 2013), or beetles infecting specific hardwood species such as *Geosmithia* sp. 12 found mostly in *Fraxinus*, *G.* sp. 8 in *Quercus* (Kolařík, Kubátová et al. 2008), *G. ulmacea* in *Ulmus* (Pepori, Kolařík et al. 2015) and *G. morbida* in *Juglans* (Kolařík, Freeland et al. 2011). The ecological role of *Geosmithia* species is mostly unknown. An exception is the pathogenic species *G. morbida* transmitted by the beetle *Pityophthorus juglandis*, which causes the dieback of *Juglans nigra* in the USA (Tisserat, Cranshaw et al. 2009; Kolařík, Freeland et al. 2011) and three ambrosia species: *G. eupagioceri*, *G. microcorthyli*, and *G. cnesini*, which are nutritional symbionts of the ambrosia beetles *Eupagiocerus dentipes*, *Microcorthylus* sp. and *Cnesinus lecontei* (Kolařík and Kirkendall 2010). These ambrosia fungi share the morphological characteristics of ambrosia fungi, in that they form a

yeast-like phase and palisades of hyphae with large terminal conidia. Although the ecology of these species is well known, little is known about the adaptations that made it possible (Schuelke, Wu et al. 2017). The genus *Geosmithia* represents a unique model for the study of fungal adaptations leading to specialization and for discerning between transitions to mutualism or parasitism.

1.3.1.1. Pathogenesis of *Geosmithia morbida*

In 2001, a dieback of black walnut (*Juglans nigra*) was recorded on the west coast of the USA in the state of Colorado. In 2010, the disease spread east to Tennessee and a year later to Virginia and Pennsylvania (Griffin 2015). In 2013, a dieback of walnuts was also recorded in northern Italy, Europe (Montecchio and Faccoli 2014) (Fig. 6). It was soon discovered that the death of trees was caused by the aggressive feeding behavior of the beetle *Pityophthorus juglandis* and the extensive formation of necrosis by the fungus *G. morbida*, which is transmitted by the beetle (Tisserat, Cranshaw et al. 2009). *P. juglandis* is a native species of North America occurring on several native walnut species (e.g., *Juglans major*) in areas of New Mexico, Arizona, and Mexico, where it is not associated with significant tree death. However, *P. juglandis* is able to colonize all North American woody plants of the genus *Juglans* and *Pterocarya* (Juglandaceae) (Utley, Nguyen et al. 2013; Hishinuma, Dallara et al. 2015) that differ in susceptibility (Utley, Nguyen et al. 2013). The most susceptible to the disease is *J. nigra*, a species native to the eastern United States, that is planted worldwide. The dieback of the black walnut is probably a result of the expansion of the beetle's range and its aggressive feeding on naive species of walnut. Other factors influencing the resistance of walnuts are abiotic conditions such as drought and soil water potential (Griffin 2015). While the humid climate in eastern natural habitats gives walnuts greater resistance to the disease, the drier west coast leads to high and rapid tree mortality and the tree dies from the first symptoms within two years. *P. juglandis* is attracted by volatile substances of both *G. morbida* and walnut trees (Blood, Klingeman et al. 2018). It is more attracted to genotypes of walnuts with a high content of α - and β -pinene. Surprisingly, ethanol, otherwise a common attractant, does not attract *P. juglandis*. An interesting finding was that beetle populations were most attracted to *G. morbida* strains from the same locality, which means that co-evolution may be taking place between them. However, Kolařík, Freeland et al. (2011) and Zerillo, Ibarra Caballero et al. (2014) found no correlation between haplotypes of *G. morbida* and geography or walnut species, indicating that *G. morbida* was introduced several times from different localities probably by transport of infected wood. *G. morbida* causes necrosis under the bark in the phloem, called canker (Tisserat, Cranshaw et al. 2009), hence the name of the condition, the thousand cankers disease. At first, the disease is localized, but later it spreads to the cambium, lesions enlarge, interconnect, and finally cause the death of the tree. However, massive beetle colonization is needed to kill a healthy tree (Utley, Nguyen et al. 2013). Genome sequencing has shown that about one-third of the proteins of this fungus are homologous to proteins with known pathogenic function (Aggarwal, Westbrook et al. 2016). However, this amount is the same as in the saprotrophic species *G. flava* and *G. putterillii* (Schuelke, Wu et al. 2017). Comparative genomics has revealed paralogs of three genes that are not present in saprotrophic species. These are the genes for hydantoinase B/oxoprolinase, aldehyde dehydrogenase, and the ABC-2-type transporter of the ATP-binding cassette protein. Additionally, a total of 38 genes under positive selection were detected, of which only two were identified in another pathogen associated with bark beetles, *Grosmannia clavigera*. All these genes are involved in protection against oxidative stress, detoxification, drug resistance, heat-shock response, or DNA repair. This may be

important in overcoming plant defenses during pathogenesis. Competition tests have shown that *G. morbida* often produces diffuse metabolites with antibiotic activity; however, strains TN3-46 and TN-34 belonging to the *Trichoderma harzianum* species complex were able to overgrow and subsequently sporulate on *G. morbida* mycelium in culture, suggesting potential use of these strains for the biological control of the thousand canker disease (Gazis, Poplawski et al. 2018).

Figure 6. Global distribution of the thousand cankers disease (A), map obtained from (Wilstermann, Hoppe et al. 2020), cankers caused by *G. morbida* (B), *G. morbida* sporulating in a gallery of *P. juglandis* (C), both photographs obtained from (Tisserat, Cranshaw et al. 2009).

1.3.1.2. Partial goals of my thesis

Based on the actual knowledge of ecology of the genus *Geosmithia* we posed following questions that are addressed in my thesis.

1. Was the increase in the size of conidia of ambrosia fungi accompanied by an enlargement of their genomes?
2. What are the physiological and biochemical adaptations of ambrosia fungi with respect to their obligatory nutritional symbiosis with ambrosia beetles?
3. Do ambrosia fungi have antibiotic properties that ensure their dominance in ambrosia beetle galleries?
4. Is the enzymatic apparatus affected by the ecological niche width of *Geosmithia* species?
5. What are the mechanisms of the pathogenesis of *G. morbida*?

1.3.2. Characteristics of the genus *Pseudogymnoascus*

Fungi of the genus *Pseudogymnoascus* (Pseudoeurotiaceae, Leotiomyces, Ascomycota) are saprotrophic psychrotolerant or psychrophilic. Exceptions are *P. pannorum*, which may occasionally cause mycoses, and *P. destructans*. *Pseudogymnoascus destructans* is a major pathogen that decimates American bat populations during the hibernation period. It causes white nose syndrome, named after the growth of white hyphae on the skin of bats. Now, we have data from the whole genome sequencing of this pathogen (Chibucos, Crabtree et al. 2013; Palmer, Drees et al. 2018) and several transcriptomic analyzes of both the pathogen (Frank 2017; Reeder, Palmer et al. 2017; Donaldson, Davy et al. 2018; Chaturvedi, DeFiglio et al. 2018) and infected bats (Field, Johnson et al. 2015; Davy, Donaldson et al. 2017). However, we still do not fully understand the pathogenesis of *P. destructans*, and many questions remain unanswered.

Figure 7. Time-lapse map of the spread of the WNS between the years 2006 and 2021 and a photograph of an infected bat, both obtained from the websites of the White-Nose Syndrome Response Team (whitenosesyndrome.org).

1.3.2.1. Origin and spread of white nose syndrome

The white nose syndrome (WNS) was observed for the first time in 2006 at Howe's Cave in New York State (Blehert, Hicks et al. 2009); however, a recent study dates the arrival of *P. destructans* in the USA to 1999 (Thapa, Turner et al. 2021). It spread from this area throughout the middle east of the United States to Canada. Since 2016 it has also been present on the west coast of the United States (Lorch, Palmer et al. 2016). At present, *P. destructans* is spread across 39 US states and seven Canadian provinces (Fig. 7). *P. destructans* was introduced to the United States from Eurasia by humans (Leopardi, Blake et al. 2015; Zukal, Bandouchova et al. 2016; Drees, Lorch et al. 2017; Trivedi, Vanderwolf et al. 2017), which is supported by its clonal reproduction accompanied by very low genetic diversity of *P. destructans* isolates in the USA compared to the situation in Europe, where both mating types are present and reproduction is probably heterothallic (Palmer, Kubátová et al. 2014). Although the WNS has been observed in a number of European countries, it has not been associated with bat

mass mortality (Zukal, Bandouchova et al. 2016), indicating long-term co-evolution of the pathogen and the host (Leopardi, Blake et al. 2015; Drees, Lorch et al. 2017). In Europe, bats also form much smaller hibernating colonies than in the USA, which greatly reduces the infectiousness (Frick, Puechmaille et al. 2016). Contact between long-term co-evolved and thus adapted *P. destructans* from Eurasia with naive populations of American bats causes their massive extinction. However, individual bat species differ in their resistance to the disease (Turner, Reeder et al. 2011). The different degree of resistance of bats to the disease can be caused by various environmental factors, such as humidity and temperature in caves or the size of the bats' body (Hayman, Pulliam et al. 2016), or a different composition of fatty acids in the bats' epidermis (Ingala, Ravenelle et al. 2017). Although one strain of *P. destructans* is spread throughout North America, different gene mutations and genotypic variation produced by recombination are found between isolates (Forsythe, Vanderwolf et al. 2021) and the isolates show some phenotypic variability, for example differences in growth rate or pigmentation (Khankhet, Vanderwolf et al. 2014; Forsythe, Giglio et al. 2018).

1.3.2.2. *The course of the WNS*

Lorch, Meteyer et al. (2011) were the first to identify *P. destructans* as the causal agent of the disease and subsequent mass extinction of bats in the United States. They also showed that the disease spreads through physical contact. The pathogen *P. destructans* has been demonstrated histologically in most infected bats (Blehert, Hicks et al. 2009), where its hyphae replace the hair follicles and the sebaceous and sweat glands, reaching the basement membrane. The fungus further damages the epidermis of the ears and wings. The entire skin lesion is further characterized by autofluorescent spots, which are used as a means of identifying the WNS (Turner, Meteyer et al. 2014). Disruption of the skin and glands in the membranes of the wings of bats causes fatal water loss, which makes them wake up and fly outside of their caves (Reeder, Frank et al. 2012) to replenish water supplies (Cryan, Meteyer et al. 2010). Bats exhaust a lot of energy to achieve normal body temperature and metabolism (Boyles and Willis 2010). Depleted fat reserves then cause their subsequent starvation (Cryan, Meteyer et al. 2010). In more than half of the infested bats studied, no dermal fat reserves needed to survive hibernation were found (Blehert, Hicks et al. 2009). Water loss can also have a major impact on blood physiology, leading to reduction in plasma volume (hypovolaemia) or metabolic acidosis (Warnecke, Turner et al. 2013; Verant, Meteyer et al. 2014). Even if infected bats get rid of the fungal hyphae during the summer, their wings remain damaged, which affects the quality of their flight and thus their survival (Reichard and Kunz 2009).

A study of the presence of WNS during the year (Fig. 8) (Langwig, Frick et al. 2015) showed that the highest prevalence of *P. destructans* in bats is at the beginning of their hibernation, specifically in autumn and early winter. During winter, the fungus grows on the bodies of bats and reaches the highest biomass load at the end of winter when hibernation ends. On the contrary, during summer, when the young are born, the prevalence decreases and fungal hyphae disappear from bat skin, due to the psychrophilic nature of the fungus. The authors discuss that such a course of prevalence has a serious impact on the size of bat populations, as the highest mortality occurs before the birth of pups. On the other hand, the spread of the disease to new localities should be reduced by the absence of visible fungal growth on the surface of the bat bodies during the active flying season in the summer. However, bats can also be infected from an environmental source, as *P. destructans* has also been isolated from the soil sediment of caves long after the infected bats left their wintering grounds. This

means that the fungus can survive without its host (Lorch, Muller et al. 2013; Urbina, Chestnut et al. 2021). For this reason Smyth, Schlesinger et al. (2013) have suggested to list *P. destructans* among ready-made pathogens. This increases the risk of host extinction, as *P. destructans* is not directly regulated by host density (Verant, Bohuski et al. 2018).

Figure 8. The seasonal pattern of *P. destructans* and its bat hosts is depicted, adopted from (Hoyt, Kilpatrick et al. 2021). The internal circle shows the abundance and growth phases of *P. destructans* during different stages in bat life history. The outer circle shows the seasonal life history of a typical temperate hibernating bat.

1.3.2.3. Searching for virulence factors

The severity of the WNS in American bat populations has sparked efforts to understand the virulence factors of *P. destructans*. The following chapters summarize the knowledge gained from genome, transcriptomes, and physiological analyses.

Whole-genome sequencing

Pseudogymnoascus destructans has a larger genome size, 35.8 Mb, than related species of the genus. The increase in genome size was accompanied by a significant expansion of repetitive sequences, which make up 38.2% of the genome (Palmer, Drees et al. 2018). Its evolution was

accompanied by significant gene losses, but also by the acquisition of unique proteins whose functions are unknown. Compared to the other *Pseudogymnoascus* species analyzed, *P. destructans* has a markedly reduced number of genes encoding CAZymes and secreted proteins, including subtilisin serine protease. The number of secondary metabolite pathways is similarly reduced.

Physiology of Pseudogymnoascus destructans

A significant reduction in enzymatic pathways has also been found when comparing the enzymatic abilities of *P. destructans* with those of cave fungi, including species of the same genus (Reynolds and Barton 2014; Chaturvedi, DeFiglio et al. 2018). *P. destructans* probably cannot use complex substrates such as keratin, chitin, or lignin as a source of nutrients and uses mainly proteins and lipids for growth (Raudabaugh and Miller 2013). Subtilisin-like serine proteases (O'Donoghue, Knudsen et al. 2015; Pannkuk, Risch et al. 2015), which cleave collagen, are the most important proteases secreted by *P. destructans*. However, their significance for pathogenesis is not clear (Reeder, Palmer et al. 2017; Donaldson, Davy et al. 2018). Other possible virulence factors are the production of siderophores (Mascuch, Moree et al. 2015), which sequester iron from the environment, and the overproduction of riboflavin (vitamin B), which exhibits autofluorescence similar to that seen in skin lesions (Flieger, Bandouchova et al. 2016).

P. destructans is a psychrophilic fungus that grows in the temperature range of 3–19°C, with an optimum between 12 and 15°C (Gargas, Trest et al. 2009; Chaturvedi, Springer et al. 2010; Verant, Boyles et al. 2012). At higher temperatures, the fungus forms septa, thickens the cell walls of the hyphae and forms arthrospores, and chlamydospores (Verant, Boyles et al. 2012). Forsythe, Giglio et al. (2018) have shown that these arthrospores can survive for up to three weeks at 23 °C. A high proportion of unsaturated fatty acids and triacylglycerols in dry weight is an adaptation of this fungus to a cold environment (Pannkuk, Blair et al. 2014). However, this makes *P. destructans* sensitive to water availability. The optimal relative humidity for its growth is around 80%, and if the humidity drops below 70%, the growth stops (Marroquin, Lavine et al. 2017). The humidity of the hibernation sites is between 60–100%, so some are more prone to the development of WNS than others. *P. destructans* is sensitive to UV-C light because of the loss of the UVE1 gene, which is involved in DNA repair after UV light destruction (Palmer, Drees et al. 2018).

Transcriptome analyses

Transcriptome analyses of *P. destructans* growing on artificial media and during pathogenic growth on bats have revealed a large effect of the growth substrate, especially the nitrogen source, on the spectrum of expressed genes (Reeder, Palmer et al. 2017; Donaldson, Davy et al. 2018). Based on these data, the authors speculate that the overexpression of certain genes during pathogenesis may not only be related to the pathogenesis itself, but also to the available spectrum of nutrients. For example, the high production of enzymes such as lipases (upregulated lipase 1 and squalene monooxygenase) could only reflect the high proportion of lipids in bat skin (Frank 2017). Another proposed virulence factor is the upregulation of heat-shock proteins. Heat-shock proteins may help the fungus to cope with the occasional return of bats to a euthermic state during hibernation (Reeder, Palmer et al. 2017), or other stressors (Donaldson, Davy et al. 2018). Proteins with high similarity to aspartic protease of *Aspergillus oryzae* and vacuolar protease AspF2 of *A. fumigatus*, both of which are involved in the penetration of epithelial cells, are also upregulated. AspF2 is the major allergen of *A. fumigatus* (Dasari, Shopova et al. 2018), thanks to which *A. fumigatus* avoids the host's immune

response. Further adaptations are linked with the acquisition of nutrients (mainly nitrogen and peptides) and micronutrients important for maintaining homeostasis (mainly ions of Zn, Fe, and Cu, which occur in limited quantities in the bat bodies). Surprisingly, more proteases were produced in culture than during WNS, including subtilisin-like proteases that were previously considered a virulence factor (Reeder, Palmer et al. 2017). Interestingly, despite the established clonality and considerable genetic uniformity of *P. destructans* in the USA, isolates of this fungus invading bats in more distant localities showed slightly different gene transcription, which means that environmental conditions may be important (Reeder, Palmer et al. 2017).

Unlike infected American bats, European bats do not show any immune response at the transcriptome level to fight the pathogen (Davy, Donaldson et al. 2017). This indicates a completely different biological response of Eurasian bats to the pathogen, e.g., the production of fatty acids that inhibit the growth of a pathogen (Frank, Ingala et al. 2016), which is a result of the long-term co-evolution between them. During mammalian hibernation, leukocyte counts decrease by 90% (Bouma, Carey et al. 2010). Occasional interruptions of hibernation are accompanied by a return of an innate immune response (mediated by neutrophils and monocytes), which can lead to an inflammatory response, reactive oxygen species production, and the slowing of the fungal infection. However, in the absence of an effective adaptive immune response (lymphocytes increase to only 50% of the normal level), the pathogen is not completely eliminated. Increased innate immune responses and transcription of genes required for wound healing have been observed in the American bat species *Myotis lucifugus* at the transcriptome level (Field, Johnson et al. 2015) and also at the proteomic level (Hecht-Höger, Braun et al. 2020). The transcription of pattern recognition receptors like C-type lectin receptors and toll-like receptors, which interact with the presence of fungal cell wall components, are also increased. The cell wall of fungi consists of an inner chitin wall, a middle β -glucan wall and an outer mannose wall. Organisms, including mammals, have receptors for these components, which in turn trigger an immune response. Transcriptome analysis of *P. destructans* revealed upregulation of genes involved in fungal cell wall rearrangements (Reeder, Palmer et al. 2017), by which the pathogen is probably trying to evade the host immune system. Bats also produce cytokines that act in a pro-inflammatory response. Inflammation causes pain and itching that wakes bats, increasing their metabolism, and reducing fat reserves. Thus, increased innate immunity accompanied by the absence of adaptive immunity leads to depletion of the bats' reserves without effective suppression of the fungal infection. In spring, at the end of hibernation, a great increase in neutrophils could lead to a strong anti-inflammatory response called the immune reconstruction inflammatory syndrome, which causes further tissue destruction (Frick, Puechmaille et al. 2016). For this reason, activation of the immune response during hibernation may have a negative effect on bat health.

1.3.2.4. Management and resistance of bats

In some populations of *M. lucifugus*, the extinction rate and pathogen load at the end of hibernation are slowing down (Lilley, Johnson et al. 2016; Langwig, Hoyt et al. 2017), indicating the bats' possible resistance to the WNS. These bats do not wake up and fly out during hibernation more often than usual before the occurrence of the WNS. Resistance might be gained, for example, through the production of a different spectrum of fatty acids or by alteration of the microbial community in the skin. These bats hibernate in the colder parts of the cave, which allows them to lower their body temperature even more and thus their metabolism. By this behavior, they save fat reserves and at the

same time slow down the growth of *P. destructans*. It is not clear whether this behavior is a reaction of bats to contact with *P. destructans* or whether they always behaved in this way, which allowed them to survive. Physical removal of sediments from caves (Meyer, Stevens et al. 2016), application of volatiles (Padhi, Dias et al. 2017), bacteria and fungi (Micalizzi, Mack et al. 2017), abiotic factors like UV-C light (Palmer, Drees et al. 2018), or vaccination (Rocke, Kingstad-Bakke et al. 2019) have been found to be able to inhibit the growth of *P. destructans*. However, it is not clear how these approaches, when used in hibernacula, would affect the cave ecosystem.

1.3.2.5. *Partial goals of my thesis*

Based on the actual knowledge of ecology of the genus *Pseudogymnoascus* we posed following questions that are addressed in my thesis.

1. Is the enzymatic profile of *P. destructans* different from those of cave fungi and other *Pseudogymnoascus* species?
2. Does *P. destructans* share common features with dermatophyte fungi? If so, how could they be involved in the virulence of *P. destructans*?
3. What abiotic factors limit the survival of *P. destructans* conidia and what effect do they have on the spread of the disease?

2. Main results

My dissertation brings together five publications in IF journals. The first four concern the evolutionary ecology of the genus *Geosmithia*, the fifth the ecophysiology of the genus *Pseudogymnoascus*.

2.1. Adaptive traits of the genus *Geosmithia*

Members of the genus *Geosmithia* are widespread symbionts of bark beetles. However, we have only little knowledge of their biology and adaptations. The ecological diversity of the genus *Geosmithia* enables us to study adaptations of ambrosia fungi, specialists to the plant family or genus, and the mechanisms of phytopathogenesis. At the same time, these life strategies evolved multiple times independently during the evolution of *Geosmithia*. Therefore, properties specific to a given ecological group are considered adaptations of these species.

The method used to study the genome size in the genus *Geosmithia* was flow cytometry (FCM). The FCM methodology is well developed in botany and zoology, where it is also widely used (e.g., Doležal, Greilhuber et al. 2007). FCM has been applied to a much lesser extent in the study of fungal genome size, although it is gaining popularity (Bleichrodt and Read 2019). Therefore, the methodology of flow cytometry in mycology requires optimization. Publication P1 presents a summary of the methodologies used so far for determining genome sizes in fungi by flow cytometry, provides an optimized FCM methodology for analyzing fungi, and introduces the new fungal standard *Aspergillus fumigatus* CEA10 for absolute genome size inference. In publication P2, we used the newly developed FCM methodology for genome size estimations to analyze 21 *Geosmithia* species. We confirmed that even in fungi, there may be a positive correlation between genome and cell size, which has so far been studied only marginally (e.g., Jorgensen, Edgington et al. 2007; Neumann and Nurse 2007). This idea is further developed into the potential impact of genome/cell size on fungal ecology. Analogically to plants and animals, we suggest that the r-K continuum concept may also be used for fungi, where a trade-off between investments into the quantity or quality of spores is observed. The dependence of *Geosmithia* fungi on their vectors ranges from weakly associated generalist, through long-term co-evolved conifer specialists, to obligatorily associated ambrosia species. We hypothesize that the nutritional nature of the symbiosis and the release from aerodynamic constraints, given by the obligatory insect transfer, enabled the selection for large and nutritionally rich conidia, which is the most pronounced in ambrosial *Geosmithia*.

Publication P3 is important as it validates the use of long-term *in vitro* preserved cultures for physiological studies. In publication P4, we consider the accumulation of oleic fatty acid to be another adaptation of ambrosia fungi, although its ecological role is not fully understood. Although ambrosial *G. microcorthyli* was a strong producer of antibiotics, this trait is not considered an adaptation associated with the ambrosia lifestyle, as it is shared by other *Geosmithia* species regardless of their ecology. Niche width affects the enzymatic potential of *Geosmithia* species, which is especially evident in species specialized in conifers, which have lost a significant part of metabolic pathways compared to generalists during their long co-evolution with their vector and host. An adaptive feature of the phytopathogen *G. morbida* is a reduction in metabolic diversity and the production of enzymes that cleave lignocellulose, which we consider a virulence factor.

2.2. Comparative study of the genus *Pseudogymnoascus*

The genus *Pseudogymnoascus* includes mainly saprotrophic psychrophilic fungi. An exception is the pathogenic species *P. destructans*, which decimates American bat populations. Publication P5 uses comparative ecophysiology to search for adaptive traits related to the unique lifestyle. The enzymatic profile and ability of *P. destructans* conidia to survive under stressful conditions was compared with saprotrophic species of the genus *Pseudogymnoascus*, with unrelated saprotrophic cave and outdoor fungi and with dermatophytes. Our assumption is that the traits that distinguish *P. destructans* from cave fungi, including *Pseudogymnoascus* spp., are under selection pressure and are an adaptation to pathogenic growth on the bat body. Common features with dermatophytes may indicate their involvement in virulence. A comparison with saprotrophic species then gives an idea, which factors limit the spread of the disease in the outdoor environment.

The main contribution of publication P5 is an ecophysiological comparison of a large number of *P. destructans* strains with fungi of various phylogenetic and ecological relatedness. Comparative ecophysiology revealed a significant reduction in the assimilation abilities of *P. destructans* compared to all the other fungi tested. *P. destructans* was characterized by massive growth on the detergent Tween 80 and by the production of extracellular lipases. For this reason, we consider lipases a virulence factor that allows fungal hyphae to penetrate and infect bat skin. Degradation of urea during the growth of *P. destructans* has led us to the hypothesis that, similarly to dermatophytes, this activity may have a function not only in nutrient uptake, but also in pathogenesis by locally increasing the pH in affected tissues. Although *P. destructans* increased the pH of the growth medium in an *in vitro* experiment above the physiological value by urea degradation, the other cave fungi showed a similar ability. In subsequent experiments, we have tried to measure the pH directly in the lesions on the bat wings using pH-sensitive fluorescent dyes. However, because of methodological problems (see Appendix 1), I was unable to experimentally verify the alkalization in the lesions. The conidia of *P. destructans* showed much greater resistance to stressful abiotic factors than hyphae. Furthermore, simulating the changes in temperature on the body surface of bats during the day and night after leaving their hibernacula significantly prolonged the viability of conidia at temperatures above 30 °C. During spring, after the end of hibernation, bats begin to fly actively, but they occasionally return to hibernation sites. Therefore, it is possible that some time after waking up, this behavior may spread the disease to nearby uninfected hibernacula.

3. Original publications

3.1. P1: Veselská, Tereza et al. (2014). *Cytometry Part A*: 85, 854-861

Application of flow cytometry for genome size determination in *Geosmithia* fungi: A comparison of methods

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ABSTRACT

Genome size has played an important role in the evolution of plants and animals because changes in genome size seem to accompany if not facilitate evolutionary adaptation to environmental conditions. Flow cytometry (FCM) is a widespread method for determining genome size thanks to its high accuracy and speed of measurements. Nevertheless, only a few comparative studies of FCM methods exist in the field of mycology, and reviews are absent. In this study, we compared the suitability of several concentrations and RNase A incubation times, fixatives and buffers for estimating genome size in fungi. We chose the genus *Geosmithia* as a model filamentous fungus. We also introduced a new standard, *Aspergillus fumigatus* CEA10, to determine absolute genome size. We found FCM to be an appropriate method for measuring genome size in fungi, but optimization steps showed that incorrect propidium iodide staining of nuclei can overestimate genome size due to cytoplasmic staining. We identified fixation with methanol:glacial acetic acid (3:1 v/v), 10% DMSO, 0.1% Triton-X 100, and 5 mM EDTA in combination with Tris-MgCl₂ buffer as the best treatment.

Keywords:

Fungi, Genome size, Flow cytometry, Confocal microscopy, Standard, Buffer, Fixation, RNase

INTRODUCTION

Genome size correlates with many organismal traits such as cell size, metabolism or growth rate (1–5), and it seems that changes in genome size accompany if not facilitate evolutionary adaptations to environmental conditions (1,6–8). Flow cytometry (FCM) is a widespread method for determining genome size due to its high accuracy and speed of measurements. The use of FCM in studies of fungi is limited by methodical problems linked to their small genome size. In contrast to plant research (9–17), only a few methodical publications exist in the field of mycology (18–21), and reviews are absent. Another problem is the absence of suitable standards (22). For this reason, some authors (e.g., 23,24) have used chicken red blood cells (2,445 Mb/2C), but their genome size differs from that of fungi by an order of magnitude. A threefold difference in genome size between the

standard and the sample can lead to significant errors (13). *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* has been used as another standard, but it has been found to be unsuitable because of chromosome length polymorphism and the presence of an active cell cycle (20). Anderson et al. (21) have proposed *Puccinia graminis* f.sp. *tritici* and *Sclerotinia sclerotiorum* as standards for rust fungi, which tend to have larger genomes. The average genome size of fungi is 37 Mb (median 28 Mb) (25), so it is of high priority to find a new standard for FCM of fungi that is close to these genome sizes. There is a limited array of fully sequenced fungal species that could serve as potential standards. Furthermore, these species must fulfill certain specific requirements. For example, their cultivation must be easy and hazard-free, they must grow quickly, produce masses of uninucleate and single-celled spores, and their genome must be stable. Fungi with large genomes (e.g., rusts and other basidiomycota) are mostly not cultivable, and fungi with small genomes (e.g., yeasts) have a complex life cycle and produce multinucleate budding cells. Also potentially applicable are filamentous fungi, which often produce conidia. We selected *Aspergillus* fungi from this group. It is, moreover, necessary to compare the methodical approaches used in mycological flow cytometric studies.

In this study, we compared the suitability of several RNase A concentrations and incubation times, fixatives, and buffers. We selected the chemicals based on published studies on fungi (Supporting Information 1) and plants. We included chemicals used in plant research due to their wide use and advanced development (12–15). We chose the genus *Geosmithia* as a model filamentous fungus. This genus includes fungi living in association with bark beetles, which infest a broad spectrum of broad-leaved trees and conifers (26–33). One species, *G. morbida*, is a proven phytopathogen responsible for massive diebacks of black walnut (29,34). Several species (e.g., *G. eupagioceri*) live in nutritional symbiosis with ambrosia beetles (28). *Geosmithia* fungi produce hydroxylated anthraquinones as pigmented secondary metabolites (35,36) and other undetermined pigments. Secondary metabolites are known to have a large impact on measurements of genome size (propidium iodide (PI) binding to DNA; e.g., 37).

The aims of this work were as follows: (1) to compare several methodical approaches covering the most commonly used fixatives and buffers in mycology and plant research; (2) to develop the best method for assessing genome size in selected *Geosmithia* species; and (3) to find an appropriate standard for genome size estimation in fungi.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Fungal Material

Geosmithia flava (Culture Collection of Fungi (CCF) CCF3354), *Geosmithia* sp. 8 (CCF4528), *Geosmithia* sp. 24 (CCF4525), and *Geosmithia* sp. 25 (CCF4205) were chosen to investigate the effects of the chemicals used. When concentrations of RNase A were tested, *Geosmithia* sp. 26 (CCF4223) was included instead of *G. flava* (CCF3354). This selection covers species that produce various pigments, have different ecologies (phloem of conifers or broad-leaved trees), and are known to exhibit intrastain variance in spore sizes (*Geosmithia* sp. 24 and *Geosmithia* sp. 26). These strains are deposited in the CCF in Prague. *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* (BY4743aa), *Aspergillus niger* (CBS513.88, NRRL350), *A. fumigatus* (Af293, CEA10), and *A. aculeatus* (CBS172.66) were tested as standards. Fungi were grown on 2° malt extract agar until a sufficient level of sporulation was reached. *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* was cultivated on yeast peptone dextrose agar until the nutrients in the medium were depleted and cells entered the stationary phase in which cells do not divide.

Experimental Design

The initial step included the most common chemicals used in published mycological studies (see Supporting Information). Only the PI concentration used was adopted from plant research (12). The chemicals tested are listed in Table 1, accompanied by their abbreviations and citations. We studied the suitability of concentration and duration of RNase A incubation, the type and time of fixation, and the buffer type. Fixation is known to modify the chromatin structure and the accessibility of DNA to fluorochromes (12). Fixation is consistently part of preparing fungal samples for FCM analysis, but a comparison of the effects of different fixatives on the quality of measurements is missing in the literature. We evaluated the suitability of treatments by comparing robust per cent coefficient of variation (rCV), the localization of PI to nuclei versus cytoplasmic staining and, in the case of buffers, the variability of fluorescent intensity among measurement replications. We carried out all optimization steps in three replications, with the exception of RNase A concentration, which we evaluated only once. We distinguished three levels of PI localization based on observations under a confocal microscope (Fig. 1). We performed the optimization steps sequentially and finally designed the best protocol for FCM genome size estimation in *Geosmithia*.

Table 1. Chemicals used in optimization steps.

Fixatives			Buffers		
Abbr.	Composition	Citation	Abbr.	Composition	Citation
4F	4% formaldehyde in TE buffer	(23)	PBS	137 mM NaCl, 2.7 mM KCl, 10 mM Na ₂ PO ₄	(24, 38, 39)
MA	methanol:acetic acid (3:1 v/v)	(40)	TE^a	10 mM Tris HCl, 1 mM EDTA, pH 8	(41)
MA+	methanol:glacial acetic acid (3:1 v/v), 10% DMSO, 0.1% Triton X-100, 5mM EDTA	(42)	Tris-MgCl₂	200 mM Tris, 4 mM MgCl ₂ ·6H ₂ O, 0.5% (v/v) Triton X-100, pH 7.5	(43)
70E	70% ethanol in water	(18, 19, 39, 44-50)	Otto's b.^b	Otto I: 100 mM citric acid, 0.5% (v/v) Tween 20 (pH 2–3) Otto II: 400 mM Na ₂ PO ₄ ·12H ₂ O (pH 8–9)	(51)
95E	95% ethanol in water	(52)	LB01	15 mM Tris, 2 mM Na ₂ EDTA, 0.5 mM spermine·4HCl,	(10)
90M	90% methanol in water	(40)		80 mM KCl, 20 mM NaCl, 0.1% (v/v) Triton X-100	

^aFCM studies in fungi often use Tris buffer (45,49) or Tris buffer with a chromatin stabilizer or/and chelator agent (18,23,24,44,50). In this study, we used TE buffer following (41).

^bStaining of nuclei was conducted in mixture of Otto I and II 1:3 to achieve pH 7.5.

Figure 1. Examples of PI localization levels: (A) (-) insufficient staining with high cytoplasmic staining, (B and C) (0) insufficient staining with low cytoplasmic staining or with cells in one sample that differ in PI localization, and (D) (+) high degree of PI localization in the nuclei.

Cell Staining

Fungal spores were collected into tubes with 20% glycerol, and their concentration was adjusted to $3-5 \times 10^6$ cells/mL. Optimization steps and genome size estimation methods are described in detail below. In brief, 1 mL of cell suspension in an Eppendorf tube was centrifuged for 10 min to create a firm pellet. The supernatant was removed, and 500 μ L of fixative was added. The fixative was washed out from the cells with detergent and cells were incubated with RNase A (MP Biomedicals, Solon, USA) in a buffer. Finally, the fluorescent dye PI (Fluka, Glossop, England) was added at a concentration of 50 mg/mL. Staining was performed at room temperature in the dark for 30 min. The cell solution was homogenized by pipetting at each resuspending step to avoid cell clumping.

Methods of Optimization Steps

General approach (GA).

- a. Centrifuge 1 mL of cell suspension in an Eppendorf tube for 10 min at 14,000 rpm.
- b. Discard supernatant, add 500 μ L of fixative and resuspend the cells by pipetting.
- c. Incubate cells with constant stirring (300 rpm) at 4 °C.
- d. Centrifuge tube for 5 min at 14,000 rpm.
- e. Wash fixative from cells with the detergent Triton X-100 (500 μ L, 0.1%).
- f. Centrifuge tube for 5 min at 14,000 rpm.
- g. Discard detergent, add 950 μ L of buffer with RNase A, and incubate cells with constant stirring at 300 rpm at 37 °C.
- h. Add 50 mg/mL of PI and stain nuclei at room temperature for 30 min.

Effects of RNase A concentration and incubation time.

- a. GA.
- b. Fixative = 70% ethanol.
- c. Incubation = overnight.
- d-f. GA.
- g. Buffer = TE, RNase A concentration¹, RNase A incubation time².
- h. GA.

Effects of fixative and time of fixation.

- a. GA.
- b. Fixatives = 4F, MA, MA+, 70E, 95E, 90M.
- c. Fixation time = overnight, 60 min, 30 min, 15 min.
- d–f. GA.
- g. Buffer 5 TE, 0.1 mg/mL RNase A for 15 min.
- h. GA.

Effect of buffer type.

- a. GA.
- b. Fixative = MA+.
- c. Incubation time = 15 min.
- d–f. GA.
- g. 0.1 mg/mL RNase A for 15 min, buffers = PBS, TE, Otto buffer, Tris-MgCl₂, LB01, LB01 (without spermine·4HCl).
- h. GA.

Method for Genome Size Estimation in *Geosmithia*

- a. Centrifuge 1 mL of cell suspension in Eppendorf tube for 10 min at 14,000 rpm.
- b. Discard supernatant, add 500 μL of MA+ and resuspend the cells by pipetting.
- c. Incubate cells for 15 min with constant stirring (300 rpm) at 4 °C.
- d. Centrifuge tube for 5 min at 14,000 rpm.
- e. Wash fixative from cells with the detergent Triton X-100 (500 μL, 0.1%).
- f. Centrifuge tube for 5 min at 14,000 rpm.
- g. Discard detergent, add 950 μL of Tris-MgCl₂ buffer with 0.1 mg/mL RNase A, and incubate cells with constant stirring at 300 rpm at 37 °C for 15 min.
- h. Add 50 μg/mL of PI and stain nuclei at room temperature for 30 min.

FCM Analysis

The samples were analyzed on an LSRII machine (Becton Dickinson, NJ) with FACSDiva 6 Software (Becton Dickinson) at the Service Centre for Cytometry and Microscopy of the Institute of Microbiology, ASCR. Excitation was performed with a Melles Griot 85-YCA-025 laser (23 mW) with the wavelength of 561 nm. Fluorescence was measured through a 590 LP filter and a 610/20 BP filter. The fluorescent signal was detected on a linear scale. All fluorescent events were recorded. The measurement was stopped when 30,000 events were captured within the area responding to the signals of labeled cells. The output was processed in FlowJo 7.6.1 (Tree Star, Ashland, USA). The data were first checked in a FSC-area—FSC-height plot to gate a population termed the “singlet.” The “singlet” was established to avoid analysis of spore clusters or chains. The events in the “singlet” population were then visualized in an SSC-area—PI-area plot. Genome sizes were taken from the median fluorescent intensity of the gated population in the SSC-area—PI-area plot. The rCV was calculated as the population standard deviation from the median divided by the population median and multiplied by 100.

Confocal Microscopy

The samples prepared for FCM analysis were also observed under an Olympus FV1000 confocal microscope (Olympus Corporation, Center Valley, USA) using a differential interference contrast (DIC) channel and a fluorescent channel to examine the level of cytoplasmic staining. The excitation was performed using a laser tuned at 2.2 mW with the wavelength of 559 nm and signal was picked up by a detector between the wavelengths of 570 and 670 nm. A 100 × (NA 1.45) oil immersion lens was used. Colorization and merging of photographs from the DIC and fluorescent channels were performed in FluoView™ FV1000 Ver.2.0c (Olympus Corporation).

Standardization

Saccharomyces cerevisiae BY4743αα, 24.1 Mb (53), *Aspergillus niger* CBS513.88, 33.9 Mb (54) and NRRL350, 34.9 Mb (55), *A. fumigatus* Af293, 29.4 Mb (56) and CEA10, 29.2 Mb (57), and *A. aculeatus* CBS172.66, 35.2 Mb (DOE Joint Genome Institute, unpublished) were tested as standards. The strains were treated in the same way as *Geosmithia* species. In the case of *A. fumigatus* CEA10, our method was compared with a method developed for *Aspergillus fumigatus* (41).

Statistical Analysis

The effects of the chemicals used on rCV and variance of PI intensity was evaluated in the program PAST (58) using a one-way ANOVA. Levene's test for homogeneity of variances was performed on each dataset before conducting the ANOVA. If the variances were heterogeneous, the Kruskal-Wallis test was used instead of the ANOVA. The Mann-Whitney test with the Bonferroni correction was then used for pairwise comparisons. If the ANOVA indicated a significant effect of a treatment, Tukey's pairwise comparison test was carried out.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Effects of Concentration and RNase Incubation Time

RNase A concentrations and incubation times broadly vary among FCM studies of fungi. Concentrations fluctuate approximately around 1 mg/mL (41,44,45), and incubation times largely range from 1 h (19,39,41) to overnight (20). Our results (see "Methods of Optimization Steps") indicate that the concentration of 0.1 mg/mL and incubation time of 15 min is sufficient for *Geosmithia* species (Fig. 2). Strains CCF4525 and CCF4223 formed two distinct cell populations. The genome sizes of these populations differed almost twofold. Only the population with the lower genome size was included in the analysis. Strain CCF4525 did not respond to different RNase A concentrations. A striking increase in rCV caused by the absence of RNase A was found for other strains tested (CCF4223, CCF4205, and CCF4528). A fluctuation in rCV was detected for concentrations higher than 0.1 mg/mL. Markedly higher rCVs were observed for samples incubated for 0 and 5 min. RNase A incubation longer than 15 min caused an increase in rCV. Such an increase in rCV could be, to a certain degree, caused by residual DNase activity of RNase. It nevertheless seems improbable that this residual activity could cause such a substantial increase in rCV. A similar incubation time (20 min) was used for *Phialophora gregata* and *Acremonium* sp. to estimate genome size in spores (50). Most FCM studies of fungi have examined yeast-like organisms, and thus, the short incubation times and low RNase A concentrations used for *Geosmithia* were potentially feasible because their spores are less metabolically active than growing yeasts. For *Paracoccidioides brasiliensis* (19) and *Geosmithia*, the absence of RNase A led to

higher rCV and cytoplasmic staining. These results agree with the knowledge that PI binds to dsDNA and dsRNA.

Figure 2. Effects of RNAse A on rCV. (A) Effect of concentration (incubation for 1 h) and (B) effect of incubation time (concentration of 0.1 mg/mL).

Effects of Fixation Type and Incubation Time

The effects of six fixatives on PI localization to nuclei were determined by following the approach described in “Methods of Optimization Steps.” The results are summarized in Tables 2 and 3. Surprisingly, the current fixative for FCM of fungi, 70% ethanol (70E), was not found to be suitable when combined with PI staining due to cytoplasmic staining. A similar result was obtained for *Candida* with mithramycin instead of PI (38). The worst resolution was achieved with 4% formaldehyde (4F), which was statistically distinct from the other fixatives ($P < 0.004$). This variation led to the detection of lower fluorescent intensities (lower PI penetration into the cells) and an increase in rCVs due to its insufficiency to suppress the viability of cells. Two populations of cells in the CCF4525 sample, which were otherwise well recognizable, were not even possible to distinguish. Methanol:acetic acid with additives (MA+) was the best fixative suitable for all strains tested. It was also the only fixative for which PI was localized to the nucleus without significant cytoplasmic staining in all replications. This fixative was a modification of the 3:1 MA solution used to wash autofluorescent compounds from cells (40). Secondary metabolites are known to have a large impact on measured genome size (PI binding to DNA; e.g., 37). *Geosmithia* produce a spectrum of secondary metabolites (35,36,59), so fixation accompanied by washing of secondary metabolites could play an important role in the quality of fluorescent measurements. The MA+ fixative was then evaluated for four incubation times: overnight, 60, 30, and 15 min (Table 3). There were no differences between fixation times ($P = 0.92$). The MA+ fixation was thereafter performed for 15 min.

Table 2. Effects of fixation time with MA+ fixative on rCV.

Strain	Fixative type											
	4F		MA		MA+		70E		95E		90M	
	rCV	Loc.	rCV	Loc.	rCV	Loc.	rCV	Loc.	rCV	Loc.	rCV	Loc.
CCF3354	18.2	-	9.6	0	9.2	+	12.7	-	10.7	0	9.8	+
CCF4528	19.3	-	8.7	0	7.8	+	8.3	-	9.3	-	8.8	+
CCF4525	19.9	-	8.8	0	8.9	+	9.1	-	9.6	-	9.2	0
CCF4205	16.9	-	11.9	+	14.2	+	13.7	-	16.3	-	11.3	0

PI localisation to the nucleus; (-), improper staining; 0, unequal staining; (+), PI localisation only in the nucleus.

Table 3. Effects of fixation on rCV and PI localisation to the nucleus.

Strain	rCV (%)			
	15 min	30 min	60 min	overnight
CCF3354	8.3	8.1	9.1	9.6
CCF4528	7.2	8.2	7.9	7.9
CCF4525	10.3	11.0	10.5	8.0
CCF4205	9.2	10.2	9.0	11.9

rCV (%), robust coefficient of variation of PI intensity

Table 4. Effects of buffer on PI fluorescence stability, rCV, and localization of PI in the nuclei.

Strains	PBS			TE			Tris-MgCl ₂		
	CV (%)	rCV (%)	Loc.	CV (%)	rCV (%)	Loc.	CV (%)	rCV (%)	Loc.
CCF3354	6.7	15.6	0	4.1	9.3	+	3.3	8.5	+
CCF4528	4.8	8.7	+	1.5	8.9	+	3.6	8.6	+
CCF4525	0.6	8.4	+	4.9	9.7	+	3.8	8.7	+
CCF4205	2.0	9.1	+	6.3	11.5	0	3.6	7.4	+
Strains	Otto's buffer			LB01 – spermin·4HCl			LB01 + spermin·4HCl		
	CV (%)	rCV (%)	Loc.	CV (%)	rCV (%)	Loc.	CV (%)	rCV (%)	Loc.
CCF3354	18.6	14.4	-	4.4	15.9	0	1.9	7.4	+
CCF4528	11.2	11.3	0	4.0	10.5	+	1.2	9.7	+
CCF4525	52.0	15.8	0	4.2	8.4	+	5.5	9.2	+
CCF4205	15.4	15.2	0	1.9	8.9	0	3.2	8.4	+

CV, coefficient of variation of PI intensity between three replications (s.d./average value of PI intensity × 100); rCV, robust coefficient of variation of PI intensity; Loc., localization of PI to the nuclei; (-), improper staining; 0, unequal staining; (+), PI localisation only in the nucleus.

Effects of Buffer Type

The buffers included in this study encompass buffers commonly used in mycology (TE and PBS) and plant research (Tris-MgCl₂ buffer, Otto's buffer and LB01 plus its variant without spermine-4HCl). For methods, see "Methods of Optimization Steps." The results are presented in Table 4. Otto's buffer caused cell clumping, which led to increased rCVs and relatively higher variance in fluorescent intensity between replications. Similarly as in Bainard et al. (60), the buffers which contained a DNA stabilizing agent (Tris-MgCl₂ and LB01 buffer) yielded the best results, such as lower rCVs (only two buffers statistically distinct from Otto's buffer, $P = 0.02$ and 0.03 , respectively), lower variance between fluorescent intensities on different days and high localization of PI to nuclei. Tris-MgCl₂ exhibited the best resolution and also showed similar interspecies variation in PI intensity between replications. This buffer contains a higher concentration of detergent compared with the others. *Geosmithia* produces hydrophobic spores (31), so Tris-MgCl₂ buffer had a better ability to suppress cell clumping (15).

Figure 3. PI staining of standards. (A) *A. niger* NRRL350, (B) *A. niger* CBS513.88, (C) *A. aculeatus* CBS172.66, (D) *A. fumigatus* Af293, (E) *S. cerevisiae* BY4743 $\alpha\alpha$, (F) *A. fumigatus* CEA10 (our method), (G) FCM histogram of PI-stained *S. cerevisiae* BY4743 $\alpha\alpha$, (H) FCM histogram of PI-stained *A. fumigatus* CEA10 (our method).

Standardization

Our results (Figs. 3A–3H) show that *A. fumigatus* CEA10 and *S. cerevisiae* BY4743 $\alpha\alpha$ are suitable standards. Both strains of *A. niger* produced multinucleate spores (1–3 nuclei per cell). All strains except *A. fumigatus* CEA10, *Aspergillus niger* CBS513.88, and *S. cerevisiae* BY4743 $\alpha\alpha$ exhibited high levels of cytoplasmic staining. Our findings also reveal that different strains of the same species can differ in their response to the methods used. In the second step, we compared the method developed for *A. fumigatus* (41) with the method developed for *Geosmithia* (this study). The results (Figs. 3F and 3H) also show that our method is convenient for *A. fumigatus* CEA10. The use of the MA+ fixative with the Tris-MgCl₂ buffer leads to lower levels of cytoplasmic staining compared with 70% ethanol and the TE buffer used by De Lucas et al. (41).

The genome size of *A. fumigatus* CEA10 estimated by FCM (29.7 Mb) using *S. cerevisiae* as a standard is in agreement with its genome size as ascertained by genome sequencing (29.2 Mb). In

our case, we found that *S. cerevisiae* can be used as a standard during the G₁/G₀ phases of the cell cycle, when cells are resting and preparing for DNA synthesis, respectively. We also found that the chromosome length polymorphism recorded for this species (20) does not cause detectable variation in genome size (variation in PI intensities between replications was that of 1.6%). We thus propose *A. fumigatus* CEA10 and *S. cerevisiae* BY4743aa as good fungal standards for FCM estimation of genome size in fungi.

Final Remarks

When optimizing the FCM protocol for estimating genome size in *Geosmithia*, we evaluated the effects of different RNase A concentrations and incubation times, different types and durations of fixation, and various buffers on rCVs, and the localization of PI to nuclei. The final protocol is described in the section “Method for Genome Size Estimation in *Geosmithia*.” The final protocol uses methanol:glacial acetic acid (3:1 v/v), 10% DMSO, 0.1% Triton-X 100, and 5 mM EDTA as a fixative, which helps wash away secondary metabolites from the cytoplasm, and Tris-MgCl₂ buffer, which is superior at reducing cell clusters compared with the other buffers tested. We found that RNase A concentrations as low as 0.1 mg/mL and RNase A incubation time of 15 min are sufficient for *Geosmithia* species. This markedly shortens the time needed for preparing FCM samples. We also propose a new fungal standard, *A. fumigatus* CEA10, for FCM of fungal species. Moreover, *S. cerevisiae* can be considered as a standard when its cell cycle is stopped.

As the use of FCM precluded simultaneous observation of cells, we used FCM in combination with confocal microscopy. Secondary metabolites play an important role in genome size estimation by FCM (37). Hydroxylated anthraquinones are fluorescent pigments produced by *Geosmithia* (35,36). Species differ in their production however, during optimization steps, we found that these differences have no effect on PI localization or rCVs.

RCV values increased with higher amounts of cytoplasmic staining and lower staining uniformity. At least in our case, rCV is therefore a good marker for stain localization and could be used by itself for optimizing FCM protocols. High rCV values can make it impossible to distinguish aneuploidy in samples and potentially lead to incorrect genome size estimates. Higher amounts of cytoplasmic staining cause the detection of higher fluorescent intensities and also produce false results. These conclusions demonstrate the enormous effects of the methods used when estimating genome size by FCM. When a proper methodology is used, however, FCM is a suitable and hugely advantageous method for estimating genome size in fungi.

SUPPLEMENTARY INFORMATION

Supplementary 1. Published FCM protocols used in genome size estimations in fungi.

Fungus	Buffer	Reducing of clumping	Fluorescent dye	Fixation	Reference
<i>Candida albicans</i> , <i>C. parapsilosis</i> , <i>C. tropical</i>	PBS, pH 7.4	Triton X-100	Mithramycin	Carnoy fixative	(38)
<i>Cryptococcus neoformans</i>	Tris, pH 8.0	Sonication	Propidium iodide	70% ethanol	(45)
<i>Candida utilis</i> , <i>Saccharomyces cerevisiae</i>	Tris, pH 7.5	No reducing	Propidium iodide	70% ethanol	(46)
<i>S. cerevisiae</i>	Tris, pH 7.5	Sonication	SYTOX Green	70% ethanol	(18)
<i>S. cerevisiae</i>	Sodium citrate, pH 7.0	No reducing	SYTOX Green	70% ethanol	(47)
<i>Histoplasma capsulatum</i>	Sodium citrate, pH 8.0	Sonication , Triton X-100	Propidium iodide	70% ethanol	(46)
<i>Benjaminiella poitrasii</i>	PBS, pH 7.2	Tween 80	Propidium iodide	70% ethanol	(39)
<i>Paracoccidioides brasiliensis</i>	Sodium citrate, pH 7.5	Sonication , Triton X-100	SYBR Green	70% ethanol	(19)
<i>Zygosaccharomyces rouxii</i>	Sodium citrate, pH 7.0	Sonication	Propidium iodide	70% ethanol	(48)
<i>Phialophora gregata</i> , <i>Acremonium</i> sp.	Tris, pH 8.0	Triton X-100	Propidium iodide	70% ethanol	(50)
<i>Aspergillus fumigatus</i>	Tris, pH 8.0	Tween 80	Propidium iodide	70% ethanol	(41)
<i>Glomales</i> spp.	PBS, Tris, pH 7.0	Triton X-100	Propidium iodide , DAPI	4% formaldehyd	(24)
<i>Armillaria</i> spp.	Tris, pH 7.4	Triton X-100	Propidium iodide	4% formaldehyd	(23)
<i>Cronartium quercuum</i> f.sp. <i>fusiforme</i>	Tris, pH 8.0	Triton X-100	Propidium iodide	NA	(21)
<i>Schizosaccharomyces pombe</i>	Tris, pH 7.4 or 8.0	Triton X-100	Hoechst 33258 Mithramycin + Ethidium bromide	70% ethanol	(49)

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Fungal Ecology

Application of flow cytometry for exploring the evolution of *Geosmithia* fungi living in association with bark beetles: the role of conidial DNA content

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ABSTRACT

Geosmithia belongs among fungi living in symbiosis with phloem-feeding bark beetles. Several species have altered their ecology to that of obligatory symbiosis with ambrosia beetles, which has led to a shift in their phenotype and caused formation of large spherical conidia. In this study, we pose the following questions; (1) Is the conidial DNA content of *Geosmithia* correlated with conidial volume?; (2) Is the DNA content of *Geosmithia* related to the degree of mutual dependence between *Geosmithia* and their vector? There was a positive and strong correlation between conidial DNA content and conidial volume in *Geosmithia*. Also species more narrowly associated with the vector tend to have a larger conidial DNA content and volume than less narrowly associated species. Ambrosia fungi achieved the biggest conidial DNA content and volume compared to other species. We suppose that polyploidisation occurred during the evolution of ambrosia species in the genus *Geosmithia*.

Keywords:

Ambrosia fungi, Bark beetles, Conidial DNA content, Conidial volume, Evolution, Generalists, Life-history traits, r/K-strategy, Specialists, Symbiosis

INTRODUCTION

Genome sizes among eukaryotic organisms differ by almost 80 000-fold (Gregory et al., 2007) and this range is thought to be even larger (Gregory 2001). It was recognised early that genome size does not correlate with organismal complexity (Mirsky and Ris, 1951). This disproportion was termed the C-value paradox (Thomas, 1971). The C-value paradox was resolved by the discovery that non-coding DNA could create the majority of DNA (Cavalier-Smith and Beaton, 1999; Gregory, 2001). Bennett (1971) pointed out that DNA influences the development not only by a gene but also by its mass, termed the nucleotype. Since then, many publications have explored the correlation between genome size and cell size (reviewed in Gregory, 2001). The mechanism that underlines this phenomenon has remained unknown until now. Cavalier-Smith and others declared that a correlation between cell size and genome size is maintained by the need for preservation of karyoplasmic volume ratio for balanced growth (Cavalier-Smith and Beaton, 1999; Cavalier-Smith, 2005). Modulation of genome size is therefore the consequence of organismal selection for optimal cell size. This assumption was supported by manipulations of genome size in yeast (Jorgensen et al., 2007) and fission yeast

(Neumann and Nurse, 2007). In fungi, a relationship between spore size and life-history strategies (Kausserud et al., 2008, 2011; Meerts, 1999; Philibert et al., 2011) or climate (Kausserud et al., 2011; Pentecost, 1981) has been found. This indicates the great importance of spore size in exploring fungal ecology and evolution. Explanations of these relationships stem from the physical characteristics of spores (floating and impact ability, drag minimisation, nutrient and water content). Additional explanations due to differences in genome size/ DNA content should also be considered. The role of genome size in species adaptations to environmental conditions was found repeatedly in plants and animals (Barow and Meister, 2003; Beaulieu et al., 2008; Smith and Gregory, 2009; te Beest et al., 2012; Vesely et al., 2012), but few studies exist in mycology, and they focus mostly on yeasts (Conant and Wolfe, 2007; Lidzbarsky et al., 2009; Talbot and Wayman, 1989).

Figure 1. Morphological variability of studied *Geosmithia* species. The bar is 10 μm (microphotographs) and 100 μm (macrophotographs). (A) *Geosmithia* sp. 8 CCF4528, a generalist producing masses of small cylindrical and catenate conidia, phialide reached $8\text{--}11 \times 2.0\text{--}2.5 \mu\text{m}$. (B) *Geosmithia* sp. 24 CCF4294, a specialist restricted to vectors feeding on the trees from the Pinaceae family. Sporulation is moderate and it produces catenate conidia which are very variable in shape. (C) *G. microcorthyli* CCF3861, primary ambrosia fungus producing big and solitary conidia, phialide reached $9\text{--}15 \times 5\text{--}7 \mu\text{m}$. All cultures were on MEA medium.

The genus *Geosmithia* (Ascomycota: Hypocreales) includes fungal species living in association with bark beetles (Coleoptera: Curculionidae, Scolytinae) or, rarely, occurring as endophytes or on alternative substrata (McPherson et al., 2013; Kolařík et al., 2004, 2005, 2007, 2008, 2011; Kolařík and Kirkendall, 2010; Kolařík and Jankowiak, 2013; Kubátová et al., 2004; Pitt and Hocking, 1997). Some of them are considered to be generalists, living in association with insects on a variety of plant hosts, the others are specialists restricted to vectors living on the single plant family Pinaceae. *Geosmithia morbida* is the only known pathogenic species from the genus and causes necrosis in *Juglans nigra* (Kolařík et al., 2011; Tisserat et al., 2009). Several species, including *Geosmithia microcorthyli*, *Geosmithia eupagioceri*, and likely *Geosmithia* sp. CCF4292, changed their ecology to that of obligatory symbiosis with ambrosia beetles (Kolařík and Kirkendall, 2010). The ambrosia fungi, which are nutritional symbionts of ambrosia beetles, share similar phenotypes (e.g., production of large globose

conidia or pleomorphism) (Batra, 1967) and in addition to *Geosmithia* and other Hypocreales (Kasson et al., 2013), these species mostly belong to the orders Ophiostomatales and Microascales (Jones and Blackwell, 1998). Interestingly, *G. microcorthyli*, a large-mitospored ambrosia fungus, is closely related to two non-ambrosial species, *Geosmithia* sp. 8 (Kolařík and Kirkendall, 2010) and *G.* sp. CCF4200 (unpublished), which all have small conidia (Fig. 1) and live in association with phloem-feeding bark beetles. This suggests the rapid evolution of large-mitospored ambrosia fungi from small-mitospored species. Sudden genome enlargement is a possible evolutionary step in the evolution of these large mitospored ambrosia fungi. *Geosmithia rufescens*, that accompanies ambrosial *G. eupagioceri* and *G.* sp. CCF4292 in beetle galleries, is an auxiliary ambrosia fungus (Kolařík and Kirkendall, 2010). This species possesses two distinct conidial types and its phenotype is in transition between ambrosial and non-ambrosial species.

The aims of this work were to correlate measured conidial DNA content of *Geosmithia* species with their respective conidial volumes and discuss the role of conidial DNA content in the ecology of *Geosmithia*, particularly for ambrosial species.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Fungal material

The full list of studied *Geosmithia* strains is in Table 1. These strains are deposited in the Culture Collection of Fungi (CCF). *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* BY4743 $\alpha\alpha$ (24.1 Mb, Goffeau et al., 1996) and *Aspergillus fumigatus* CEA10 (29.2 Mb, Fedorova et al., 2008) were used as standards (Veselská et al., 2014). Fungi were grown on 2 % malt extract agar (20 g malt extract, (Oxoid, Basingstoke, UK), 15 g Bacto-agar (Difco, Detroit, USA), 1 L H₂O), until a sufficient level of sporulation was reached. Yeast species were cultivated on yeast extract peptone dextrose agar (10 g Bacto-yeast extract (Difco, Detroit, USA), 20 g Bacto-peptone (Difco, Detroit, USA), 20 g D-glucose, 1 L H₂O).

Determination of conidial volume

Conidial sizes were measured from images taken with an Olympus BX51 microscope using DIC. Length and width were measured for at least 50 conidia with the program QuickPhoto. The volume was calculated from the equation for prolate ellipsoid: $V = 4/3\pi(a/2)^2b/2$, where a is the width and b is the length of each spore (Kausrud et al., 2008).

Conidial DNA content estimation

Cell staining

This was effected as described in Veselská et al. (2014). In brief, 1 ml of cell suspension ($3-5 \times 10^6$ cells ml⁻¹) in Eppendorf tube was centrifuged for 10 min at 20 800 g to create a firm pellet. The supernatant was removed and 500 μ l of methanol: glacial acetic acid (3:1 v/v), 10 % dimethyl sulfoxide, 0.1 % Triton X-100, 5 mM EDTA was added for 15 min. The fixative was washed out from the cells with 0.1 % Triton X-100 and cells were incubated for 15 min at 37 °C with 0.1 mg ml⁻¹ RNase A (MP Biomedicals, Solon, USA) in TrisMgCl₂ buffer pH 7.5 (200 mM Tris, 4 mM MgCl₂·6 H₂O, 0.5 % (v/v) Triton X-100). Finally, the fluorescent dye propidium iodide (Fluka, Glossop, England) was added at a concentration of 50 mg ml⁻¹. Staining was performed at room temperature in the dark for 30 min.

FCM setting

The samples were analysed on an LSRII machine (Becton Dickinson, New Jersey, USA) with FACSDiva 6 Software (Becton Dickinson) at the Service Centre for Cytometry and Microscopy at the Institute of Microbiology, ASCR. Excitation was performed with a Melles Griot 85-YCA-025 laser (23 mW) with the wavelength of 561 nm. Fluorescence was measured through a 590 LP filter and 610/20 BP filter. FSC and SSC signals were measured on a logarithmic scale because of the large range of conidial sizes in *Geosmithia*. Fluorescent signal was detected on a linear scale. All fluorescent events were recorded. Measurement was stopped when 30 000 events were captured within the area responding to the signals of labelled cells. The output was processed in FlowJo 7.6.1 (Tree Star, Inc., Ashland, USA).

Conidial DNA content and volume calculation and statistics

The data from FCM analysis were first checked on a plot of signal intensities of area and height of forward scattered light (FSC-A – FSC-H) to gate a population termed the “singlet”. The “singlet” was established to avoid analysis of conidial clusters or chains. The events in the “singlet” population were then visualised in a plot of signal intensities of areas of side scattered light and fluorescent light (SSC-A – PI-A). Relative conidial DNA contents were taken from the median fluorescent intensity of the gated population on the SSC-A – PI-A plot. The robust per cent coefficient of variation (rCV) was calculated as the population standard deviation from the median divided by the population median and multiplied by 100. AlignFlow flow cytometry alignment beads of 2.5 µm for 488 nm excitation (Invitrogen, Eugene, USA) were used as an internal standard for DNA content estimation. The beads served to ensure the stability of device measurements. The fluorescence value for each sample was corrected with the per cent deviation of the fluorescence of its internal beads to the fluorescence of the beads in the first measured sample. The absolute conidial DNA content was calculated from the equation: $C_{\text{sam}} = F_{\text{sam}}/F_{\text{std}}C_{\text{std}}$, where $C_{\text{sam/std}}$ is the DNA content of the sample/standard and $F_{\text{sam/std}}$ is the median of fluorescent intensity of the sample/standard.

Relative median absolute deviation (RMAD) was used to measure variability in conidial volume, which expresses the spread relative to the median as a percentage. This method was used for its resilience to outliers in the data set. RMAD was calculated from the equation:

$RMAD(X) = 100 \text{ Median}_i (|X_i - \text{Median}_j(X_j)|) / \text{Median}_j(X_j)$, where X is the data set and X_j is an element of that set.

Regression between conidial DNA content and volume was calculated with the programme PAST (Hammer et al., 2001) using the linear RMA model. The values of DNA content and conidial volume were logarithmically transformed before analysis. When some strains displayed two peaks in the FCM histogram, the median over both populations was included in the analysis. Differences in conidial DNA content and conidial volume between ecological groups were tested by the Mann-Whitney test in the programme PAST.

Confocal microscopy

The samples prepared for FCM analysis were also observed under Olympus FV1000 confocal microscope (Olympus Corporation, Center Valley, USA) using DIC and a fluorescent channel. The excitation was performed using a laser tuned at 2.2 mW with the wavelength of 559 nm and signal was picked up by a detector between the wavelengths of 570–670 nm. If the object was cut, the sections had a thickness of 0.42 µm. A × 100 (NA 1.45) oil immersion lens was used. Colourisation, merging of

photos from DIC and fluorescent channel and 3D visualisation were performed in FluoView FV1000 Ver.2.0c (Olympus Corporation).

RESULTS

Conidial DNA content of *Geosmithia*

Conidial DNA content and volume, we estimated for 21 *Geosmithia* species (Table 1, Fig. 2), including seven generalists, seven specialists, one plant pathogen, three ambrosia fungi, one auxiliary ambrosia species and two species from broadleaved trees with little known host range. Conidial DNA content ranged between 1 and 1.4 multiples of the smallest DNA content (CCF4527) except for the ambrosial *G. microcorthyli* whose conidial DNA content was 2.6 times bigger and *G. eupagioceri* whose total genome mass was 17.8 times bigger. Several species exhibited intra-strain variation in conidial DNA content. These included: likely ambrosial *G. sp.* CCF4292 and four specialists: CCF4525 and CCF4294 (*G. sp.* 24), CCF4223 (*G. sp.* 26), CCF4206 (*G. sp.* 27), and CCF4526 (*G. sp.* 31). For these, populations with bigger DNA contents (p2) had DNA contents that were 1.8–1.9 times larger than populations with smaller DNA contents (p1). Two strains of *G. sp.* 24 (CCF4525, CCF4294) had the same DNA content and p1:p2 ratio. The strains CCF4223, CCF4292 and CCF4526 had p1:p2 ratios of 1:4.2, 2:1 and 1:8.4, respectively. The non-ambrosial species *G. sp.* 8 and *G. sp.* CCF4200 and sister ambrosial species *G. microcorthyli* produced conidia with greatly dissimilar volumes (10.4 – 11.8 μm^3 vs. 88.3 μm^3) and their DNA contents reached nearly half that of ambrosial *G. microcorthyli* DNA content (24.8–29.2 Mb vs. 53.9 Mb). The conidia of *G. eupagioceri* were multinucleated (typically 3–7, rarely up to 15 nuclei per cell) (Fig. 3). The nuclei were often clustered together in several groups. The multiplication of nuclei takes place in conidia attached to the phialides. Vegetative hyphae are mostly uninucleate, rarely with 2–3 nuclei (Fig. 3). The fluorescent intensity histograms for ambrosial *G. microcorthyli* and *G. eupagioceri* exhibited lower resolution and higher cytoplasmic staining compared to other *Geosmithia* spp. These species may potentially possess cytoplasmic components that interact with propidium iodide.

Correlation between conidial DNA content and volume and its relation to species ecology

Conidial DNA content and conidial volume were strongly correlated (Fig. 4A, $R^2 = 0.80$, $p < 0.00001$), even when the multinucleated species *G. eupagioceri* was omitted from the analysis (Fig. 4B, $R^2 = 0.76$, $p < 0.00001$). Specialists had significantly larger genomes and spore volumes than generalists, $p < 0.03$. The ambrosia fungi were similar to specialists, $p < 0.3$, when *G. eupagioceri* was withdrawn from the analysis.

Table 1. List of *Geosmithia* spp. and their conidial DNA content and volume.

Species	Strain	Ecology	Reference	Conidial DNA content [Mb] ^a				rCV ^b [%]	Conidia length [μm ³] ± RMAD ^c [%]	Conidia width [μm ³] ± RMAD [%]	Conidia volume [μm ³] ± RMAD [%]
				<i>Saccharomyces cerevisiae</i> BY4743αα as a standard	<i>Aspergillus fumigatus</i> CEA10 as a standard						
<i>Geosmithia</i> sp. 1	CCF4529	PHL ^d , generalist	(Kolařík et al. 2008)	21.8	21.5			7.4	4.2 ± 6.2	2.3 ± 8.0	11.6 ± 15.3
<i>G. putterillii</i>	CCF3342	PHL, generalist	(Kolařík et al. 2004)	26.3	26.0			10.5	4.4 ± 6.8	2.1 ± 4.8	10.5 ± 14.6
<i>G. flava</i>	CCF3354	PHL, generalist	(Kolařík et al. 2004)	25.8	25.5			7.2	4.0 ± 5.0	2.2 ± 7.0	9.7 ± 12.8
<i>G. sp. 8</i>	CCF4528	PHL, unknown	(Kolařík et al. 2008)	24.8	24.5			8.2	4.1 ± 7.3	2.1 ± 9.5	10.4 ± 20.0
<i>G. sp. 8</i>	CCF4207	PHL, unknown	unpublished	27.2	26.9			9.4	4.5 ± 5.5	2.3 ± 6.8	12.9 ± 14.5
<i>G. sp. 9</i>	CCF3703	PHL, specific to Pinacee	(Kolařík et al. 2008)	23.5	23.3			9.3	3.3 ± 6.1	2.0 ± 10.0	7.1 ± 23.0
<i>G. sp. 16</i>	CCF4201	PHL, specific to Pinacee	(Kolařík et al. 2008)	28.4	28.0			8.7	4.2 ± 4.8	2.8 ± 7.1	17.2 ± 14.3
<i>G. sp. 20</i>	CCF4527	PHL, generalist	(Kolařík et al. 2007)	20.8	20.5			7.4	4.5 ± 3.5	2.0 ± 6.0	9.3 ± 15.2
<i>G. sp. 21</i>	CCF4531	PHL, generalist	(Kolařík et al. 2007)	27.9	27.6			8.9	3.9 ± 3.5	2.1 ± 8.2	8.7 ± 20.2
<i>G. sp. 22</i>	CCF3645	PHL, generalist	(Kolařík et al. 2007)	23.0	22.8			7.8	3.4 ± 5.7	2.0 ± 5.8	7.0 ± 13.0
<i>G. sp. 24</i>	CCF4525			p ¹ 24.5	p ² 45.2	p ¹ 24.2	p ² 44.7	p ¹ 8.2	p ² 8.1	5.0 ± 10.0	3.4 ± 8.0

		PHL, specific to Pinacee	(Kolařík and Jankowiak 2013)	p^1p^2 38.6		p^1p^2 38.2		NA ^e			29.1 ± 33.1	
G. sp. 24	CCF4294	PHL, specific to Pinacee	(Kolařík and Jankowiak 2013)	p^1 24.9 p^1p^2 38.4	p^2 44.8	p^1 24.6 p^1p^2 38.0	p^2 44.3	p^1 7.9 NA	p^2 7.1	5.3 ± 11.1	2.8 ± 9.6	22.9 ± 28.0
G. sp. 25	CCF4205	PHL, specific to Pinacee	(Kolařík and Jankowiak 2013)	24.2		24.0		6.6		5.0 ± 6.4	2.7 ± 5.8	18.3 ± 16.1
G. sp. 26	CCF4223	PHL, specific to Pinacee	(Kolařík and Jankowiak 2013)	p^1 25.7 p^1p^2 45.7	p^2 48.5	p^1 25.5 p^1p^2 45.2	p^2 48.0	p^1 8.4 NA	p^2 8.7	6.1 ± 7.8	3.6 ± 9.9	40.3 ± 24.2
G. sp. 27	CCF4206	PHL, specific to Pinacee	(Kolařík and Jankowiak 2013)	p^1 23.6 p^1p^2 37.9	p^2 44.4	p^1 23.4 p^1p^2 37.5	p^2 43.9	p^1 10.2 NA	p^2 7.6	5.5 ± 6.9	2.5 ± 9.2	17.3 ± 24.4
G. sp. 31	CCF4526	PHL, specific to Pinacee	(Kolařík and Jankowiak 2013)	p^1 28.3 p^1p^2 51.3	p^2 51.1	p^1 28.0 p^1p^2 50.7	p^2 50.5	p^1 7.5 NA	p^2 6.6	6.0 ± 6.7	3.4 ± 5.9	37.0 ± 16.5
G. microcorthyli	CCF3861	Ambrosial	(Kolařík and Kirkendall 2010)	53.9		53.3		15.6		5.5 ± 6.8	5.5 ± 6.8	88.3 ± 20.3
G. eupagioceri	CCF3754	Ambrosial	(Kolařík and Kirkendall 2010)	p^1 369.1 p^1p^2 1189.7	p^2 1665.5	p^1 365.0 p^1p^2 1176.4	p^2 1646.9	p^1 19.8 NA	p^2 24.0	9.6 ± 7.6	9.6 ± 7.6	460.8 ± 22.8
G. morbida	CCF3879	PHL, pathogen	(Kolařík et al. 2011)	24.7		24.4		9.7		4.5 ± 5.6	2.1 ± 4.8	11.0 ± 9.9

<i>G. rufescens</i>	CCF4524	auxiliary ambrosial	(Kolařík and Kirkendall 2010)	24.3		24.1		10.1		4.1 ± 5.3	2.1 ± 13.2	9.9 ± 27.9
<i>G. sp. CCF3554</i>	CCF3554	PHL, generalist	unpublished	24.5		24.3		8.3		4.1 ± 4.9	2.3 ± 4.4	11.4 ±16.9
<i>G. sp. CCF4200</i>	CCF4200	PHL, unknown	unpublished	29.2		28.9		16.4		4.4 ± 4.6	2.3 ± 4.4	11.8 ± 13.6
<i>G. sp. CCF4292</i>	CCF4292	Ambrosial	(Kolařík and Kirkendall 2010)	^{p1} 27.8	^{p2} 50.7	^{p1} 27.5	^{p2} 50.2	^{p1} 11.3	^{p2} 10.4	4.9 ± 8.2	3.0 ± 10.0	22.6 ± 20.6
				^{p1p2} 37.4		^{p1p2} 37.0		NA				

^a p1-population 1 with lower conidial DNA content , p2- population 2 with larger conidial DNA content, p1p2- conidial DNA content as a median over both populations (p1 and p2), ^b robust coefficient of variation of fluorescent intensity histograms, ^c relative median absolute deviation, ^d phloeophagous, ^e not available.

Figure 2. Examples of fluorescent intensity histograms for *Geosmithia* spp. The secondary minority peaks are doublets. rCV – robust coefficient of variation of fluoresce.

Figure 3. Propidium iodide labelled *Geosmithia eupagioceri*. (A) conidiophore and (B) conidia.

Figure 4. Conidial DNA content and volume regression. (A) All species are plotted ($R^2 = 0.80$, $p < 0.0001$), (B) all species except *G. eupagioceri* are plotted ($R^2 = 0.76$, $p < 0.0001$). Cross – ambrosia species, diamond – specialists, circle – generalists, square – auxiliary ambrosia species, triangle – pathogen.

DISCUSSION

Conidial DNA content and its correlation to conidial volume in *Geosmithia*

The positive correlation between genome size and cell size is well documented across eukaryotic organisms (Gregory, 2001) and also seems to be present in fungi (Jorgensen et al., 2007; Kuldau et al., 1999; Moon et al., 2002; Neumann and Nurse, 2007; Nielsen and Yohalem, 2001; Suzuki et al., 1982). In this study, we confirmed this correlation for *Geosmithia*. We also found that conidial DNA content and conidial volume are linked with the ecology of species. Specialists and ambrosia fungi with narrower association with their vector tended to have a larger conidial DNA content and volume than generalists. The strength of the mutual dependence between fungi and beetles is considered here to be the deciding factor influencing conidial DNA content and volume manipulation or *vice versa*.

Genome size and spore volume affects several life-history traits, e.g., dispersal ability, amount of nutrients within a spore and resilience to climate factors. The negative correlation between genome size and metabolic and growth rate has also been found repeatedly (Beaulieu et al., 2008; Gregory, 2002; Opazo et al., 2005; Wyngaard et al., 2005). A high metabolic rate, growth rate and investment into the quantity of offspring are typical signs of an *r*-strategy. In general, a fungus produces a higher number of small spores than large spores from the same limited amount of nutrients. These small spores are dispersed across larger distances than large ones. In contrast, larger spores provide proportionally more nutrients necessary for germination than smaller ones, which also increase their resilience to climate factors (Kausserud et al., 2008, 2011; Meerts, 1999). Fungi producing high numbers of small spores could thus be considered *r*-strategists, whereas fungi producing limited amounts of large spores could be considered *K*-strategists.

We conclude that the trade-off between spore quantity (dispersal potential) and spore quality (nutritional value increasing the fitness of the vector) must be balanced by *Geosmithia* generalists, specialists and ambrosial species.

Generalists

Taxonomically unrelated *Geosmithia* generalists had similarly small genome sizes and produced conidia with small volumes, indicating that these species are *r*-strategists. A high quantity of small conidia can be important for fungi dispersed by a wide spectrum of vectors and by air, which is true for *Geosmithia* generalists. *R*-strategy could be favoured in environments with high competition, such as galleries of phloem feeding beetles. High growth rate and high spore production enable them to quickly occupy galleries and obtain higher probability of transfer *via* beetles to a new substratum.

Specialists and ambrosia fungi

The fungal genome is very plastic and could lead to intrastrain variability in genome size (Bridge et al., 1987; Kullman, 2005). Intra-strain variability in conidial DNA content was detected in four *Geosmithia* specialists and in likely ambrosial *G. sp.* CCF4292. These species produced haploid and nearly diploid conidial populations and also displayed large variation in conidial volume (up to 33.1 %). This plasticity in conidial DNA content and cell size imparts to these fungi above mentioned advantages of both *r*- and *K*-strategy, and refers to balancing trade-offs between them. Startlingly, the non-ambrosial *G. sp.* 8 and *G. sp.* CCF4200 and their sister ambrosial *G. microcorthyli* produced conidia with greatly dissimilar volumes and a nearly two-fold difference in DNA content. Ambrosial *G. microcorthyli* and *G. eupagioceri* thus represent the final step in the *r*-*K* continuum, which is characterised by

investment into the quality of conidia and dependence on dissemination by vectors. Some fungi, e.g., *Neurospora crassa* (Schmit and Brody, 1976), are known to produce conidia partly arrested in G2 phase of the cell cycle. The first peak in FCM analysis thus corresponds to C-value of an organism, but the second peak could correspond to conidia arrested in G2 phase (2C-value) or refer to real intra-strain variation in genome size (change in C-value). The example of *N. crassa*, that produce mix of conidia arrested in G1 and G2 phases, thus suggests that C-values solely estimated by FCM analysis of conidia should be taken with caution. The presence of nuclei in G2 phase in specialists and ambrosia fungi could thus explain measured variation in their conidial DNA content. Nevertheless, the p2 population in specialists and ambrosial CCF4292 achieved only 1.8–1.9 multiple of the p1 population, which separated it clearly from doublets and should also separate it from conidia in G2 phase. It is also improbable that almost all conidia of *G. sp. 31* and all conidia of *G. microcorthyli* are arrested in G2 phase of the cell cycle. Cells in vegetative mycelium and conidiophores of *G. microcorthyli* are larger than these of non-ambrosial sister species *G. sp. 8* and *G. sp. CCF4200* (Fig. 1), which point to the stable presence of nuclei with nearly two-fold genome size in the whole life cycle of *G. microcorthyli*.

Evolutionary changes in genome size are caused by several mechanisms (Aguileta et al., 2009; Zolan, 1995) and result from gradual or quantum shifts (Gregory and Hebert, 1999). Gradual shifts are caused by expansion of repetitive elements whereas quantum shifts, as observed in *G. microcorthyli*, suggest the presence of polyploidisation. Polyploidisation has played an important role in the evolution of plants and animals (Soltis and Soltis, 1999) and seems to be also common in fungi (Albertin and Marullo, 2012). It is thought that gene duplications in yeast enable them to faster utilise sources that favour polyploids against haploid ancestors (Conant and Wolfe, 2007; Talbot and Wayman, 1989). The significance of this phenomenon in the evolution of ambrosia fungi is not known. In our study we cannot decide if the quantum shifts in conidial DNA content in *Geosmithia* specialists and ambrosia fungi are achieved by presence of conidia arrested in G2 phase or by polyploidisation. Further studies are needed to clarify the origin of these shifts in conidial DNA content.

Although phloem-feeding bark beetles are not dependent on a fungal diet, fungus-colonised phloem has a higher nutritional value than fungus-free phloem, which has a positive effect on the development of the beetle brood (reviewed by Six, 2012). *Geosmithia* specialists are restricted to a limited range of vectors in Europe (Kolařík and Jankowiak, 2013), which suggests long-term co-evolution with vectors. The tendency of *Geosmithia* specialists to have conidia with greater DNA content and volume could, thus, be a consequence of their potentially stronger symbiosis with vectors which enable them to overcome aerodynamic constraints and provide more nutrients for their vectors. This is more pronounced in ambrosia beetles, which are nutritionally dependent on fungi. Production of large conidia by ambrosia fungi could greatly affect the fitness of beetles and lead to the positive selection of large-mitospored mutants by insect vectors. The conidia with larger DNA content simultaneously provide higher amounts of phosphorus and nitrogen (Maheshwari, 2005), which are often limiting factors. The ambrosia fungi *G. microcorthyli* and *G. eupagioceri* had the biggest conidial DNA content and, therefore, volume. *G. eupagioceri* was unique among *Geosmithia* spp. in that it produced multinucleate spores. The conidial DNA content of *G. eupagioceri* could not be explained by the number of nuclei per conidium itself. Although cytoplasm staining had apparently contributed somewhat to the genome mass detected in *G. eupagioceri*, it could not be the sole explanation. We suppose that this species is also polyploid, although its genome size is waiting to be resolved. In addition to genome expansion, the multiplication of nuclei per conidium, is another way to enlarge cell

volume. Increases in genome mass done by multiplication of nuclei were also reported in fungal crops of higher attine ants and termites (reviewed in Kooij, 2013; Nobre et al., 2014). Another example is the human-planted *Agaricus bisporus* which is multinucleate (1–26 nuclei) in comparison to its free-living sister species *Agaricus bitorquis* (reviewed in Kooij, 2013). Production of multinucleate cells seems to be often restricted to the structures harvested by the insects. In *Geosmithia eupagiceri* multinucleated conidia represent the significant part of the beetles diet (Kolařík and Kirkendall, 2010), whereas uninucleate vegetative mycelium is not harvested. Similarly the *Termitomyces* fungi have multinucleated mycelium and conidia but sexual spores are uninucleate (Nobre et al., 2014). This shows that increase in total genome mass and subsequent cell size inflation is often a way to acquire higher relative nutritional value in fungal insect symbionts.

In summary, we found a strong correlation between conidial DNA content and conidial volume in *Geosmithia* and confirmed that conidial DNA content plays an important role in the ecology of *Geosmithia* species. We assume that there is a trade-off between production of high amounts of small conidia, which are easily disseminated by air, and large conidia, which contain more nutrients, but whose dissemination is dependent on a vector. The enlargement of conidial DNA content and number of nuclei per conidium in *Geosmithia* could, thus, be an evolutionary tool for achieving optimal conidial volume, which might promote the evolution of obligatory symbiosis between fungi and their vectors.

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3.3. P3: Veselská, Tereza and Miroslav Kolařík (2019). Data in Brief: 27, 104568

Data in Brief

Fungal metabolic profile dataset was not influenced by long-term *in vitro* preservation of strains

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ABSTRAKT

Comparative ecophysiology is highly valuable approach to reveal adaptive traits linked with specific ecological niches. Although long-term *in vitro* preserved fungal isolates are often used for analyses, only sparse data is available about the effect of such handling on fungal physiology. The purpose of our data is to show the effect of long-term *in vitro* preservation of fungal strains on their metabolic profiles. This data is related to research paper “Adaptive traits of bark and ambrosia beetle-associated fungi” (Veselská et al., 2019). Biolog MicroPlates™ for Filamentous fungi were used to compare metabolic profiles between freshly isolated and long-term *in vitro* preserved strains of two *Geosmithia* species. Additionally, carbon utilization profiles of 35 *Geosmithia* species were assessed, including plant pathogen *G. morbida* and three ambrosia species. Data also shows differences in carbon utilization profiles among diverse ecology types presented in the genus.

Keywords:

Fungi, Metabolic profile, Biolog microarray, Fungal physiology, In vitro preservation, Comparative ecophysiology

Subject area	Microbiology
More specific subject area	Fungal physiology
Type of data	Table, graph
How data was acquired	Biolog MicroPlate™ for Filamentous fungi, plate reader INFINITE M200 TECAN (Tecan Instrument, Austria) with MAGELLAN software, PAST program
Data format	Analyzed data, Raw data in supplementary material
Experimental factors	Species ecology and time of preservation, i.e. short vs. long-term.
Experimental features	Fungal conidia were inoculated into Biolog MicroPlates™ for Filamentous fungi and the absorbance at 750 nm was recorded to assess fungal growth. Comparative ecophysiology and comparison of freshly isolated and long-term in vitro preserved fungal strains were assessed using statistical program PAST.
Data source location	Collection location, plant and beetle hosts are in Table 1
Data accessibility	Data is with this article.
Related research article	Veselská, T., Skelton, J., Kostovčík, M., Hulcr, J., Baldrian, P., Chudíčková, M., Cajthaml, T., Vojtová, T., Garcia-Fraile, P. and Kolařík, M., 2019. Adaptive traits of bark and ambrosia beetle-associated fungi. <i>Fungal Ecology</i> . 41, 165-176. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.funeco.2019.06.005

VALUE OF THE DATA

- Comparative ecophysiology is valuable tool for tracing of species adaptive traits and identification of potential virulence factors in plant, animal and human pathogenic fungi. Usually, long-term *in vitro* preserved isolates are used for physiological analysis, but little is known about the effect of such handling on fungal physiology. Presented data investigate the reliability of using the long-term preserved fungal cultures for physiological analysis.
- Data disproves negative effect of long-term preservation on fungal metabolic profile, which enables researchers to use such strains for physiological studies.
- Data shows metabolic profiles of carbon utilization for most of *Geosmithia* species which includes also ambrosia fungi and severe phytopathogen *G. morbida*.
- Raw data provides growth values on each carbon source. This is helpful for further identification of adaptive traits of these important species.

DATA

Biolog MicroPlate™ for Filamentous fungi was used to assess carbon sources utilization profiles of *Geosmithia* fungi living in symbiosis with bark beetles (1). Their ecology spans from facultative to obligatory ambrosia symbiosis and from saprotrophic to pathogenic nourishment of severe phytopathogen *G. morbida* (Table 1). The aims were to test whether metabolic profiles of *Geosmithia* species are modified by their ecology and whether long-term preservation of strains has effect on their metabolic profiles. The distinct metabolic profiles belonging to particular ecology types are pictured in Fig. 1 and Table S1. The similarity in metabolic profiles of freshly isolated and long-term preserved

strains of *Geosmithia* sp. 5 and *G. langdonii* is shown in Fig. 1 and Table S1. Raw data containing growth value of individual strains on each carbon source is presented in Table S1. Raw data is helpful for further identification of adaptive traits of important ambrosia and pathogenic species.

EXPERIMENTAL DESIGN, MATERIALS AND METHODS

Fungal strains

The metabolic profiles of 60 strains belonging to 35 *Geosmithia* species (Table 1) were analyzed. These strains are deposited in the Culture Collection of Fungi (CCF) or at Institute of Microbiology of the Czech Academy of Sciences for several years. Then, two species, *G. sp. 5* and *G. langdonii*, were chosen and the effect of long-term *in vitro* preservation (0–10 years) on fungal carbon assimilation profiles was observed. Fresh strains of these species were isolated from active beetle galleries in 2009 and identified as it is described in Pepori et al. (2). These strains were analyzed within a 2 months on Biolog MicroPlates™ for Filamentous fungi. Altogether, three “old” and six “new” strains of *G. sp. 5* and four “old” and four “new” strains of *G. langdonii* were compared. The species classification follows Kolařík et al. (3).

Biolog MicroPlate™ for Filamentous fungi

Biolog MicroPlate™ for Filamentous fungi contains 95 different dried carbon sources and one negative control. Fungal conidia from grown cultures were transferred into the inoculating fluid (0.25% Phytigel, 0.03% Tween 40) by rolling a swab across sporulating areas to get the final transmittance of $75 \pm 2\%$. The inoculated plates (200 µl per well) were then incubated in the dark at 25 °C and absorbance at 750 nm was used to measure mycelial growth at 24, 48, 72, 96 and 168 h. An absorbance reading taken 96 h after the inoculation was included in the analysis, because sporulation occurred in some strains after that time. Two technical replicates per strain were prepared.

Statistical analysis

The absorbance of the negative control was subtracted from all substrates within one plate and negative values were assigned a value of zero (4). Biolog™ data were visualized on PCA (Principal Component Analysis) in PAST program (5). The statistical significance of the type of ecology was evaluated by one-way NPMANOVA with Bonferroni-corrected *p* values using Bray-Curtis distance and 9999 permutations.

Table 1. List of *Geosmithia* species.

Species	Ecology type	Strain code	Culture collection	Strain code in Fig. 1	Substrate (mostly as insect vector/plant hosts)	Locality	Year of isolation	Reference
G. sp. 1	PF, G	1_1790	CCF4529	1	<i>Hypoborus ficus/Ficus carica</i>	Azerbaijan, Shaki Rayonu	2006	Kolařík et al. (2007)
G. sp. 2	PF, G	2_1510	CCF4270	2	<i>Scolytus kirschii/Ulmus minor</i>	Italy, Termoli	2004	Kolařík et al. (2007)
G. sp. 4	PF, G	4_1722	CCF4278	4	<i>Pteleobius vittatus F. / Ulmus laevis</i>	Czech R., Břeclav	2004	Kolařík et al. (2008)
G. putterillii	PF, G	6_103	CCF3342	6	<i>Scolytus rugulosus/Prunus sp.</i>	Czech R., Velemín	2000	Kolařík et al. (2004)
G. flava	PF, G	7_264	CCF3354	7	<i>Hylesinus fraxini/Fraxinus excelsior</i>	Slovakia, Muráň castle	2002	Kolařík et al. (2004)
G. sp. 8	PF, HWS	8_124	CCF3350	8a	<i>Scolytus intricatus/Quercus sp.</i>	Czech R., Prague	2001	Kolařík et al. (2008)
		8_1712a	CCF4277	8b	<i>Scolytus intricatus/Quercus cerris</i>	Bulgaria, Kardzaly	2005	Kolařík et al. (2008)
		37_1806	CCF4207	8c	<i>Scolytid beetle/Acacia smithii</i>	Australia, Eungella, Credition Hall	2006	Kolařík et al. (2007)
G. sp. 11	PF, G	11_551	CCF3555	11	<i>Scolytus intricatus/Quercus pubescens</i>	Hungary, Vilányi hegy Mts.	2003	Kolařík et al. (2008)
G. sp. 12	PF, HWS	12_284	CCF4300	12a	<i>Ernoporicus fagi/Fagus silvatica</i>	Slovakia, Pieniny National Park	2002	Kolařík et al. (2008)

		12_1632	CCF4274	12b	<i>Hylesinus varius/Fraxinus excelsior</i>	Czech R., Pacov	2005	Kolařík et al. (2008)
G. ulmacea	PF, HWS	13_924	CCF4601	13	<i>Scolytus multistriatus/Ulmus minor</i>	Czech R., Hodonín, Bulhary	2004	Kolařík et al. (2008)
G. obscura	PF, G	17_391	CCF3424	17	<i>Taphrorychus bicolor/Fagus sylvatica</i>	Czech R., Louny, Hřivice	2003	Kolařík et al. (2008)
G. lavendula	PF, G	18_1219	CCF4268	18a	<i>Hypoborus ficus/Ficus carica</i>	Croatia, Dalmatia, Sibenik	2005	Kolařík et al. (2007)
		18_1781	CCF4285	18b	<i>Hypoborus ficus/Ficus carica</i>	Azerbaijan, Baki Sahari, Baku	2006	Kolařík et al. (2007)
G. sp. 19	PF, G	19_1085a	CCF3658	19	<i>Hypoborus ficus/Ficus carica</i>	Italy, Molise, Termoli	2004	Kolařík et al. (2007)
G. sp. 20	PF, G	20_764	CCF4527	20	<i>Phloetribus scarabeoides/Olea europea</i>	Syria, Krak des Chevaliers	2004	Kolařík et al. (2007)
G. sp. 21	PF, G	21_1665	CCF4530	21	<i>Hypoborus ficus/Ficus carica</i>	Spain, Rosal de la Frontera	2005	Kolařík et al. (2007)
G. sp. 22	PF, G	22_739	CCF3645	22	<i>Phloetribus scarabeoides/Olea europea</i>	Jordan, Wadi al Mujib	2004	Kolařík et al. (2007)
G. morbida	HWS, P	41_1218	CCF3879 (CBS 124664)	41a	<i>Pityophthorus juglandis/J. nigra</i>	USA, Colorado, Boulder	2007	Kolařík et al. (2011)
		41_U173	CCF4576	41b	<i>Pityophthorus juglandis/J. nigra</i>	USA, California, Rio Oso	2009	Kolařík et al. (2011)

		41_U1259. 55	-	41c	<i>Pityophthorus juglandis/Juglans sp.</i>	USA, Oregon	2008	Kolařík et al. (2011)
		41_U1259. 59	-	41d	<i>Pityophthorus juglandis/Juglans sp.</i>	USA, Oregon	2008	Kolařík et al. (2011)
G. sp. 9	PF, SP	9_1210	CCF3703	9	<i>Cryphalus piceae/Abies alba</i>	Poland, Myślenice	2005	Jankowiak et Kolařík (2010)
G. sp. 16	PF, SP	16_08m	CCF4201	16	<i>Pityophthorus pityographus/Picea abies</i>	Poland, Czajowice	2007	Kolařík et Jankowiak (2013)
G. sp. 24	PF, SP	24_RJ06ka	CCF4525	24	<i>Pityogenes bidentatus/Pinus sylvestris</i>	Poland, Zaborze	2007	Kolařík et Jankowiak (2013)
G. sp. 26	PF, SP	26_1796	CCF4223	26	<i>Pityophthorus pityographus/Pinus silvestris</i>	Czech R., Seník	2006	Kolařík et Jankowiak (2013)
G. sp. 27	PF, SP	27_0919	CCF4206	27	<i>Pityogenes bidentatus/Pinus silvestris</i>	Poland, Żurada	2006	Kolařík et Jankowiak (2013)
G. sp. 28	PF, SP	28_279	CCF4210	28	<i>Polygraphus poligraphus/Picea abies</i>	Poland, Chyszówki	2007	Kolařík et Jankowiak (2013)
G. sp. 30	PF, SP	30_09m	CCF4209	30	<i>Pityophthorus pityographus /Picea abies</i>	Poland, Czajowice	2007	Kolařík et Jankowiak (2013)
G. sp. 31	PF, SP	31_21k	CCF4526	31	<i>Pityophthorus pityographus/Pinus sylvestris</i>	Poland, Czajowice	2007	Kolařík et Jankowiak (2013)

G. sp. 29	PF, SP	33_1827b	CCF4221	33	<i>Pityophthorus pityographus + Cryphalus piceae/Abies alba</i>	Czech R., Boubín hill	2008	Kolařík et Jankowiak (2013)
G. sp. 30	PF, SP	34_1833	CCF4208	34	<i>Cryphalus abietis/Abies alba</i>	Czech R., Jílové u Prahy	2008	Kolařík et Jankowiak (2013)
G. sp. 25	PF, SP	35_1835	CCF4205	25	<i>C. piceae + P. pityographus/Abies alba</i>	Czech R., Plešné jezero lake	2008	Kolařík et Jankowiak (2013)
G. sp. 5	PF, G	5_U1.2c.25	CNR28	5a	<i>Scolytus multistriatus/Ulmus minor</i>	Czech R., Středokluky	2009	Pepori et al. (2015)
		5_U6.3e.35	CNR48	5b	<i>Scolytus multistriatus/Ulmus minor</i>	Czech R., Velký Osek	2009	Pepori et al. (2015)
		5_U7.8b	CNR30	5c	<i>Scolytus multistriatus/Ulmus laevis</i>	Czech R., Velký Osek	2009	Pepori et al. (2015)
		5_U8.1a	CNR49	5d	<i>Scolytus multistriatus/Ulmus minor</i>	Czech R., Maršovice	2009	Pepori et al. (2015)
		5_U8.1b	-	5e	<i>Scolytus multistriatus/Ulmus minor</i>	Czech R., Maršovice	2009	Pepori et al. (2015)
		5_U8.12b	-	5f	<i>Scolytus multistriatus/Ulmus minor</i>	Czech R., Maršovice	2009	Pepori et al. (2015)

		5_580	-	5g	<i>Hypoborus ficus/Ficus carica</i>	France, Biaritz, Ondres	2003	Kolařík et al. (2007)
		5_1550	CCF4271	5h	<i>Scolytus intricatus/Quercus petraea</i>	Czech R., Mlynářův luh, 1997	1997	Kolařík et al. (2008)
		5_137m	CCF4215	5i	<i>Pityophthorus pityographus galleries/Picea abies</i>	Poland, Szydłowiec	2007	Kolařík et Jankowiak (2013)
<i>G. omnicola</i>	PF, G	10_989	CCF3560	10a	<i>Scolytus pygmaeus/Ulmus minor</i>	Czech R., Břeclav	2004	Kolařík et al. (2008)
		10_1788	CCF4286	10b	<i>Hypoborus ficus/Ficus carica</i>	Azerbaijan, Suvalan	2006	Kolařík et al. (2007)
		10_U2.6a	CNR5	10c	<i>Scolytus multistriatus/Ulmus minor</i>	Czech R., Středokluky	2009	Pepori et al. (2015)
		10_U7.5a	CNR8	10d	<i>Scolytus multistriatus/Ulmus laevis</i>	Czech R., Velký Osek	2009	Pepori et al. (2015)
		10_942	-	10e	<i>Hypoborus ficus/Ficus carica</i>	Croatia, Brač Island	2004	Kolařík et al. (2007)
<i>G. langdonii</i>	PF, G	15_U5.3a	CNR11	15a	<i>Scolytus multistriatus/Ulmus minor</i>	Czech R., Velký Osek	2009	Pepori et al. (2015)
		15_U7.9a	CNR6	15b	<i>Scolytus multistriatus/Ulmus laevis</i>	Czech R., Velký Osek	2009	Pepori et al. (2015)

		15_U8.6c	CNR117	15c	<i>Scolytus multistriatus/Ulmus minor</i>	Czech R., Maršovice	2009	Pepori et al. (2015)
		15_U8.12a	-	15d	<i>Scolytus multistriatus/Ulmus minor</i>	Czech R., Maršovice	2009	Pepori et al. (2015)
		15_1645	-	15e	<i>Scolytus multistriatus/Ulmus laevis</i>	Czech R., Neratovice	2005	Kolařík et al. (2005)
		15_1683	CCF4276	15f	<i>Ernoporus tiliae/Tilia sp.</i>	Czech R., Nové Hradky	2005	Kolařík et al. (2008)
		15_1603c	CCF3562	15g	<i>Phloeosinus thujae/Thuja occidentalis</i>	Czech R., Poříčí nad Sázavou	2005	Kolařík et al. (2008)
		15_1619	CCF4272	15h	<i>bostrichid beetle/Pistacia lentiscus</i>	Portugal, Sesimbra	2005	Kolařík et al. (2007)
G. cnesini	AF	29_1820	CCF4292	29	<i>Cnesinus lecontei/Croton draco</i>	Costa Rica, Heredia	2007	Kolařík et al. (2015)
G. microcorthyli	AF	38_A2	CCF3861	38	<i>Microcorthylyus sp./Cassia grandis</i>	Costa Rica, Heredia	2006	Kolařík et Kirkendall (2010)
G. eupagioceri	AF	39_A1	CCF3754	39	<i>Eupagiocerus dentipes/Paullinia renesii</i>	Costa Rica, Heredia	2006	Kolařík et Kirkendall (2010)
G. rufescens	AAF	42_1821	CCF4524	42	<i>Cnesinus lecontei/Croton draco</i>	Costa Rica, Heredia	2007	Kolařík et Kirkendall (2010)

Ecology : PF – association with phloem feeding beetles, G – generalist, SF – specialists to *Fagus*, SP – specialist to Pinaceae, HWS – hardwood specialists, P – pathogen, AF – ambrosia fungi, AAF – auxiliary ambrosia fungi.

Figure 1. Principal component analysis (PCA) plot of the metabolic profiles of 60 *Geosmithia* strains and comparison of “new” and “old” strains of *G. sp. 5* and *G. langdonii*. Different ecology types as follow: diamond – long-term co-evolved specialists, dot, triangle, star – facultative symbionts, cross – obligatory symbiont, inverted triangle – auxiliary ambrosial fungi, polygon, square – hardwood specialists, square – pathogen, triangle – new (5a-f) and old (5g-i) strains of *G. sp. 5*, star – new (15a-d) and old (15e-h) strains of *G. langdonii*. Based on one-way NPMANOVA, facultative generalists were significantly ($p < 0.005$) different from long-term co-evolved specialists and phytopathogen.

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Fungal Ecology

Adaptive traits of bark and ambrosia beetle-associated fungi

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ABSTRACT

A phenotype is the expression of interactions between species genotype and environment. We quantified the contributions of ecological and phylogenetic associations to phenotypic variation in *Geosmithia* fungi. *Geosmithia* are symbiotic beetle-associated saprotrophs with a range of life histories and host specificities, including obligate nutritional beetle mutualists (ambrosia fungi) and phytopathogens. We hypothesized that: (1) species phenotypes are better explained by their ecology than by their phylogenetic relationships; (2) niche specialization was accompanied by enzymatic capability losses; and (3) ambrosia *Geosmithia* species have higher nutritional quality and antibiotic capabilities than species with facultative symbioses. Our results confirmed that long-term co-evolved specialists have reduced metabolic breadth in comparison to generalists. Phytopathogenic *G. morbida* produces unique enzyme suites with affinity to ligno-cellulose. Mycelia of ambrosia fungi contain large amounts of oleic fatty acid with nutritive and possibly allelopathic function. Overall, our results indicate that *Geosmithia* ecology have greater effect on species phenotype than their phylogenetic relationships.

Keywords:

Ambrosia fungi, Generalists, Pine specialists, Phenotypic variation, Adaptive traits, Variation partitioning, Enzymes, Fatty acids, Geosmithia morbida

INTRODUCTION

Bark beetles primarily feed on plant tissues, but fungi are often important nutritional components throughout their life cycle (Harrington, 2005), and these fungi greatly affect the beetles' subcortical niche (Six, 2013). Fungal-beetle relationships can be described from several perspectives, i.e., according to the strength of the statistical frequency of association, according to the direction of

symbiosis (mutual benefit or parasitism) and whether coevolution has occurred between the beetle vectors and the fungi. Many hypotheses have been proposed about the influence of the most frequent fungal associates on the beetles, including pathogenic effects on the plant host, degradation of tree-produced defence compounds, increased stress tolerance or production of antibiotics (Hofstetter et al., 2015). However, statistical association does not imply causality, and even less is known about whether any reciprocal co-evolution has taken place. Similarly, some fungal associates of beetles are phytopathogenic, for example *Ophiostoma novo-ulmi*, *Leptographium wageneri* (Kirisits, 2004) and *Raffaelea lauricola* (Ploetz et al., 2013), but their effects on the fitness of the vectoring beetles have not been assessed. It is likely that the fungal associates influence the nutritional ecology of the beetles, which calls for comprehensive studies of their metabolic capabilities. Whereas the relationships between bark beetles and fungi are often facultative, associations between ambrosia beetles and their fungi are defined by obligate relationships. Ambrosia fungi are cultivated by ambrosia beetles in their galleries situated in the xylem and are typically the sole source of beetle nutrition. Thus ambrosia fungi are essential, mutually beneficial, and co-evolved.

Nutritional relationships between mutualistic fungi and their vectors drive symbioses. Yet we are only beginning to understand the adaptive evolutionary changes that arise from fungus-beetle associations. For example, mutualistic fungi accumulate nitrogen in galleries which greatly increases the rate of beetle development (Ayres et al., 2000). However, the specific nutritional ecology of ambrosia fungi has rarely been studied (Kim et al., 2011; De Fine Licht and Biedermann, 2012). Fungi also provide sterols needed by the beetles as hormone precursors (e.g. ecdysone) and as building blocks of the cell membrane (Clayton, 1963). Kok et al. (1979) suggested that ambrosia beetles from the genus *Xyleborus* cannot develop without the fungal sterol ergosterol. However, Bentz and Six (2006) did not find any relation in the closeness of the beetle/fungus association and the quantity of ergosterol in fungal dry weight. Thus, the importance of ergosterol content remains ambiguous. Most ambrosia fungi do not degrade the structural polymers of plant tissues, such as cellulose and lignin (Kim et al., 2011; De Fine Licht and Biedermann, 2012), yet there are exceptions such as basidiomycete ambrosia fungi (Kasson et al., 2016). In summary, fundamental questions about the beetle-fungus nutritional ecology remain unanswered, including which fungal traits, such as nutritional value (e.g. ergosterol and lipid content), allelopathy or enzymatic activities, are under selective pressure in relation to the association between transmitted fungi and their vectors.

Species in the fungal genus *Geosmithia* (Ascomycota: Hypocreales) are widespread and abundant associates of subcortical insects, particularly bark beetles (Curculionidae: Scolytinae) and auger beetles (Bostrichidae) (reviewed in Kolařík et al., 2017). The majority of *Geosmithia* species are frequently associated generalists, vectored by a broad range of insects feeding on a variety of mainly hardwood plants and sometimes occurring outside of the bark beetle galleries (e.g., as endophytes or soil fungi e Kolařík et al., 2017). However, some species have highly specific niches, such as the Pinaceae-specialists which have never been found outside of this habitat (Kolařík and Jankowiak, 2013; Jankowiak et al., 2014; Kolařík et al., 2017). Angiosperm tree-dwelling specialists are usually specific to particular tree genera: *G. ulmacea* to *Ulmus*, (Pepori et al., 2015), *G. sp. 8* to *Quercus*, *G. sp.12* to *Fraxinus* (Kolařík et al., 2008) and *G. morbida* to *Juglans* (Kolařík et al., 2011). *Geosmithia morbida* is a pathogenic species which causes Thousand Cankers Disease in black walnut (*Juglans nigra*) (Tisserat et al., 2009; Kolařík et al., 2011). It has impacted black walnut across the USA and has recently been found in Europe. The mechanisms of its pathogenicity remain unknown despite research efforts (Schuelke et

al., 2017). Three independent origins of nutritional ambrosia fungi have been documented in *Geosmithia*. These include *G. microcorthyli*, *G. eupagioceri* (Kolařík and Kirkendall, 2010) and likely also *G. cnesini* (Kolařík et al., 2015). *Geosmithia rufescens*, which accompanies the ambrosial *G. eupagioceri* and *G. cnesini* in ambrosia beetle galleries, is an auxiliary ambrosia fungus (Kolařík and Kirkendall, 2010).

Comparative eco-physiology was successfully used in tracing adaptive traits in fungal symbionts of ants (De Fine Licht, Schiøtt et al., 2010) and in a fungal pathogen of bats (Chaturvedi et al., 2018). The aims of this project were to use comparative ecophysiology, and to attribute functional trait variation among *Geosmithia* species to ecological or phylogenetic components. This separation further enabled us to identify traits that are under selective pressure, and their importance in the formation of particular symbiotic associations.

In this study, we analyzed the enzyme profiles, biochemical composition and antibiotic capabilities of *Geosmithia* species. Enzymatic analyses outline the abilities of fungi to metabolize nutrients in plant tissues and thus make them accessible to the beetles through mycophagy. Biochemical composition approximates the nutritive value of fungal mycelia. Antibiotic capabilities reflect the potential of fungi to protect beetle galleries against microbial competitors and enemies. Our hypotheses were that: (1) species phenotypes are better explained by their ecology than by their phylogenetic relationships; (2) niche specialization was accompanied by enzymatic capability losses; and (3) *Geosmithia* mutualists have higher nutritional quality and antibiotic capabilities than species with facultative symbioses.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Fungal material and cultivation

Twenty-three *Geosmithia* species were selected (Table 1) to represent diverse individual ecological strategies and phylogenetic lineages. These strains had been kept in culture for several years (1–10 y); this has no effect on their metabolic capabilities, however (Veselská and Kolařík, in press). We define generalists as those found on a wide range of plant families, primarily angiosperm trees. Accordingly, we define specialists as those restricted to a single plant genus or family, including the pathogen *G. morbida*, and ambrosia fungi specific to a single ambrosia beetle taxon. These strains are deposited in the Culture Collection of Fungi (CCF) or at the Institute of Microbiology of the Czech Academy of Sciences. The default growth medium was 2% malt extract agar (malt extract 20 g, glucose 20 g, peptone 1 g, 1 l of distilled H₂O), unless noted otherwise.

Phylogenetic analyses

All isolates were identified to the species level based on ITS rDNA sequences or alternative gene markers described in the original publications (Table 1). A phylogeny was constructed based on partial sequences of elongation factor 1 α (TEF-1 α) and the second largest subunit of the RNA polymerase II gene (RPB2). Both genes were amplified and sequenced according to Kolařík et al. (2017). Sequence alignments were obtained using MAFFT 6 (Kato and Toh, 2008) (see Appendix 1 for dataset). Bayesian phylogenetic analyses were performed using MrBayes v3.1.2 (Ronquist and Huelsenbeck, 2003). A metropolis-coupled Markov chain Monte Carlo search algorithm with 2,000,000 generations was used. Burn-in was determined using Tracer 1.4 (<http://tree.bio>).

ed.ac.uk/software/tracer) and discarded. Evolutionary models (TN93 + G) were determined by using MEGA 5.05 (Tamura et al.,2011).

Enzymatic analysis

Analysis of extracellular enzyme activities

Enzymes were extracted from cultures growing on a seminatural medium (SNM) for one month. The SNM, developed during the course of our study, was composed of minced bark beetle adults (*Ips typographus*) and phloem of lime (*Tilia cordata*) and pine (*Pinus sylvestris*) as these trees are a common substrate for *Geosmithia*. Minced beetles and phloem were air dried, sterilized by autoclaving and mixed in a ratio of 1:23:23 (beetles: lime phloem: pine phloem). Glass Petri dishes with the sterile dried SNM (6 g per dish) were moistened by an inoculation solution (1 g of Bacto-pepton and 1 g of Bacto-yeast extract, Difco, in 1 l of distilled water) containing conidia (3.2–4.5 10⁶ conidia/ml) to attain the final moisture level of 75%. Inoculated SNM dishes were sealed with adhesive tape at four points for safe manipulation, deposited in open plastic bags to retain the moisture and air flow, and cultivated for one month. After that, the entire content of each Petri dish was put in 50-ml tubes, mixed with 30 ml of 50 mM sodium acetate buffer (pH 5.0) and extracted for 2 h at 4 °C with constant mixing. The mixture was centrifuged for 8 min at 3,000 rpm to exclude the SNM. The supernatant containing extracellular enzymes was further filtered through filter paper to remove remaining contaminants.

The spectrum of analysed enzymes is listed in Table 2 together with their function and assays used. We assessed the activities of β -glucosidase, α -glucosidase, cellobiohydrolase, β -xylosidase, N-acetylglucosaminidase, arylsulfatase, phosphomonoesterase, phosphodiesterase, alanine- and leucine aminopeptidases with fluorogenic substrates 4-methylumbelliferone (MUF) and 7-amido-4-methylcoumarin (AMC) (Megazyme, Ireland); individual fluorogenic substrates are stated in Table S1. Fluorescence of the released reaction products was measured as described previously (Baldrian, 2009) using a method modified from Vepsäläinen et al. (2001). The fluorescence value of each MUF/AMC fluorogenic substrate was corrected by subtraction of background fluorescence of the SNM medium.

Laccase (EC 1.10.3.2) activity was measured by monitoring the oxidation of ABTS (2,2'-azinobis-3-ethylbenzothiazoline-6-sulfonic acid (Bourbonnais and Paice, 1990);) in citrate-phosphate buffer (100 mM citrate, 200 mM phosphate, pH 5.0). The formation of the resulting green dye was evaluated spectrophotometrically at 420 nm. The activities of manganese peroxidase (EC 1.11.1.13; MnP), Mn-independent peroxidases (MIP) and oxidases were assayed according to Ngo and Lenhoff (1980) in succinate-lactate buffer (100 mM, pH 4.5). MBTH (3-methyl-2-benzothiazolinone hydrazone) and DMAB (3,3-dimethylaminobenzoic acid) are oxidatively coupled by the action of the enzyme, and the formation of a purple indamine dye product was detected spectrophotometrically at 595 nm. The activities of MIP were measured in samples without manganese sulfate, which was substituted by an equimolar amount of ethylenediaminetetraacetate. For the detection of the activity of oxidases, hydrogen peroxide was substituted by water. Activities of endo-1,4- β -glucanase (EC 3.2.1.4) and endo-1,4- β -xylanase (EC 3.2.1.8) were measured with Azo-CM Cellulose and Azo-Xylan, respectively, using the protocol and calibration curves of the supplier (Megazyme, Ireland).

Table 1. List of analysed *Geosmithia* strains, their ecology, and methods used.

<i>Geosmithia</i> spp.	References	Ecology	Strain	Genbank accession number		Codes used in figures	Extracellular enzymes	Biolog FF	Biolog PM, sporulation	Lipids, ergosterol	Antibiotic activity
				RPB2	TEF-1 α						
G. sp. 1	(Kolařík et al. 2007)	PF, G	CCF4529	Submitted	submitted	G1	+	+	+	+	-
G. putterillii	(Kolařík et al. 2004)	PF, G	CCF3342	Submitted	submitted	Gput	+	+	+	+	+
G. flava	(Kolařík et al. 2004)	PF, G	CCF3354	Submitted	submitted	Gfla	+	+	+	+	+
G. sp. 8	(Kolařík et al. 2008)	PF, HWS	CCF4528	Submitted	submitted	G8	+	+	+	+	+
			CCF4207	Submitted	submitted		+	+	+	+	+
G. sp. 9	Jankowiak et Kolařík (2010)	PF, SP	CCF3703	Submitted	submitted	G9	+	+	+	+	+
G. sp. 12	(Kolařík et al. 2008)	PF, HWS	CCF4274	Submitted	submitted	G12	-	+	+	-	-
G. ulmacea	(Kolařík et al. 2008)	PF, HWS	CCF4601	Submitted	submitted	Gulm	-	+	+	-	+
G. langdonii	(Kolařík et al. 2017)	PF, G	CCF3554	HG799926	HG799874.1	Glan	+	+	+	+	-
G. sp. 16	(Kolařík et al. 2008)	PF, SP	CCF4201	HE604234.1	HE604206	G16	+	+	+	+	-
G. sp. 20	(Kolařík et al. 2007)	PF, G	CCF4527	Submitted	submitted	G20	+	+	+	+	+
G. sp. 21	(Kolařík et al. 2007)	PF, G	CCF4530	Submitted	submitted	G21	+	+	+	+	-

G. sp. 22	(Kolařík et al. 2007)	PF, G	CCF3645	Submitted	submitted	G22	+	+	-	+	+
G. sp. 24	(Kolařík and Jankowiak 2013)	PF, SP	CCF4525	Submitted	submitted	G24	+	+	+	+	+
G. sp. 25	(Kolařík and Jankowiak 2013)	PF, SP	CCF4205	HE604253	HE604219	G25	+	+	+	+	+
G. sp. 26	(Kolařík and Jankowiak 2013)	PF, SP	CCF4223	LN907601.1	LN907596	G26	+	+	+	+	+
G. sp. 27	(Kolařík and Jankowiak 2013)	PF, SP	CCF4206	HG799893.1	HG799839.1	G27	+	+	+	+	+
G. sp. 31	(Kolařík and Jankowiak 2013)	PF, SP	CCF4526	HE604256	HE604230.1	G31	+	+	+	+	+
G. microcorthyli	(Kolařík and Kirkendall 2010)	AF	CCF3861	FM986794	submitted	Gmic	+	+	+	+	+
G. eupagioceri	(Kolařík and Kirkendall 2010)	AF	CCF3754	Submitted	submitted	Geup	+	+	+	+	+
G. morbida	(Kolařík et al. 2011)	HWS, P	CCF3879	Submitted	submitted	Gmor	+	+	+	+	+
			1259	Submitted	submitted		+	+	+	+	+
			CCF4576	Submitted	submitted		+	+	+	+	-

<i>G. rufescens</i>	Kolařík and Kirkendall 2010)	AAF	CCF4524	Submitted	submitted	Gruf	+	+	+	+	+
<i>G. sp.</i> CCF4200	unpublished	PF, G	CCF4200	Submitted	submitted	G36	+	+	+	+	+
<i>G. cnesini</i>	Kolařík and Kirkendall 2010)	AF	CCF4292	Submitted	submitted	Gcne	+	+	+	+	+

Ecology : PF – association with phloem feeding beetles, G – generalist, SF – specialists to *Fagus*, SP – specialist to Pinaceae, HWS – hardwood specialists, P – pathogen, AF – ambrosia fungi, AAF – auxiliary ambrosia fungi, +/- – analysis done/undone.

Table 2. List of analyzed enzymes, their function and assays.

Process	Enzyme	Assay
Cellulose degradation	β -glucosidase	MUF
	cellobiohydrolase	MUF
	endoglucanase	depolymerization
Degradation of polysaccharides	α -glucosidase	MUF
	N-acetylglucosaminidase	MUF
Degradation of hemicelluloses	β -xylosidase	MUF
	endoxylanase	depolymerization
S acquisition	Arylsulfatase	MUF
P acquisition	phosphomonoesterase	MUF
	Phosphodiesterase	MUF
N acquisition	alanine aminopeptidase	AMC
	leucine aminopeptidase	AMC
Lignin transformation	Peroxidases	DMAB
	Laccase	ABTS
	Oxidases	DMAB

MUF – methylumbelliferone, AMC – amidomethylcoumarin, DMAB – 3,3-dimethylaminobenzoic acid, ABTS – 2,2'-azinobis-3-ethylbenzothiazoline-6-sulfonic acid.

Biolog analysis

Biolog FF MicroPlate™ (FF) and Biolog Phenotype Micro-Arrays™ (PM) (Biolog, Inc., Hayward, CA) were used to evaluate the assimilation profiles of carbon (FF), nitrogen (PM3B), phosphorus, sulfur (PM4A) and nutrient supplement (PM5) sources following manufacturer's instructions. The inoculated plates were then incubated in the dark at 25 °C and absorbance at 750 nm was used to measure mycelial growth at 24, 48, 72, 96 and 168 h. Two technical replicates per strain were prepared for FF plates and one replicate for PM plates. An absorbance reading taken 96 h after the inoculation was included in the analysis. The absorbance of the negative control was subtracted from all substrates within one plate and negative values were assigned a value of zero (Garland, 1996).

In addition, substrates in FF plates were divided into several guilds (carbohydrates, carboxylic acids, amino acids, amines/amides, polymers and miscellaneous) following Dobranic and Zak (1999), with the exceptions of the amino acids guild, which was combined with the guild of amines/amides, and the guild of polymers, which was transferred to the 'miscellaneous' guild containing various type of substrates. The reason for the merging was the low number of substrates within the particular guilds. We also evaluated sporulation in each PM well using a stereomicroscope 1 week after inoculation. Sporulation was classified into four levels: 0 – none, 1 – low, 2 – middle, 3 – high.

Analysis of total fatty acids and ergosterol

For measurements of fatty acids and ergosterol content, fungi were grown in a Petri dish for 11 d on MEA overlaid with a cellophane disc to physically separate the fungal biomass from the medium. Total fatty acids from lyophilized fungal biomass were extracted in a mixture of chloroform-methanol-phosphate buffer (1:2:0.8). Fatty acid fractions were separated using solid-phase extraction cartridges (LiChrolut Si 60, Merck), and the samples were subjected to mild methanolysis (Šnajdr et al.,

2008). The free methyl esters of fatty acids were analyzed by gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (Varian 3400; ITS-40, Finnigan). The gas chromatography (GC) instrument was equipped with a split/splitless injector, and a DB-5MS column was used for separation (60 m, 0.25 mm i.d., 0.25 mm film thickness). The temperature programme started at 60 °C and was held for 1 min in splitless mode. Then, the splitter was opened and the oven was heated to 160 °C at a rate of 25 °C/min. The second temperature ramp was up to 280 °C at a rate of 2.5 °C/min; this temperature was maintained for 10 min. The solvent delay time was set to 8 min. The transfer line temperature was set to 280 °C. Mass spectra were recorded at 1 scan/s under electron impact at 70 eV, with a mass range of 50–350 amu. Methylated fatty acids were identified according to their mass spectra using a mixture of chemical standards obtained from Sigma.

The content of ergosterol in dry weight of 11 d old mycelium was analyzed by the method developed by Bååth (2001) and modified by Šnajdr et al. (2008). Lyophilized samples were sonicated (90 min, 70 °C) in 1 ml of cyclohexane and 3 ml of 10% KOH in methanol. Then, 1 ml of distilled water was added to samples and ergosterol was triple-extracted with 2 ml of cyclohexane. The samples were dried under nitrogen and dissolved in 1 ml of methanol by heating to 40 °C for 15 min. The samples were analyzed isocratically using a Waters Alliance high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) system (Waters, USA) with methanol as a mobile phase at a flow rate of 1 ml/min. Ergosterol was detected using a UV light at 282 nm.

Antibiotic production assessment

To quantify the diversity of antibiotic compounds produced by individual *Geosmithia* species, we used the Kirby-Bauer disk diffusion susceptibility approach. An optimized extraction procedure was developed by testing different solvents and sorbents. Subsequent ultra-high-performance liquid chromatography method with diode array detection (UPLC-DAD) analysis was applied to cover the broadest spectrum of extracted extracellular compounds (Tylová et al., 2011). After 14 d of submerged cultivation of *Geosmithia* spp., the fermentation broth (MEA without agar, shaken on a rotary shaker, 3.4 Hz) was centrifuged (15 min at 4,000 g) and then filtered through a 2-µm glass microfibre filter (Whatman, UK). Prior to solid phase extraction (SPE), the pH of the samples was adjusted to 3 with formic acid (98–100%). The SPE was performed using 60-mg Oasis MCX cartridges. The sorbent was conditioned with 2 ml of methanol followed by equilibration with 2 ml of Milli-Q water; 50 ml of fermentation broth from each strain was passed through the cartridge at the flow rate of 3 ml/min, and the sorbent was then rinsed with 2 ml of water and 2 ml of a formic acid/water solution (1:99, v/v). Afterwards, the cartridge was air-dried and the secondary metabolites were eluted using 2 ml of methanol. The methanol extracts were evaporated to dryness and reconstituted in 100 µl of methanol. The organisms used for antimicrobial activity testing included Gram-positive bacteria *Kocuria rhizophila* CCM = ATCC9341, previously known as *Micrococcus luteus*, Gram-negative bacteria *Escherichia coli* ATCC3988, yeast *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* CCM8191 (=ATCC9763) and the following filamentous fungi: saprophyte *Penicillium decumbens* CCF4423, insect pathogenic *Beauveria bassiana* CCF4422 and endophyte *Graphium fimbriisporum* CCF4421. Bacteria were cultivated on a beef extract medium containing: beef extract 10 g/l, peptone 10 g/l, NaCl 5 g/l and agar 20 g/l; pH 7.2 adjusted by NaOH. Yeasts were cultivated on a yeast extract medium consisting of: glucose 40 g/l, peptone 4 g/l, yeast extract 5 g/l and agar 20 g/l; pH 7.0 adjusted by NaOH. Filamentous fungi were cultivated on MEA. The plates were then overlaid with the indication organism (suspended in a sterile saline solution and vortexed until a smooth suspension was obtained). The filter paper discs were impregnated with

Figure 1. Analytical pipeline used to separate the effects of ecology from those of phylogenetic history along several axes of phenotypic variation in *Geosmithia* fungi. Our pipeline provides: (1) a quantitative assessment of phenotypic variation explained by ecological and phylogenetic differences among fungi, (2) a statistical test of the significance of each source of variation, while accounting for variation explained by the other source, and (3) visualizations of the independent effects of ecology on phenotypic variation after removing phylogenetic effects.

25 ml of fungal extract and air-dried. A disc impregnated with methanol served as a blank control. Afterwards, the impregnated discs were placed on to the surface of the agar. Growth inhibition zones, indicating the antimicrobial activity of the fungal extract, were detected after 24 h of incubation at 30 °C for bacteria, after 24 h at 38 °C for yeast and after 48 h at 24 °C for filamentous fungi. Following the incubation, inhibition zones were evaluated and measured (Bauer et al., 1966).

Statistical analyses

Our objective was to determine the degree to which functional traits of *Geosmithia* are driven by their ecology and constrained by their evolutionary histories. This was accomplished by regression of phylogenetic eigenvectors and ecological axes against several functional trait datasets in a variation partitioning analysis (Fig. 1).

Predictor variables 1: phylogenetic eigenvectors

Phylogenetic eigenvectors are vector representations of phylogenetic relationships among taxa and can be used as covariates in linear and nonlinear models to account for variation among taxa (e.g. ecological, morphological, physiological, etc.) that is attributed to phylogenetic relationships (Diniz-Filho et al., 2012). Phylogenetic eigenvectors are orthogonal and together describe all scales of phylogenetic variation among taxa in the dataset. They can, therefore, be used to rigorously account for broad- and fine-scale phylogenetic correlations among taxa (Tedersoo et al., 2013). To generate phylogenetic eigenvectors for *Geosmithia*, branch lengths from the best scoring tree obtained by the phylogenetic analysis were imported using the ‘ape’ R package (Paradis et al., 2004); (R Development Core Team, 2010) and converted into an ultrametric phylogram, which is an additive phylogenetic tree for which all paths from the root to branch tips are equal. From the ultrametric phylogram, a pairwise distance matrix of branch lengths was then calculated for all taxa. Principal coordinates analysis was then used to calculate phylogenetic eigenvectors from the pairwise distance matrix of branch lengths (Fig. 2, Diniz-Filho et al., 2012).

Predictor variables 2: ecological axes:

The contribution of realized niches to functional traits was tested by three different approaches:

Ecological affinities among *Geosmithia* species were calculated from their known ranges of associations with host plant families (Fig. 3). A binary matrix of observed associations between *Geosmithia* species and plant families was imported using the ‘vegan’ R package (R Development Core Team, 2010; Oksanen et al., 2013) and used to calculate a Jaccard distance matrix. The Jaccard distances showed signs of distance saturation (52% of rigorously account for broad- and fine-scale phylogenetic correlations among taxa (Tedersoo et al., 2013). To generate phylogenetic eigenvectors for *Geosmithia*, branch lengths from the best scoring tree obtained by the phylogenetic analysis were imported using the ‘ape’ R package (Paradis et al., 2004); (R Development Core Team, 2010) and converted into an ultrametric phylogram, which is an additive phylogenetic tree for which all paths from distances were equal to 1) because many *Geosmithia* species shared no observed host taxa. To examine ecological relationships among taxa with no shared host species, hybrid multidimensional scaling (HDMS) was used to ordinate all *Geosmithia* species according Jaccard distance, using the monoMDS() function and allowing equal dissimilarities to have different fitted values (using the ‘hybrid’ method and ‘weak treatment’ for ties; see Tuomisto et al., 2012) and supporting information

for the monoMDS() function in the 'vegan' package in R 3.3.3). The dimensionality ($k = 3$) was chosen based on an assessment of a scree plot (McCune et al., 2002). The resultant HDMS axes scores were used in subsequent variation partitioning to represent ecological relationships among Geosmithia species. Simulation studies have established HDMS as an effective means to resolve relationships among entities with no shared qualities for subsequent variation partitioning analyses (Tuomisto et al., 2012).

1. To assess effects of generalist versus specialist ecologies (TAXA), independent of plant host composition, we also included the number of plant families each species is known to associate with.
2. To determine the effects of insect fungiculture (AMB), we also included a binary variable differentiating between ambrosial or non-ambrosial fungi.

Figure 2. Bayesian inference tree and graphical representation of phylogenetic eigenvectors used in variation partitioning analysis. Circles represent eigenvector coordinates. The size of each circle is scaled to absolute values, and black-and-white circles represent negative and positive values, respectively.

We used a Mantel test (mantel() function in the 'vegan' R package) to test for correlations between the two predictor dataset, namely the phylogenetic and ecological distance matrices.

Figure 3. Ecological variables used in variation partitioning. At the top, a hierarchical clustering dendrogram shows the ecological relationships among *Geosmithia* species (with the numbers of species as labels). The circle plot illustrates ecological variables, including hybrid multidimensional scaling (HMDS) axes, the number of known host plant families and the presence of an ambrosial lifestyle. Circle size is scaled to the absolute value for each variable. White indicates positive values and black negative values. HMDS scores were obtained by ordination of a Jaccard distance matrix calculated from the binary host plant association matrix shown at the bottom of the figure. The HMDS axes describe the dimensions of variation among plant associations of *Geosmithia* species. For instance, HMDS1 captures the difference between pine specialist taxa (cluster on the far left), generalists (middle) and ambrosia fungi (cluster on the far right). Used code for species: 13 – *G. ulmacea*, 6 – *G. putterillii*, 10 – *G. omnicola*, 18 – *G. lavendula*, 38 – *G. microcorthyli*, 41 – *G. morbida*, 29 – *G. cnesini*, 42 – *G. rufescens*, 39 – *G. eupagioceri*.

Response variables and variation partitioning:

A response matrix was constructed for each of several functional trait datasets. Because of high variability in the magnitude of measurements for elements within matrices, all columns of each functional trait matrix were standardized by the column maximum and normalized as needed. To avoid over-fitting the subsequent variation partitioning model, we used forward model selection of phylogenetic eigenvectors and, separately, forward selection of ecological HDMS based on adjusted R-squared and an alpha significance level determined by 9,999 permutations (Blanchet et al., 2008). We also only included phylogenetic eigenvectors that captured more than two percent of the variation among isolates. Model selection was carried out using the 'packfor' R package (Blanchet et al., 2008) with a significance level of $\alpha = 0.1$ to identify potentially important explanatory vectors, as in Tedersoo

et al. (2013). Only the single best predictor was retained when automated selection did not retain any predictors. Variation partitioning was then used to determine the amount of variation explained by the selected ecological and phylogenetic models, and the amount of explained variation that was shared between explanatory variables. Redundancy analysis (RDA) was used to test the statistical significance of testable components of the variation partitioning, namely the effect of ecology with phylogenetic effects removed and the effect of phylogeny with ecological effects removed (Peres-Neto et al., 2006). For each functional trait dataset with a significant ecological model, we visualized the RDA model that represented the variation of the given functional trait among *Geosmithia* species that was explained by their ecological distance (approximated by host plant associations), with phylogenetic effects removed.

We also investigated relationships between ecological and phylogenetic predictors with the univariate response of the diversity of extracellular enzymes produced by each species and the diversity of substrates that each species could utilize. Biolog™ growth profiles were separated for carbon, nitrogen, phosphorus and nutrient supplement assays prior to univariate analyses. For each response variable, diversity was calculated as Simpson's index of diversity. Simpson's diversity was transformed to real number equivalents (Jost, 2006), which reflects the richness and evenness of growth profiles by approximating the number of substrates with an equal measured growth rate for each species. Model selection was used as described above to select significant ecological and phylogenetic predictors. Final models were fit using the `lm()` function in the base R package.

Differences in the amounts of ergosterol, carbon guilds and saturation of fatty acids between ecological groups were evaluated using Kruskal-Wallis statistics supplemented with a Mann-Whitney pairwise comparison and Bonferroni correction. Both analyses were carried out in PAST software (Hammer et al., 2001).

RESULTS

We identified the independent impacts of ecology and phylogeny on functional traits in *Geosmithia*, which allowed a robust assessment of their individual effects. This result is supported by the lack of a correlation between phylogenetic and ecological distances according to Mantel's test (Fig. S1), and was confirmed by variation partitioning analyses, which showed no significant shared fraction between ecological and phylogenetic predictors in any of the functional trait datasets. Overall, ecology was a much better predictor of the phenotype in every analysis (Table 3). In cases where model selection retained some phylogenetic eigenvectors (Table 4), the phylogenetic fraction was not significant in variation partitioning (Table 3), except lipid analysis where the phylogenetic fraction was small but statistically significant.

Enzymatic analysis

The ecological variables explained more than 20% of the variation observed in the enzymatic composition (Table 3) which was well predicted by ecological affinities (HMDS predictors) (Table 5). The initial model selection also retained the phylogenetic eigenvector PE4 (Table 4). However, PE4 did not explain a significant fraction in the variation partitioning analysis (Table 3). In a univariate analysis, there were no significant relationships between ecology or phylogeny and enzyme diversity. This indicates that all depending on the ecology of *Geosmithia* species. *Geosmithia* pine specialists formed a distinct group in the RDA analysis (Fig. 4), which may reflect their ecological specialization to the pine environment. They were associated with higher production of lignin and cellulose-transforming

enzymes (laccase, oxidase, manganese peroxidase, β -glucosidase and cellobiohydrolase), phosphodiesterase and leucine aminopeptidase. Generalists were characterized by the production of enzymes cleaving hemicellulose (β -xylosidase, α -glucosidase and endoxylanase) and arylsulfatase, and by almost absence of enzymes modifying lignin. The pathogen *G. morbida* was unique in production of all enzymes cleaving the structural components of the plant cell wall (i.e. cellulose, hemicellulose and lignin); nevertheless, their production was moderate. Ambrosia fungi were dissimilar to each other in the composition of their extracellular enzymes. *G. microcorthyli* exhibited the highest activities of lignin transforming enzymes (laccase, Mn-peroxidase and oxidases), *G. eupagioceri* displayed high activity of endoxylanase. *G. cnesini* and the auxiliary ambrosial *G. rufescens* did not exhibit any enzymes linked with the degradation of lignocellulose. The ability to degrade chitin (N-acetylglucosaminidase) was detected in all studied strains and was not linked with species ecology (Table S1).

Table 3. Proportion of variation in each functional trait dataset explained exclusively by ecology (left shaded column), exclusively by phylogeny (right shaded column) and the shared portion (centre shaded column). Bold font indicates statistical significance according to partial RDA (* $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$). The shared portion of variation explained by both ecology and phylogeny cannot be tested for significance.

Functional trait datasets	Ecology	ecology + phylogeny	phylogeny
Extracellular enzymes	0.204**	0.016	0.014
Biolog TM – growth	0.170**	0.020	0.01
Biolog TM - sporulation	0.122*	0.005	0.035
Lipids	0.060*	0.000	0.044*

Table 4. Selected phylogenetic vectors from forward model selection.

Functional traits	phy. Eigenvectors	R-squared	cum. adj R ²	p-value
Extracellular enzymes	PE4	0.081	0.030	0.098
Biolog TM - growth	PE2	0.074	0.025	0.064
Biolog TM -sporulation	PE2	0.089	0.041	0.074
Lipids	PE1	0.898	0.039	0.064

Biolog MicroPlates analysis

Ecological predictors explained 17% of the compositional variation in growth performance on BiologTM substrates whereas phylogenetic relationships were not significant predictors (Table 3). The number of plant taxa (TAXA) was the strongest ecological predictor, though one dimension of ecological affinities (HMDS2) and the variable differentiating between ambrosial and free-living (AMB) fungi were also significant (Table 5, Fig. 5). Ecology also explained variation in the total diversity of substrate utilization by each *Geosmithia* species (Table 6). Diversity in utilized carbon and nitrogen sources was best explained by predictors of ecological affinity (HMDS1 and HMDS2). By contrast, the

best predictor of diversity in the utilization of phosphorus and sulfur substrates and nutrient supplement was the number of known plant hosts (TAXA) and ambrosial status, respectively (Table 6). Pine specialists and the pathogen *G. morbida* have lost a number of metabolic pathways. This corresponds to the significant difference in substrate diversity. The proportional representation of carbon guilds remained similar between the ecological groups (Kruskal-Wallis, $p > 0.4$) whereas specialists and the plant pathogen exhibited a slight shift towards saccharides. Ambrosial life history (AMB) and ecological affinities (HMDS2) were the best predictors explaining variation in sporulation on Biolog™ microplates (Table 5). The sporulation of ambrosia fungi and the auxiliary ambrosia species *G. rufescens* was supported on nutrient supplement substrates whereas that of hardwood specialists *G. sp. 12*, *G. ulmacea* and *G. sp. 8* was enhanced on phosphorus and sulfur sources (Fig. 6).

Table 5. Selected ecological vectors from forward model selection for multivariate phenotype data. HMDS axes are visualized in Figure 3. TAXA = number of plant families known to associate with, AMB = ambrosial life history.

Functional traits	predictors	R-squared	cum. adj R ²	p-value
Extracellular enzymes	HMDS2	0.116	0.066	0.006
	HMDS1	0.106	0.130	0.008
	HMDS3	0.095	0.188	0.026
	AMB	0.068	0.220	0.076
Biolog™ – growth	TAXA	0.173	0.129	0.001
	HMDS2	0.087	0.178	0.043
	AMB	0.100	0.245	0.020
Biolog™ – sporulation	AMB	0.132	0.086	0.048
	HMDS2	0.082	0.127	0.075
Lipids	HMDS1	0.101	0.051	0.037

Table 6. Best linear models for total diversity of carbon, nitrogen, phosphorus, and nutrient supplement substrates that each species could assimilate. No phylogenetic eigenvectors were retained for any substrate type. HMDS axes = plant affinities are visualized in Figure 3, TAXA = number of plant families, AMB = ambrosial life history. For the best carbon model, adjusted $R^2 = 0.552$, $F_{2,18} = 13.34$, $p < 0.001$. For the best nitrogen model, adjusted $R^2 = 0.448$, $F_{2,18} = 9.12$, $p = 0.002$. For phosphorus, adjusted $R^2 = 0.368$, $F_{2,19} = 9.274$, $p = 0.007$. For nutrient supplements adjusted $R^2 = 0.448$, $F_{2,19} = 12.650$, $p = 0.002$.

Models	Predictor	Estimate	Standard error	T	p-value
Carbon	HMDS2	-13.584	2.968	-4.577	< 0.001
	HMDS1	-6.207	2.000	-3.104	0.006
Nitrogen	HMDS1	-9.893	2.813	-3.517	0.002
	HMDS2	-12.373	4.176	-2.963	0.008
Phosphorus and sulphur	TAXA	3.317	1.030	3.045	0.007
Nutrient supplement	AMB	21.840	6.142	3.556	0.002

Ergosterol and total fatty acids

The proportional content of ergosterol in dry weight ranged from 0.23 to 0.81%, with a mean value of 0.42%. Twenty-four different fatty acids were detected in *Geosmithia* (Table S2). The most abundant fatty acids were palmitic acid (16:0), linoleic acid (18:2 ω 6,9), oleic acid (18:1 ω 9), stearic acid (18:0) and an unidentified acid (20:4). Ecological affinity (HMDS1) was the best predictor, although phylogeny also significantly contributed to the lipid variation. All three ambrosial species were characterized by high proportions of oleic acid. Nevertheless, *G. sp. 8* and *G. sp. CCF4200*, sister species to the ambrosial *G. microcorthyli*, displayed the same pattern, so the ambrosial vs. free-living predictor was not significant (Table 5, Fig. 7). The proportional lipid content in dry weight was similar among the *Geosmithia* species, with a median of approximately 10%. We divided fatty acids into three groups: saturated, unsaturated (with one double bond) and polyunsaturated. In congruence with previous results (HMDS1 vector), pine specialists were statistically separated from ambrosia fungi in all fatty acid groups (Kruskal-Wallis, $p < 0.05$). Ambrosia fungi had the highest proportion of saturated and unsaturated fatty acids but contained the lowest proportion of polyunsaturated fatty acids. The pathogen *G. morbida* displayed a shift from unsaturated to polyunsaturated fatty acids, which constituted up to nearly 40% of the total fatty acids.

Kirby-Bauer disk diffusion susceptibility test

We detected antibiotic production against at least one model organism in nearly half of the strains tested, but it was not connected with species ecology. Inhibition of the insect pathogen *Beauveria bassiana* and Gram-positive bacteria *Kucuria rhizophila* was the most frequent (Table S3). The most potent species were pine specialist *G. sp. 9*, which inhibited all model organisms, followed by the ambrosia species *G. microcorthyli* and the pathogen *G. morbida*, which inhibited five of six

model organisms. Nevertheless, high intra-species variability was documented in some species, which indicates either that this trait is strain-specific or that our method was not sufficiently sensitive.

Figure 4. Partial RDA showing variation among *Geosmithia* species in extracellular enzyme profiles that is explained by ecology. Arrows indicate retained significant ecological predictor variables – ecological affinities (HMDS axis) and ambrosial life history (AMB). Green – pine specialists, brown – generalists, red – ambrosial species, blue – pathogen, orange – auxiliary ambrosia species. Species codes are listed in Table 1. Abbreviation of enzymes: A – alanine aminopeptidase, α G – α -glucosidase, C – cellobiohydrolase, EG – endoglucanase, EX – endoxylanase, G – β -glucosidase, L – leucine aminopeptidase, Lac – laccase, MIP – Mn-independent peroxidases, MnP – Mn-peroxidases, N – N-acetylglucosaminidase, Ox – oxidases, P – phosphomonoesterase, PP – phosphodiesterase, S – arylsulfatase, X – xylosidase.

Figure 6. Partial RDA showing variation among *Geosmithia* species in Biolog™ sporulation profiles that is explained by ecology. Arrows indicate the retained significant ecological predictor variables – ecological affinities (HMDS2) and ambrosial life history (AMB). Coloured circles represent scores for each Biolog substrate. N – nitrogen sources, PS – phosphorus and sulfur sources, NS – nutrient supplementary sources. Generalist are represented by brown color, pine specialists by green, pathogen by blue, ambrosial species by red, auxiliary ambrosial species by orange and hardwood specialists by black. Species codes are listed in Table 1.

Figure 7. Partial RDA showing variation among *Geosmithia* species in lipid (lip) and ergosterol (E) profiles that is explained by ecology. The arrow indicates the retained significant ecological predictor – ecological affinities (HMDS1). Generalist are represented by brown colour, pine specialists by green, pathogen by blue, ambrosial species by red and auxiliary ambrosial species by orange. Values of fatty acids are divided by their saturation. Species codes are listed in Table 1.

DISCUSSION

The aim of our study was to attribute functional trait variation among *Geosmithia* species to ecological and phylogenetic effects. This enabled us to identify traits that are under selective pressure, and perhaps related to the formation of particular symbiotic associations. All the features under study, except ergosterol content and the production of antibiotics, were better explained by the ecology of each *Geosmithia* species than by their phylogenetic relationships. These results suggest that *Geosmithia* phenotypes are highly adaptable and not heavily constrained by phylogenetic history.

Nevertheless, we also found some traits common for all *Geosmithia* species. Their growth was supported on urea, uric acid and partly ammonia on Biolog™ plates which demonstrates their ability to recycle nitrogen, possibly from beetle excretions. They also possess an exo-enzyme cleaving chitin, the main component of the fungal cell wall and of the beetle exoskeleton. As the concentration of nitrogen in beetle galleries markedly affects beetle fitness (Ayres et al., 2000), nitrogen recycling seems to be of great importance. We also detected antibiotic activities in the majority of *Geosmithia* species,

which is in concordance with spectrum of secondary metabolites detected earlier (Stodůlková et al., 2009, 2010). *Geosmithia* fungi are thereby able to actively affect populations of other fungi and/or bacteria in beetle galleries with which they compete for growth substrate, nutrients uptake and beetle transfer. Notable allelopathy observed in ambrosial *G. microcorthyli* suggests that, in cooperation with fungus-cultivating beetles (Batra, 1966; Beaver, 1989), ambrosia fungi themselves could participate in suppression of airborne fungal contaminants occurring in young ambrosial galleries. Even though some fungal mycoparasites act as promising antagonists against the phytopathogenic *G. morbida* (Gazis et al., 2018), this species possesses strong antibiotic capabilities. This might explain its omnipresence in the walnut twig beetle ecosystem. The total ergosterol and lipid content of *Geosmithia* species was not explained by species ecology. We concur with Bentz and Six (2006) that these features are not under selective pressure in the fungus-beetle association.

We found that metabolic capabilities, extracellular production and spectrum of fatty acids are driven by species ecology with only little effect of phylogenetic relationships. Breadth of the niche (phylogenetic diversity of plant hosts) was the best predictor tested, which supports our hypothesis. *Geosmithia* generalists, with the most unrestricted relationships with beetles and host trees are enzymatically versatile which suggest absence of any specific co-evolution with the vector beetles. This is reflected in their ability to grow on a broad spectrum of substrates (Biolog™ analysis), in which they are similar to fungal saprotrophs such as the ubiquitous *Trichoderma/Hypocrea* species (Kubicek et al., 2003). *Geosmithia* generalists tend to cleave hemicellulose by high endoxylanase and xylosidase activities and by extensive growth on arabinose and galactose, the most abundant saccharides in hemicellulose chains (Cosgrove, 1997; Santiago et al., 2013). They massively sporulate within 1 week on a broad spectrum of carbon and nitrogen substrates which reflects their ability to rapidly grow and sporulate in beetle galleries. According to the *r-K* selection theory, species respond to ecological trade-offs by investing either into large amounts of less developed offspring, or into production of fewer but competitively stronger offspring. This theory has been also applied to microorganisms (Andrews and Harris, 1986), where species belonging to *r*-strategists are characterized by quick growth on nutrient rich substrates under optimal conditions and frequent occurrence of disturbances. In contrast, *K*-strategists grow well in stable and nutrient poor environments (they are specialized).

Geosmithia generalists live in association with a broad range of bark beetles species infesting multiple plant families. Consequently, they have to cope with unpredictable substrate switches, which could have a similar effects as disturbances. *Geosmithia* generalists can be characterized by quick growth and early and massive production of small conidia. For these reasons, similarly to Veselská and Kolařík (2015), we consider *Geosmithia* generalist *r*-strategists.

With the exception of increased sporulation on sulphur sources, angiosperm tree specialists (*G. sp. 12*, *G. ulmacea* and *G. sp. 8*) were similar to generalists in their enzymatic potential. By contrast, *Geosmithia* pine specialists expressed strong narrowing of their enzymatic richness by growing only on a small number of Biolog™ substrates. We propose that the limitation of *Geosmithia* specialists to a single plant family Pinaceae and possible long-term co-evolution with their vectors (Kolařík and Jankowiak, 2013) has led to a loss of unnecessary metabolic pathways, a trend documented from a variety of specialists (Kelley and Farrell, 1998). Obligatory mutualisms between phloem-feeding bark beetles and fungi are mostly known from beetles specialized on conifers. This might indicate a tendency of conifer bark beetles to gain necessary nutrients through mycophagy (Six, 2013). *Geosmithia* pine specialists were also unique in their extracellular enzymatic profiles. Their enzyme

suite, including cellobiohydrolase, β -glucosidase, laccase and manganese peroxidase, suggests the capacity to alter the structural components of plant tissues, i.e. cellulose and lignin, suggesting the capacity to fully utilize their plant substrate. They are also characterized by weaker sporulation compared to *Geosmithia* generalists and by a tendency to create large conidia with increased DNA content (Veselská and Kolařík, 2015). Larger conidia accumulate more nutrients than smaller ones, which enhances their resilience to negative climatic factors during germination (Kausrud et al., 2011) and makes them a better diet source for beetles. We suppose that substrate and vector specificity to the pine environment and the long-term co-evolution between these beetles and *Geosmithia* led to a decrease in the total fungal diversity in beetle galleries and thus to lower competition between fungal species for transport on beetle bodies. *Geosmithia* pine specialists thus take advantage of competitive release and resulting niche stabilization. As a consequence, they appear to invest in progeny fitness by conserving nutrient sources and energy by enzymatic streamlining and by the production of large conidia with greater resilience. This classifies them among *K*-strategists.

The entire genus *Geosmithia* displays high enzymatic versatility which is especially manifested in *G. morbida*. Although the genome of *G. morbida* is not enriched in CAZymes compared to nonpathogenic *Geosmithia* species (Schuelke et al., 2017), we have identified that this single species is able to modify, to a certain extent, all structural components of the plant body (lignocellulose and hemicellulose – Table S1). We, therefore, propose that the enzymatic versatility of *G. morbida* is one of its virulence factors. *G. morbida* is a weak pathogen in its native region and became a threat only after it spread outside this area. It is possible that this enzymatic versatility, accompanied by the aggressive feeding behaviour of the twig beetle *Pityophthorus juglandis* and environmental pressure on its host in the expanded geographic range (Tisserat et al., 2009; Hulcr and Dunn, 2011), are reasons for the occasional *Juglans nigra* dieback.

Adaptive change in enzymatic equipment shaped by mutualistic symbiosis has been described in fungal symbionts of ants (De Fine Licht et al., 2010). However, the specific nutritional ecology of ambrosia fungi has rarely been studied. Similarly to Huang et al. (2018), we found that the ambrosial *Geosmithia* are not highly enzymatically specialized. In general, ambrosia fungi are obligatorily dependent on transmission by specific ambrosia beetle species; however, they are often generalists with respect to the number of plant hosts species. In ambrosial *Geosmithia*, our result follows this pattern. They have preserved their enzymatic diversity allowing them to utilize nitrogen and phosphorus sources available in the xylem network and in beetle galleries in the form of excrements, exuviae and dead beetles (Meerts, 2002). Likewise in other ambrosia fungi (Kim et al., 2011; De Fine Licht and Biedermann, 2012), lignocellulose degradation is not linked with the ambrosial strategy in the genus *Geosmithia*. Hypothetically, lignocellulose degradation can cause the loss of protection provided by beetle galleries which possibly precluded the evolution of these enzymatic abilities in ambrosia fungi. Their specialization to vectors seems to reside in their production of large conidia with increased genome size and nutritive value (Veselská and Kolařík, 2015), and probably in the accumulation of oleic fatty acid in the mycelium. Other potentially important variables, such as protein content and essential amino acids content, need to be tested. Ambrosial status was not a significant predictor in our lipid analysis due to the strong similarity of generalist sister species of ambrosial *G. microcorthyli*. Nevertheless, the high production of oleic acid (up to 50%) in these sister species was unique among generalists and may be considered a preadaptation to ambrosial ecology. There are no data about the spectrum of essential fatty acids in bark beetles. However, animals, including weevils

(Earle et al., 1967), cannot synthesize linoleic (18:2) and linolenic fatty acids (18:3) which are therefore considered essential. Kok (1979) detected both of these essential fatty acids in three ambrosial fungi associated with *Xyleborus* beetles, and they constituted up to 30% of all fatty acids. Davis et al. (2019) detected a similar profile of fatty acids in a beetle-associated *Leptographium*. In *Geosmithia*, we found only linoleic fatty acid (mean content of 25%) which was most abundant in pine specialists and least abundant in ambrosial species. Nevertheless, linoleic and linolenic fatty acids are biosynthesized via desaturation of oleic acid, a process also known in fungi (Buček et al., 2014). Production of fatty acids is strongly affected by fungal growth conditions and culture age (Gottlieb et al., 1968; Shimp and Kinsella, 1977; Stahl and Klug, 1996). Our inability to detect linolenic fatty acid in ambrosial *Geosmithia* could indicate their inability to synthesize it or unsuitable conditions for its production during fungal growth. Perhaps, some interaction between fungi and ambrosial beetles is necessary for its synthesis. Moreover, oleic and linoleic fatty acids are known necromones signaling the presence of dead insects. Most arthropods avoid these places (Sun and Zhou, 2013) and thus defend itself against predation and illness (Yao et al., 2009). However, for the ambrosial beetles *Trypodendron lineatum* and *Gnathotrichus* spp., oleic acid does not act as a potent repellent (Nijholt, 1980). Considering the high content of oleic fatty acid in ambrosial *Geosmithia*, we could reason that their ambrosia beetles might repudiate oleic acid as a warning signal. This could give them a competitive advantage because other insects identify their galleries as places which should be avoided.

CONCLUSION

In this study we demonstrate that several adaptive changes have occurred during the evolution of *Geosmithia* fungi living in symbiosis with bark beetles. The first one is the growth restriction to a limited range of substrates, accompanied by enzymatic streamlining in pine specialists. They have lost a broad spectrum of metabolic pathways that are present in *Geosmithia* generalists over the course of their long co-evolution with beetles. Narrowing of the diversity of metabolic pathways was also observed in another *Geosmithia* specialist, the pathogen *G. morbida* which causes necrosis in *Juglans nigra* phloem tissue. The shift from a saprotrophic to a pathogenic life strategy in this species triggered a secondary adaptive change – the alternation of the enzymatic apparatus to modify lignocellulose, the main component of the cell wall of woody plants, which we propose is one of its virulence factors. As the third adaptive change in *Geosmithia* evolution, we suggest an increase in the nutritive value of ambrosia fungi by conidial and DNA content enlargement (Veselská and Kolařík, 2015) and proportional augmentation of oleic fatty acid in mycelial dry weight. However, the role of oleic acid is unclear. We suppose that apart of its nutritive value, oleic acid could hide ambrosia beetle galleries from other insects, including parasites or parasitoids, providing ambrosia beetles with a competitive advantage. Another adaptation or pre-adaption widespread across all ecological groups of *Geosmithia* is the ability to ecologically suppress a diversity of microbes (including entomopathogens) and recycle nitrogen via effective utilization of urea and chitin.

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SUPPLEMENTARY INFORMATION

Figure S1. Mantel's test revealed no significant correlation between ecological and phylogenetic distance matrices.

Table S1. Extracellular enzymatic activities of *Geosmithia*.

Ecology	<i>Geosmithia</i> strains	Code	Activity of extracellular enzymes mU/g															
			Cellulose degradation			Hemicellulose degradation		Polysaccharides degradation		N Acquisition		P Acquisition		S acquisition	Lignin transformation			
			G	C	EG	X	EX	aG	N	A	L	P	PP	S	Ox	MIP	MnP	Lac
Generalists	CCF4529	G1	2.2 ± 0.2	11.8 ± 1.6	0.5 ± 0.5	11.9 ± 0.8	0.2 ± 0.2	1.0 ± 0.1	5.8 ± 0.5	0.0	0.0	4.6 ± 1.1	0.1 ± 0.0	8.4 ± 1.5	0.9 ± 0.1	0.0	0.8 ± 0.7	0.1 ± 0.1
	CCF3342	Gput	2.4 ± 0.4	16.5 ± 0.5	1.2 ± 0.9	8.8 ± 0.1	8.4 ± 0.9	0.3 ± 0.0	7.1 ± 0.5	0.0	0.0	5.0 ± 0.5	0.1 ± 0.0	1.5 ± 0.7	1.7 ± 0.01	0.2 ± 0.1	0.2 ± 0.2	0.0
	CCF3354	Gfla	5.3 ± 0.6	10.6 ± 0.5	11.3 ± 2.1	5.6 ± 0.3	6.5 ± 2.2	0.3 ± 0.1	7.0 ± 0.3	0.0	0.0	13.5 ± 0.4	0.1 ± 0.0	2.3 ± 1.4	1.5 ± 0.0	0.0	0.2 ± 0.2	0.6 ± 0.1
	CCF4528	G8	6.4 ± 0.6	9.4 ± 0.7	0.0	12.2 ± 0.9	1.5 ± 0.1	0.2 ± 0.0	7.7 ± 0.4	0.0	0.0	13.4 ± 0.5	0.1 ± 0.0	9.8 ± 0.6	2.2 ± 0.6	0.0	0.6 ± 0.3	0.4 ± 0.3
	CCF4207	G8	2.2 ± 0.3	9.2 ± 0.9	0.3 ± 0.3	13.1 ± 0.6	2.0 ± 0.9	0.4 ± 0.0	6.1 ± 0.2	0.0	0.0	9.7 ± 0.2	0.1 ± 0.0	13.1 ± 0.5	2.5 ± 0.4	0.0	0.3 ± 0.1	0.4 ± 0.1
	CCF3554	Glan	3.3 ± 0.6	6.3 ± 1.2	0.2 ± 0.2	10.4 ± 0.7	0.6 ± 0.3	0.8 ± 0.1	6.9 ± 0.2	0.0	0.0	15.3 ± 0.7	0.1 ± 0.0	0.6 ± 0.1	1.8 ± 0.2	0.0	0.2 ± 0.1	0.0
	CCF4527	G20	1.1 ± 0.3	10.1 ± 0.6	0.9 ± 0.3	14.8 ± 0.6	11.0 ± 1.6	1.1 ± 0.1	1.2 ± 0.0	0.0	0.1 ± 0.0	15.0 ± 0.5	0.3 ± 0.0	3.7 ± 0.9	0.9 ± 0.2	0.0	1.5 ± 2.4	0.0
	CCF4530	G21	0.4 ± 0.2	8.4 ± 1.2	6.0 ± 3.0	14.1 ± 1.2	5.2 ± 0.2	0.7 ± 0.3	6.9 ± 0.3	0.0	0.0	13.8 ± 0.2	0.2 ± 0.0	4.1 ± 0.5	0.9 ± 0.2	0.1 ± 0.1	0.0	0.1 ± 0.0
	CCF3645	G22	0.8 ± 0.3	11.8 ± 0.4	2.3 ± 0.4	13.5 ± 0.8	7.4 ± 1.7	0.7 ± 0.1	6.7 ± 0.5	0.0	0.0	14.4 ± 0.4	0.0	3.2 ± 1.9	3.6 ± 0.4	0.0	0.0	4.1 ± 0.5
	CCF4200	G36	4.3 ± 0.4	11.3 ± 0.4	2.9 ± 1.4	11.7 ± 0.4	2.8 ± 1.7	0.3 ± 0.0	7.4 ± 0.2	0.0	0.0	9.0 ± 1.6	0.3 ± 0.0	9.5 ± 0.4	1.4 ± 0.0	0.0	0.3	0.0
Specialists to Pinaceae	CCF3703	G9	12.2 ± 0.3	12.7 ± 0.2	1.6 ± 0.0	2.4 ± 0.1	2.4 ± 0.3	0.4 ± 0.0	7.0 ± 0.1	0.0	0.5 ± 0.2	11.1 ± 0.8	1.8 ± 0.0	2.1 ± 0.1	4.7 ± 1.8	0.0	0.5 ± 0.1	4.8 ± 0.1
	CCF4201	G16	11.6 ± 0.3	10.9 ± 1.5	0.5 ± 0.4	9.2 ± 0.4	0.7 ± 0.0	0.3 ± 0.1	6.5 ± 0.6	0.0	0.1 ± 0.0	13.3 ± 0.1	0.3 ± 0.1	4.8 ± 1.0	5.3 ± 0.6	0.0	0.0	10.1 ± 3.1
	CCF4525	G24	10.0 ± 2.3	2.8 ± 0.1	0.0	1.8 ± 0.1	0.5 ± 0.3	0.0	3.7 ± 0.2	0.0	0.7 ± 0.4	2.6 ± 0.1	0.7 ± 0.1	6.3 ± 0.8	1.9 ± 0.3	0.0	0.4 ± 0.3	0.5 ± 0.1

	CCF4205	G25	7.4 ± 2.4	2.5 ± 1.9	0.0	1.0 ± 0.5	0.2 ± 0.2	0.1 ± 0.0	3.9 ± 1.0	0.0	0.0	4.1 ± 1.9	0.3 ± 0.1	1.8 ± 0.7	2.1 ± 0.7	0.0	0.4 ± 0.2	0.3 ± 0.3
	CCF4223	G26	3.2 ± 0.7	12.6 ± 0.7	0.6 ± 0.4	9.5 ± 1.7	0.9 ± 0.5	0.1 ± 0.1	6.2 ± 0.3	0.0	0.0	14.1 ± 0.7	2.4 ± 0.2	2.8 ± 0.8	11.2 ± 0.9	0.0	1.9 ± 0.6	14.4 ± 1.2
	CCF4206	G27	7.3 ± 0.1	16.2 ± 0.2	0.9 ± 0.9	7.1 ± 0.3	2.0 ± 0.2	0.2 ± 0.1	7.0 ± 0.1	0.0	0.1 ± 0.1	13.3 ± 0.1	2.8 ± 0.4	3.7 ± 1.9	1.9 ± 0.1	0.0	0.4 ± 0.9	0.0
	CCF4526	G31	5.8 ± 0.8	14.0 ± 1.3	0.6 ± 0.5	11.2 ± 2.4	0.4 ± 0.2	0.0 ± 0.0	6.7 ± 0.3	0.0	0.0	13.1 ± 0.7	0.8 ± 0.1	3.3 ± 0.5	11.2 ± 4.0	0.0	0.0	10.9 ± 1.0
Ambrosial species	CCF4292	Gcne	5.7 ± 0.7	14.4 ± 0.3	0.3 ± 0.3	6.5 ± 0.3	0.2 ± 0.1	0.2 ± 0.0	7.1 ± 0.2	0.0	0.0	10.3 ± 0.4	0.1 ± 0.0	8.9 ± 0.9	1.7 ± 0.0	0.1 ± 0.3	0.0	0.0
	CCF3861	Gmic	5.3 ± 0.4	16.4 ± 0.5	0.2 ± 0.2	9.8 ± 0.4	1.1 ± 0.2	0.8 ± 0.1	7.0 ± 0.2	0.0	0.0	12.4 ± 0.6	0.3 ± 0.0	12.1 ± 0.3	16.0 ± 1.0	0.0	1.7 ± 0.4	24.3 ± 1.4
	CCF3754	Geup	8.4 ± 0.9	13.4 ± 0.9	0.0	3.0 ± 0.5	16.7 ± 1.5	0.1 ± 0.0	3.2 ± 1.1	0.0	0.0	13.6 ± 0.3	0.1 ± 0.0	3.7 ± 0.7	1.6 ± 0.6	0.0	0.2 ± 0.2	0.2 ± 0.2
Plant pathogen	CCF4576	Gmor	10.3 ± 0.3	8.2 ± 0.5	0.3 ± 0.1	3.6 ± 0.3	11.0 ± 1.5	0.3 ± 0.0	6.6 ± 0.2	0.0	1.0 ± 0.2	11.9 ± 0.7	0.9 ± 0.0	2.5 ± 0.2	2.5 ± 0.2	0.0	0.0	1.4 ± 0.3
	CCF3879	Gmor	9.1 ± 0.6	9.2 ± 0.4	0.4 ± 0.2	4.1 ± 0.2	12.2 ± 1.7	0.4 ± 0.0	6.9 ± 0.3	0.0	0.0	8.8 ± 2.6	0.1 ± 0.0	1.8 ± 0.1	3.2 ± 0.3	0.0	0.7 ± 0.1	4.1 ± 0.1
	1259	Gmor	11.7 ± 0.2	7.8 ± 1.7	3.5 ± 1.6	2.4 ± 0.2	17.4 ± 2.3	0.4 ± 0.0	6.5 ± 0.3	0.0	0.0	14.4 ± 0.2	0.1 ± 0.0	3.8 ± 1.6	2.5 ± 0.3	0.2 ± 0.2	0.5 ± 0.1	3.4 ± 0.7
Auxiliary ambrosial	CCF4524	Gruf	11.4 ± 0.2	17.4 ± 0.2	0.7 ± 0.5	0.9 ± 0.0	0.4 ± 0.2	1.1 ± 0.1	7.1 ± 0.2	0.1 ± 0.1	0.0	7.9 ± 0.9	0.1 ± 0.0	4.5 ± 0.3	1.7 ± 0.1	0.0	0.3 ± 0.3	0.0

Abbreviation of enzymes and respective fluorogenic 4-methylumbelliferone (MUF) and 7-amido-4-methylcoumarin (AMC) substrates in parenthesis, if this method was used. For detailed method see Material and Method section : A – alanine aminopeptidase (L-alanine-AMC), αG – α- glucosidase (MUF-α-D-glucopyranoside), C – cellobiohydrolase (MUF-β-D-cellobioside), EG – endoglucanase, EX – endoxylanasa, G – β-glucosidase (MUF-β-D-glucopyranoside), L – leucine aminopeptidase L-leucine-AMC, Lac – laccase, MIP – Mn-independent peroxidases, MnP – Mn-peroxidases, N – N-acetylglucosaminidase (MUF-N-acetyl-β-D-glucosaminide), Ox – oxidases, P – phosphomonoesterase (MUF-phosphate), PP – phosphodiesterase (bis-(MUF) phosphate), S – arylsulphatase (MUF-sulfate potassium salt), X – xylosidase (MUF-β-D-xylopyranoside).

Table S2. Ergosterol content and spectrum of fatty acid in *Geosmithia*.

Strains	Code	E	Lip	14:0	15:0	16:1w9	16:1w7	16:0	17:1	17:0	18:2w6.9	18:1w9	18:1w7
CCF4529	G1	0.3 ± 0.0	16.2 ± 10.5	0.2 ± 0.0	0.2 ± 0.0	0.1 ± 0.0	1.2 ± 0.1	19.7 ± 1.8	0.1 ± 0.0	0.2 ± 0.0	29.1 ± 3.0	39.0 ± 6.6	0.3 ± 0.1
CCF3342	G6	0.5 ± 0.0	10.0 ± 0.6	0.3 ± 0.0	0.4 ± 0.1	0.1 ± 0.0	0.7 ± 0.1	20.2 ± 0.1	0.1 ± 0.0	0.2 ± 0.0	27.5 ± 0.9	34.7 ± 0.4	0.0
CCF3354	Gfla	0.4 ± 0.0	10.4 ± 1.1	0.1 ± 0.1	0.1 ± 0.0	0.4 ± 0.1	0.4 ± 0.2	11.1 ± 5.2	0.1 ± 0.0	0.1 ± 0.0	32.8 ± 3.4	44.1 ± 4.5	0.2 ± 0.0
CCF4528	G8	0.5 ± 0.0	9.6 ± 0.4	0.1 ± 0.0	0.2 ± 0.0	0.3 ± 0.0	1.6 ± 0.1	16.0 ± 0.1	0.3 ± 0.0	0.2 ± 0.0	8.1 ± 0.9	49.3 ± 0.9	0.7 ± 0.0
CCF4207	G8	0.4 ± 0.0	7.9 ± 0.5	0.2 ± 0.0	0.2 ± 0.1	0.2 ± 0.1	0.7 ± 0.1	25.4 ± 0.1	0.2 ± 0.1	0.1 ± 0.1	14.8 ± 4.1	44.6 ± 7.0	0.2 ± 0.0
CCF3703	G9	0.4 ± 0.0	14.6 ± 2.9	0.3 ± 0.0	0.1 ± 0.0	0.1 ± 0.0	0.9 ± 0.0	21.8 ± 0.6	0.1 ± 0.0	0.1 ± 0.0	28.3 ± 0.7	31.1 ± 1.1	0.5 ± 0.0
CCF3554	Glan	0.7 ± 0.1	12.5 ± 0.3	0.2 ± 0.0	0.6 ± 0.0	0.1 ± 0.0	2.0 ± 0.2	24.7 ± 0.8	0.2 ± 0.0	0.2 ± 0.0	26.5 ± 1.0	33.6 ± 0.8	0.3 ± 0.2
CCF4201	G16	0.2 ± 0.0	12.1 ± 0.6	0.1 ± 0.0	0.1 ± 0.0	0.0	0.2 ± 0.0	13.1 ± 0.2	0.0	0.1 ± 0.0	42.7 ± 0.5	30.0 ± 0.2	0.1 ± 0.0
CCF4527	G20	0.5 ± 0.0	11.1 ± 0.6	0.3 ± 0.0	0.1 ± 0.0	0.1 ± 0.0	0.7 ± 0.1	28.1 ± 0.3	0.0	0.1 ± 0.0	16.3 ± 0.2	32.5 ± 0.9	0.1 ± 0.1
CCF4530	G21	0.3 ± 0.0	9.7 ± 0.6	0.1 ± 0.0	0.1 ± 0.0	0.2 ± 0.0	0.2 ± 0.0	21.8 ± 0.8	0.1 ± 0.0	0.2 ± 0.0	25.3 ± 0.3	29.8 ± 0.3	0.0
CCF3645	G22	0.5 ± 0.0	10.2 ± 0.5	0.4 ± 0.0	0.2 ± 0.0	0.1 ± 0.0	0.7 ± 0.0	28.7 ± 0.2	0.1 ± 0.0	0.1 ± 0.0	22.6 ± 1.0	31.9 ± 1.4	0.1 ± 0.0
CCF4525	G24	0.5 ± 0.0	6.7 ± 2.4	0.3 ± 0.1	0.4 ± 0.2	0.1 ± 0.0	6.6 ± 0.7	22.3 ± 3.3	1.1 ± 0.4	0.1 ± 0.1	26.6 ± 4.9	34.0 ± 4.0	2.2 ± 0.3
CCF4205	G25	0.3 ± 0.1	6.9 ± 4.5	0.2 ± 0.1	0.5 ± 0.2	0.1 ± 0.1	0.4 ± 0.0	17.8 ± 4.3	0.5 ± 0.2	0.9 ± 0.2	24.4 ± 12.1	38.5 ± 3.1	0.4 ± 0.1
CCF4223	G26	0.3 ± 0.0	5.0 ± 4.0	0.1 ± 0.0	0.3 ± 0.1	0.2 ± 0.1	0.4 ± 0.1	22.7 ± 5.4	0.1 ± 0.1	0.2 ± 0.0	35.7 ± 7.0	26.5 ± 6.5	0.3 ± 0.0
CCF4206	G27	0.4 ± 0.1	8.8 ± 1.6	0.2 ± 0.0	0.0	0.1 ± 0.0	1.1 ± 0.1	22.0 ± 0.2	0.1 ± 0.0	0.0	29.3 ± 0.8	30.7 ± 1.0	0.7 ± 0.0
CCF4526	G31	0.2 ± 0.0	8.7 ± 2.1	0.1 ± 0.0	0.3 ± 0.1	0.1 ± 0.1	0.2 ± 0.1	17.3 ± 1.8	0.1 ± 0.1	0.4 ± 0.1	45.8 ± 5.6	21.5 ± 6.8	0.1 ± 0.1
CCF3861	Gmic	0.5 ± 0.0	13.0 ± 7.3	0.3 ± 0.0	0.3 ± 0.0	0.1 ± 0.0	0.7 ± 0.1	26.5 ± 0.9	0.2 ± 0.1	0.1 ± 0.0	9.9 ± 5.4	44.3 ± 6.1	0.1 ± 0.0
CCF3754	Geup	0.3 ± 0.0	9.8 ± 2.3	0.3 ± 0.0	0.2 ± 0.1	0.1 ± 0.0	0.7 ± 0.2	24.7 ± 0.8	0.2 ± 0.1	0.2 ± 0.1	11.0 ± 15.0	46.4 ± 12.7	0.4 ± 0.2
CCF3879	Gmor	0.5 ± 0.1	8.7 ± 1.9	0.2 ± 0.0	0.1 ± 0.1	0.1 ± 0.0	0.6 ± 0.1	20.5 ± 2.3	0.2 ± 0.1	0.3 ± 0.2	34.2 ± 10.7	28.8 ± 2.2	0.2 ± 0.1
1259	Gmor	0.4 ± 0.1	10.6 ± 1.4	0.2 ± 0.0	0.4 ± 0.0	0.1 ± 0.0	0.6 ± 0.0	20.5 ± 1.0	0.4 ± 0.0	0.6 ± 0.0	27.8 ± 1.7	32.0 ± 0.6	0.4 ± 0.0
CCF4576	Gmor	0.5 ± 0.1	12.3 ± 1.6	0.2 ± 0.0	0.4 ± 0.0	0.1 ± 0.0	0.5 ± 0.0	21.5 ± 0.2	0.4 ± 0.0	0.7 ± 0.0	34.3 ± 0.8	26.4 ± 0.5	0.3 ± 0.0
CCF4524	Gruf	0.4 ± 0.0	8.3 ± 7.7	0.3 ± 0.1	0.2 ± 0.1	0.1 ± 0.0	0.8 ± 0.1	18.9 ± 0.3	0.1 ± 0.1	0.3 ± 0.1	31.2 ± 5.4	37.3 ± 5.9	0.2 ± 0.2
CCF4200	G36	0.6 ± 0.0	7.1 ± 0.8	0.2 ± 0.0	0.2 ± 0.0	0.2 ± 0.0	0.7 ± 0.1	24.5 ± 0.2	0.3 ± 0.1	0.2 ± 0.0	15.5 ± 1.7	44.1 ± 6.4	0.2 ± 0.1
CCF4292	Gcne	0.3 ± 0.0	7.5 ± 1.6	0.2 ± 0.1	0.1 ± 0.0	0.1 ± 0.0	0.5 ± 0.1	22.4 ± 2.2	0.2 ± 0.1	0.2 ± 0.0	16.6 ± 11.7	44.1 ± 10.5	0.3 ± 0.3

Table S2. Continue

Strains	Code	18:0	20:5	20:5	20:5w3.6. 9.12.15	20:3	20:4	20:2w6.9	20:1w9 - 20:1w7	20:0	21:1	22:0	23:0	24:0
CCF4529	G1	5.2 ± 0.5	0.1 ± 0.1	0.1 ± 0.0	0.1 ± 0.0	0.6 ± 0.2	1.4 ± 2.2	0.6 ± 0.1	0.4 ± 0.4	0.3 ± 0.0	0.1 ± 0.0	0.3 ± 0.1	0.0	0.8 ± 0.1
CCF3342	G6	6.7 ± 0.6	0.0	0.1 ± 0.0	0.1 ± 0.0	0.3 ± 0.2	6.7 ± 0.4	0.5 ± 0.0	0.0	0.3 ± 0.0	0.1 ± 0.1	0.2 ± 0.0	0.1 ± 0.0	0.7 ± 0.0
CCF3354	Gfla	4.8 ± 0.3	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.1 ± 0.2	1.8 ± 3.1	1.2 ± 0.1	0.6 ± 0.5	0.4 ± 0.0	0.1 ± 0.0	0.5 ± 0.1	0.0	1.0 ± 0.1
CCF4528	G8	2.9 ± 0.1	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.6 ± 0.1	17.8 ± 1.9	1.0 ± 0.0	0.0	0.1 ± 0.0	0.1 ± 0.0	0.1 ± 0.0	0.1 ± 0.0	0.5 ± 0.0
CCF4207	G8	6.9 ± 2.1	0.0	0.1 ± 0.0	0.0	0.7 ± 0.3	3.3 ± 5.7	0.4 ± 0.2	0.3 ± 0.2	0.4 ± 0.1	0.1 ± 0.1	0.3 ± 0.0	0.0	0.7 ± 0.2
CCF3703	G9	6.4 ± 0.2	0.0	0.1 ± 0.0	0.0	0.7 ± 0.1	6.9 ± 0.8	0.5 ± 0.0	0.0	0.3 ± 0.0	0.2 ± 0.0	0.3 ± 0.0	0.0	1.4 ± 0.1
CCF3554	Glan	3.0 ± 0.1	0.0	0.1 ± 0.1	0.1 ± 0.0	0.3 ± 0.1	6.3 ± 1.5	0.4 ± 0.0	0.0	0.2 ± 0.0	0.1 ± 0.0	0.2 ± 0.0	0.1 ± 0.0	0.7 ± 0.0
CCF4201	G16	6.4 ± 0.0	0.0	0.1 ± 0.0	0.1 ± 0.0	0.6 ± 0.0	5.0 ± 0.2	0.9 ± 0.0	0.0	0.0	0.1 ± 0.0	0.1 ± 0.0	0.0	0.2 ± 0.0
CCF4527	G20	8.2 ± 0.3	0.0	0.1 ± 0.0	0.1 ± 0.0	0.5 ± 0.1	11.3 ± 0.4	0.1 ± 0.1	0.2 ± 0.1	0.3 ± 0.0	0.1 ± 0.0	0.2 ± 0.0	0.0	0.5 ± 0.1
CCF4530	G21	10.9 ± 0.1	0.0	0.1 ± 0.0	0.1 ± 0.0	0.5 ± 0.1	8.9 ± 0.9	0.6 ± 0.1	0.0	0.3 ± 0.0	0.2 ± 0.1	0.2 ± 0.0	0.0	0.4 ± 0.1
CCF3645	G22	7.9 ± 0.5	0.0	0.1 ± 0.0	0.0	0.2 ± 0.0	5.4 ± 0.3	0.2 ± 0.0	0.1 ± 0.1	0.4 ± 0.0	0.1 ± 0.0	0.3 ± 0.0	0.0	0.7 ± 0.0
CCF4525	G24	2.4 ± 0.7	0.2 ± 0.2	0.1 ± 0.0	0.1 ± 0.1	0.4 ± 0.1	1.9 ± 0.0	0.3 ± 0.1	0.1 ± 0.0	0.0	0.2 ± 0.1	0.0	0.0	0.6 ± 0.4
CCF4205	G25	9.7 ± 4.3	0.3 ± 0.2	0.2 ± 0.1	0.2 ± 0.2	1.3 ± 0.8	1.5 ± 2.3	1.0 ± 0.4	1.0 ± 0.9	0.4 ± 0.1	0.3 ± 0.1	0.1 ± 0.0	0.0	0.3 ± 0.1
CCF4223	G26	6.5 ± 0.5	0.3 ± 0.2	0.1 ± 0.0	0.2 ± 0.1	0.6 ± 0.7	3.7 ± 6.0	0.3 ± 0.1	0.4 ± 0.3	0.1 ± 0.1	0.7 ± 0.2	0.1 ± 0.1	0.0	0.4 ± 0.1
CCF4206	G27	4.9 ± 0.3	0.0	0.1 ± 0.0	0.1 ± 0.0	0.4 ± 0.0	9.5 ± 0.2	0.2 ± 0.0	0.1 ± 0.1	0.0	0.1 ± 0.0	0.1 ± 0.0	0.0	0.2 ± 0.0
CCF4526	G31	7.6 ± 0.8	0.1 ± 0.1	0.1 ± 0.1	0.1 ± 0.0	0.7 ± 0.4	3.0 ± 2.7	1.2 ± 0.2	0.3 ± 0.6	0.1 ± 0.1	0.2 ± 0.1	0.1 ± 0.1	0.0	0.5 ± 0.1
CCF3861	Gmic	11.7 ± 2.7	0.1 ± 0.1	0.1 ± 0.0	0.1 ± 0.0	0.7 ± 0.2	2.9 ± 4.8	0.1 ± 0.1	0.2 ± 0.2	0.6 ± 0.1	0.1 ± 0.1	0.4 ± 0.0	0.1 ± 0.0	0.4 ± 0.1
CCF3754	Geup	10.8 ± 1.9	0.1 ± 0.1	0.1 ± 0.1	0.1 ± 0.1	1.3 ± 0.7	1.1 ± 1.8	0.4 ± 0.2	0.1 ± 0.0	0.7 ± 0.0	0.1 ± 0.1	0.4 ± 0.0	0.1 ± 0.0	0.5 ± 0.1
CCF3879	Gmor	6.9 ± 0.2	0.2 ± 0.1	0.0	0.1 ± 0.1	0.4 ± 0.7	4.1 ± 6.9	0.2 ± 0.0	0.4 ± 0.2	0.2 ± 0.0	0.3 ± 0.2	0.2 ± 0.1	0.0	1.6 ± 0.6
1259	Gmor	5.5 ± 0.4	0.1 ± 0.0	0.1 ± 0.0	0.1 ± 0.0	1.4 ± 0.1	7.8 ± 1.1	0.5 ± 0.1	0.0	0.3 ± 0.0	0.2 ± 0.0	0.2 ± 0.0	0.0	0.9 ± 0.1
CCF4576	Gmor	5.3 ± 0.1	0.1 ± 0.0	0.1 ± 0.0	0.1 ± 0.0	1.4 ± 0.1	5.9 ± 0.6	0.4 ± 0.0	0.0	0.0	0.2 ± 0.1	0.2 ± 0.0	0.0	1.4 ± 0.0
CCF4524	Gruf	8.4 ± 0.2	0.1 ± 0.1	0.0	0.1 ± 0.0	0.1 ± 0.1	0.6 ± 0.8	0.1 ± 0.1	0.1 ± 0.0	0.3 ± 0.0	0.3 ± 0.3	0.2 ± 0.1	0.1 ± 0.1	0.4 ± 0.2
CCF4200	G36	7.5 ± 0.2	0.0	0.1 ± 0.0	0.1 ± 0.0	0.8 ± 0.2	3.4 ± 5.8	0.3 ± 0.0	0.3 ± 0.1	0.3 ± 0.0	0.2 ± 0.0	0.2 ± 0.0	0.1 ± 0.0	0.9 ± 0.2
CCF4292	Gcne	10.5 ± 0.2	0.2 ± 0.2	0.1 ± 0.0	0.2 ± 0.1	1.0 ± 0.4	1.4 ± 2.0	0.4 ± 0.0	0.2 ± 0.2	0.5 ± 0.0	0.1 ± 0.1	0.3 ± 0.0	0.1 ± 0.0	0.4 ± 0.2

E – total ergosterol content in fungal dry weight (ppm), Lip – total fatty acid content in fungal dry weight (%).

Table S3. Inhibition zones (cm) from Kirby-Bauer disk diffusion susceptibility test used for detection of antibiotic activities against model organisms.

Ecology	<i>Geosmithia</i> strains	Species code	Model organisms					
			<i>Saccharomyces cerevisiae</i>	<i>Escherichia coli</i>	<i>Kocuria rhizophila</i>	<i>Graphium fimbriisporum</i>	<i>Beauveria bassiana</i>	<i>Penicillium decumbens</i>
Specialists to Pinaceae	CCF3703	G9	1.0	0.9	1.2	1.1	0.7	0.7
	CCF4525	G24	0	0.0	0.9	0.8	0.8	0.7
	CCF4205	G25	0.8	0	1	0	0.9	0
	CCF4223	G26	0	0	0	0	0	0
	CCF4206	G27	0	0	0.8	0	0	0
	CCF4526	G31	0	0	0	0	0.7	0
Generalists	CCF3342	Gput	0	0	0	0	0	0
	CCF3354	Glan	0	0	0	0	0	0
	CCF4528	G8	0	0	0	0	0	0
	CCF4207	G8	0	0	0.8	0	0.7	0.7
	CCF4601	Gulm	0	0	0	0	0	0
	CCF4527	G20	0	0	0.8	0	0	0
	CCF3645	G22	0	0	0	0	0	0
	CCF4200	G36	0	0	0	0	0	0
Ambrosial species	CCF4292	Gcne	0	0	0	0	0	0
	CCF3861	Gmic	0.8	0	1.6	0.8	0.7	0.7
	CCF3754	Geup	0	0	0	0	0	0
Plant pathogen	CCF3879	Gmor	0	0.8	0.8	0.7	0.7	0.7
	1259	Gmor	0.9	0	1.0	1.1	0.8	0.9
Auxiliary ambrosial	CCF4524	Gruf	0.9	0	0	0.8	0.7	0.7

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Comparative eco-physiology revealed extensive enzymatic curtailment, lipases production and strong conidial resilience of the bat pathogenic fungus *Pseudogymnoascus destructans*

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ABSTRACT

The genus *Pseudogymnoascus* encompasses soil psychrophilic fungi living also in caves. Some are opportunistic pathogens; nevertheless, they do not cause outbreaks. *Pseudogymnoascus destructans* is the causative agent of the white-nose syndrome, which is decimating cave-hibernating bats. We used comparative eco-physiology to contrast the enzymatic potential and conidial resilience of *P. destructans* with that of phylogenetically diverse cave fungi, including *Pseudogymnoascus* spp., dermatophytes and outdoor saprotrophs. Enzymatic potential was assessed by Biolog MicroArray and by growth on labelled substrates and conidial viability was detected by flow cytometry.

Pseudogymnoascus destructans was specific by extensive losses of metabolic variability and by ability of lipid degradation. We suppose that lipases are important enzymes allowing fungal hyphae to digest and invade the skin. *Pseudogymnoascus destructans* prefers nitrogenous substrates occurring in bat skin and lipids. Additionally, *P. destructans* alkalizes growth medium, which points to another possible virulence mechanism. Temperature above 30 °C substantially decreases conidial viability of cave fungi including *P. destructans*. Nevertheless, survival of *P. destructans* conidia prolongs by the temperature regime simulating beginning of the flight season, what suggests that conidia could persist on the body surface of bats and contribute to disease spreading during bats active season.

INTRODUCTION

Pseudogymnoascus destructans (Pseudeurotiaceae, Ascomycota)¹ is a fungus that infects the skin of hibernating bats and causes the disease called the white-nose syndrome (WNS)^{2–4}. This fungus is native to Eurasian bat hibernacula, where it behaves as a not too virulent cutaneous pathogen. It

causes sporadic mortality and health deterioration, but not apparent changes in bat populations^{5,6}. This fact, together with the high genetic diversity of the European *P. destructans* populations, suggests its long co-evolution with its hosts⁶⁻¹⁰. A single *P. destructans* clone was introduced from Europe or Asia to the United States, where it encountered naïve hosts and has been causing massive mortality observed since 2006^{11,12}. Despite of its clonal growth *P. destructans* manifests some phenotypical divergence^{13,14}.

Pseudogymnoascus destructans infects naked parts of the bat skin, such as the muzzle, ears and flight membranes, where it forms cup-like epidermal erosions and ulcerations. Unlike dermatophytes¹⁵, *P. destructans* invades not only the epidermis, but grows into deeper parts of the skin, the dermis^{2,15-17}. The ability to make a lesion is the same between *P. destructans* strains in the United States and Europe¹⁸. The lethal progress described as WNS is thus a result of complex interactions of variables, which are under debate¹⁹⁻²². Despite availability of extensive studies on *P. destructans* biology, the decided answer about its virulence and biology still missing and further research is desired to get closer. *P. destructans* shares some virulence factors with dermatophytes^{23,24}, such as subtilisin-like proteases degrading collagen²⁵, but lacks others, for example keratinase²⁶. Comparative studies^{16,24} have identified siderophore secretion as virulence factor^{19,27}, which is similar to fungi forming deeper mycotic infections²⁸, where siderophores play an important role in the pathogenesis. *Pseudogymnoascus destructans*, in contrast to non-virulent *Pseudogymnoascus* species, is also unique in its overproduction of riboflavin, the role of which in virulence needs to be assessed further¹⁹. The WNS transcriptome revealed over fifty genes that are upregulated during the infection process on the side of the fungus²⁹⁻³¹. They include numerous secreted proteases (including destructins and a homolog of the *Aspergillus fumigatus* major allergen Asp2), heat shock proteins, ureases, metal-binding siderophores, enzymes responsible for fatty acid utilization and protein kinases.

WNS is spread by bat-to-bat transmission during hibernation³² and by infections from environmental pool of the cave sediments^{33,34}. Non-pathogenic *Pseudogymnoascus* species are common soil fungi also living outside of hibernacula¹. To the contrary, alternative habitats for *P. destructans* are so far unknown. It is unclear which physiological constraints restrict this fungus to the cold and humid habitats of caves. *P. destructans* is a psychrophilic fungus growing at temperatures between 3 and 19 °C, with an optimal range of 12–15 °C. Its growth stops at 10 °C and above 20 °C³⁵⁻³⁷. The optimal relative humidity for the growth of *P. destructans* is around 80%, which is the moisture level found in bats' hibernacula and their body surface during hibernation¹⁵. Its psychrophilic nature enables bats to clear any visible infection during summer, when ambient temperatures exceed the upper limit for *P. destructans* growth. Nevertheless, we have only sparse information about its conidial resilience^{13,38,39}. It therefore remains unknown whether *P. destructans* conidia can disseminate on the body surface of bats during the active flight season to new hibernacula and participate in the spreading of the disease.

The goal of our study was to compare phenotype of *P. destructans* with that of (1) other *Pseudogymnoascus* species to find traits specific to *P. destructans*. We propose that these traits are potentially under selective pressure and are possible virulence factors, (2) cave fungi to identify common traits related to growth in cave habitat and thus not directly linked with *P. destructans* pathogenesis and (3) dermatophytes which are pathogens and thus shared traits could be important in *P. destructans* virulence. Our study combines knowledge of prior studies on virulence factors of *P.*

destructans and compares phenotype of *P. destructans* with phenotype of ecologically related species, which enables to estimate selective pressure leading to pathogenicity of *P. destructans*.

RESULTS

Biolog analysis

Analyzed ecological groups formed well-defined clusters on PCA analysis (Fig. 1), only a cave inhabiting fungus *Myotisia cremea* (Onygenales), which lives on the bats guano, clustered with dermatophytes. Based on one-way NPMANOVA analysis, *P. destructans* significantly differed in growth potential from dermatophytes on each of the Biolog MicroPlates tested ($p < 0.05$). *Pseudogymnoascus destructans* was also distinct from cave fungi ($p < 0.05$) except growth on sulfur and phosphorus sources ($p = 0.75$). The main differences between these groups resided in the limitation of *P. destructans* to only a few nitrogen substrates and its increased growth potential on nutrient supplements (Supplementary Dataset online). *Pseudogymnoascus destructans* was significantly distinct from *Pseudogymnoascus* species on carbon and nutrient supplements ($p < 0.05$). *Pseudogymnoascus* species were similar to cave fungi on all microplates ($p > 0.7$). When all microplates were integrated into one analysis (Fig. 1), *P. destructans* was significantly separated from cave fungi, *Pseudogymnoascus* spp. and dermatophytes ($p < 0.02$), and dermatophytes differed from cave fungi ($p = 0.01$). *Pseudogymnoascus* spp. were significantly different from *P. destructans* ($p < 0.02$) and were similar to cave fungi ($p = 1$).

Pseudogymnoascus destructans was remarkable for its relatively low SA and SR but high H values on microplates containing carbon and nitrogen sources (Fig. 2). This means that even if *P. destructans* growth is supported by only a few carbon and nitrogen sources, it also preserves a weak growth capability on most of them. The most growth-supporting carbon and nitrogen substrates for *P. destructans* were the lipid Tween 80, glycogen, and urea, allantoin, uric acid and ammonia (Table 1, Supplementary Table S1 online). Cave fungi and dermatophytes also favoured these nitrogen substrates. *P. destructans* grew well on nutrient supplements, especially on amino acids. All groups had similar growth potential on phosphorus and sulphur substrates. Cave fungi displayed versatility in carbon utilization (highest value of SA, SR and H). Dermatophytes were specific in their preference for nitrogenous carbon sources (mostly amino acids and N-acetyl-D-glucosamine).

Semi-quantitative extracellular enzymes activities

We compared the production of extracellular enzymes cleaving connective tissue between *P. destructans* and other *Pseudogymnoascus* species. We detected the production of lipases, elastases and collagenases. *Pseudogymnoascus destructans* was specific in the production of lipases and lack of elastases. There was no difference in the production of collagenases (Table 2).

Medium alkalization by urea degradation

Pseudogymnoascus species including *P. destructans* significantly increase pH in Sabouraud medium supplemented with urea (permutation test, $p = 0.0001$) (Fig. 3, Supplementary Table S2 online). Dermatophytes increased the pH of both media equally ($p = 0.8$), except for *Arthroderma uncinatum* which only alkalized medium without the presence of urea. Outdoor saprotrophs alkalized none of media analysed ($p = 0.29$). We detected a slight pH decrease (< 0.2) in both of sterile media over the course of the experiment. This means that the detected changes in the pH of inoculated media were the result of fungal growth.

Figure 1. PCA analysis showing dissimilarities in nutrient metabolism between *P. destructans*, other cave fungi and dermatophytes on Biolog Microplates. The plotted PCA axes describe 52.3% of the variability in the data. Tt – *Trichophyton terrestre*, Cm – *Chrysosporium merdarium*, L.sp. – *Leotiomyces* sp. CCF6130, P.71/11 – *Pseudogymnoascus* sp. 2 AK71/11, P.77/11 – *P. sp.* 2 AK77/11, P.87/11 – *P. sp.* 4 AK87/11, P.51/11 – *P.sp.* 1 AK51/11, Ms – *Metapochonia suchlasporia*, Aa – *Aspergillus askiburgiensis*, Oc – *Oidiodendron cerealis*, Myc - *Myotisia cremea* CCF5407, Tm – *T. mentagrophytes*, Au – *Arthroderma uncinatum*, Mc – *Microsporum canis*, Mg – *M. gypseum*.

Figure 2. Growth characteristics on Biolog MicroPlates described by SA, SR and H values. Different letters indicate significant differences between groups and same letters indicate similarity based on Kruskal-Wallis statistics supplemented with Mann–Whitney pairwise comparison and Bonferroni correction.

Table 1. Top ten utilized substrates by *P. destructans* on each Biolog MicroPlates, nutrient sources in parentheses.

FF (C)	PM3 (N)	PM4 (S+P)	PM5 (nutrient supplements)
Tween 80	Gly-Gln	Cytidine-2-monophosphate	L-lysine
D-mannose	Urea	O-phosphoryl-ethanolamine	L-leucine
Gentibiose	Guanosine	O-phospho-L-serine	L-valine
D-trehalose	Gly-Asn	6-phospho-gluonic acid	Orotic acid
D-fructose	Gly-Glu	Guanosine-2-monophosphate	L-isoleucine + L-valine
α-D-glucose	Allantoin	2-deoxy-D-glucose 6-phosphate	D,L-α,δ-diamino-pimelic acid
Glycogen	Ala-Gly	D-3-phospho-glyceric acid	D-alanine
L-glutamic acid	L-glutamine	Carbamyl phosphate	L-tyrosine
Turanose	Ammonia	Uridine-5-monophosphate	L-cysteine
D-psicose	Uric acid	Guanosine-5-monophosphate	Trans-4-hydroxy L-proline

Table 2. Semi-quantitative extracellular enzymes activities indicate the presence of lipases and lack of elastases in *Pseudogymnoascus destructans* compared to *P. spp.*

Species	Strain	Lipases (olive oil)	Elastases pH 5.5	Elastases pH 7	Elastases pH 8.5	Collagenases pH 5.5	Collagenases pH7	Collagenases pH 8
<i>P. destructans</i>	20631-21 ^T	+	-	-	-	+	+	+
	CCF3941	+	-	-	-	+	+	+
	CCF3943	+	-	-	-	+	+	+
	CCF4103	+	-	-	-	+	+	+
	CCF4987	+	-	-	-	+	+	+
	CCF4986	+	-	-	-	+	+	+
<i>P. sp. 1</i>	CCF5025	-	-	-	-	+	+	+
<i>P. sp. 2</i>	CCF5030	-	-	++	+	+	+	+
<i>P. sp. 2</i>	CCF5027	-	-	++	-	+	+	+
<i>P. sp. 2</i>	CCF5029	-	-	+++	+++	+	+	+
<i>P. sp. 3</i>	CCF5026	-	-	++	++	+	+	+

- Activity absent, +/++/+++ detected activity from weak to strong.

Conidial viability under stressful conditions

We evaluated conidial viability under stressful conditions over a period of 42 days for nine *P. destructans* strains, three non-pathogenic *Pseudogymnoascus* species and two air-borne *Aspergillus* species (Fig. 4, Supplementary Table S3 online).

All *Pseudogymnoascus* species, including *P. destructans*, were sensitive to temperatures higher than 30 °C. At the end of the incubation at 30 and 37 °C, conidial viability of *Pseudogymnoascus* spp.

dropped to 44.1% and 6.3%, respectively. *P. destructans* conidia exhibited greater resilience to incubation in 30 °C, final viability of its conidia was 57.2%. Nevertheless, its conidial viability was less than 4% at temperatures between 34 and 37 °C. *P. destructans* was also mildly sensitive to UVA/B radiation, with 49.8% of viable conidia. Our next experiment traced the conidial viability of *P. destructans* strains over a 12-h period of repeated temperature switches from 20 to 34 °C. The changing of temperature markedly enhanced their conidial viability to 64.5%. Even after 85 days of exposure, their conidial viability remained between 6 and 17%, with a mean value of 11.1%. The *Aspergillus* species were resistant to all of the stressful conditions. Sensitivity to the dry conditions was similar across the tested species.

Figure 3. Increase of growth medium pH caused by urea metabolism. The Sabouraud medium is plotted in black and the Sabouraud medium supplemented with urea is plotted in red. Pd – *Pseudogymnoascus destructans*, P.spp. – *Pseudogymnoascus* species, Derma – dermatophytes, Out-Sapro – outdoor saprotrophs.

Figure 4. Test of conidial viability under stressful conditions. A-C: Conidial viability affected by variable stress factors for 42 days. D: prolonged effect of periodic temperature switches from 34 to 20 °C (12 h period, 85 days) on conidial viability of *P. destructans*. Mean values standard deviations for seven strains are presented. Stress factors with a minor effect are plotted in blue. Stress factors causing a decrease in conidial viability under 50% are marked red.

DISCUSSION

Our aims were (1) to ascertain the enzymatic potential and ability of environmental alkalization of *P. destructans*, to compare it with a phylogenetically diverse set of cave fungi (including non-pathogenic *Pseudogymnoascus spp.*), dermatophytes and outdoor saprotrophs, and (2) to characterize the viability of *P. destructans* conidia under stressful conditions. This enabled us to trace potential virulence factors of *P. destructans* and to propose the physiological constraints of *P. destructans* that limit its distribution to bat-inhabited caves. Information about conidial stress tolerance is necessary for a complex evaluation of the dissemination potential of *P. destructans* and the spreading of the white-nose syndrome. We found that *P. destructans* has extensively reduced metabolic potential compared to species tested, including other *Pseudogymnoascus* species. *P. destructans* produces lipases, which may be important for its pathogenicity. Conidia of *P. destructans* are more resilient than mycelium to harsh environmental conditions. Thus, it could mean that conidia contribute to disease spreading after bat departures from caves after winter.

The enzymatic profile of *P. destructans* was more similar to saprotrophic cave fungi than to dermatophytes. The similarity of *P. destructans* with cave fungi found in this study was expectable and points to its descent from the saprotrophic *Pseudogymnoascus* species. *P. destructans* is generally

isolated directly from bats, but rarely also from sediments of abandoned caves³³ where it grows on cellulose and protein/lipid substrates^{40,41}. Our Biolog analyses indicate that *P. destructans* is able to use a broad range of carbon, nitrogen, phosphorus and sulfur sources, but its growth on most such sources is weak. This suggests that *P. destructans* could survive with low fitness on a variety of substrates. Nevertheless, faster-growing cave fungi probably outcompete *P. destructans* on these non-preferred substrates.

Despite the supposed saprophytic origin of *P. destructans*, our results from enzymatic and total Biolog assimilation profiles clearly separate *P. destructans* from cave fungi, including *Pseudogymnoascus* spp. Compared to cave fungi, *P. destructans* strains display intensive enzymatic curtailment on Biolog MicroPlates. We propose that it could be result of *P. destructans* long-term specialization to a specific niche with limited set of available nutrients, which led to subsequent selective loses of metabolic pathways. This supports previous evidence that the metabolism of *P. destructans* is restricted compared to other *Pseudogymnoascus* species^{38,42-44} and confirms the long co-evolution between this pathogen and its hosts.

Both dermatophytes and *P. destructans* grow on mammal skin, and thus have similar nutrient sources available for growth. Our sampling unable us to draw decided conclusions; however, it seems that they have different nutritive strategy. While dermatophytes prefer nitrogenous substrates, *P. destructans* is rather specialized on lipid substrates. *P. destructans* even differs from analyzed cave fungi, including non-pathogenic *Pseudogymnoascus* spp., that prefer saccharides as carbon sources. These results correspond with prior findings of lipid degradation by *P. destructans*^{40,45}. We propose that *P. destructans* preference of lipids is one of virulence factors, which enables *P. destructans* to colonize bat tissues. Lipases enable fungi to damage epidermal and epithelial tissue. They also influence fungal growth, adherence and dissemination inside the host⁴⁶. Our comparative eco-physiological approach proposes outstanding role of lipid and fatty acid degradation in the virulence of *P. destructans*, as already noted by Donaldson et al.²⁹ based on transcriptomic data. Given the facts that *P. destructans* lacks keratinolytic activity and that phospholipids are a major component of all cell membranes, lipases are probably the most important enzymes allowing fungal hyphae to digest and invade the integumentary structures of infected skin, forming cup-like erosions diagnostic of the white-nose syndrome.

Similarly to cave fungi including *Pseudogymnoascus* spp., *P. destructans* prefers urea, allantoin, ammonia and uric acid as nitrogen sources. These substances are products of the metabolic breakdown of nitrogenous compounds. Beside occurrence in sediments, these substances are also contained in urine and sweat. In bat skin, they are typical components of sweat glands, where hyphal growth of *P. destructans* was described² and thus where are easily accessible for its nutrition. Beside nitrogen metabolism, urease has a versatile functions in plants, animals and microorganisms, as is reviewed in⁴⁷. It participates in fungal pathogenesis^{48,49}, for example by production of ammonia which cause environmental alkalization⁵⁰ and subsequent spontaneous creation of reactive oxygen species⁵¹ and tissue damage. We detected an increase in pH caused by the degradation of urea during cultivation of *P. destructans*. Nevertheless, we were not successful in direct pH measurements in bat necrosis, thus further experiments are needed to examine the role of pH manipulation in virulence of *P. destructans*.

Similarly to other *Pseudogymnoascus* species, *P. destructans* produces collagenases that erode connective tissues and enable fungi to penetrate the skin of bats. Collagenase production is well known

in *P. destructans*^{25,52}, but from our data we propose that it is probably a preadaptation present in the whole genus, not an adaptation primarily responsible for the behavior of *P. destructans*. This corresponds with the fact that *P. destructans* has an equal level of protease expression (including that of destructins) in agar culture and on the wings of bats²⁹. Similarly, subtilisin-like serine proteases, whose role in virulence is not yet clear, are present both in *P. destructans* and *P. pannorum*²⁵. Our results presume that *P. destructans* lacks the ability to cleave other constitutive proteins in the skin, elastin and keratin, which may suggest that the pathogen does not use enzymatic skin degradation primarily for nutrient acquisition. Thus, we propose that other nutrient sources like lipids, urea and various nitrogenous sources found in sweat glands are targets for assimilation by *P. destructans*.

Preceding studies have shown that temperatures above 20 °C³⁷ and relative humidity lower than 70%⁵³ impedes the mycelial growth of *P. destructans*. Our viability tests revealed that conidia of *P. destructans* are more resilient to higher temperatures and lower humidity than its mycelium. Recent study³⁹ has proposed that conidia of *P. destructans* could germinate even after exposition to elevated temperatures. Our simulation of temperature changes on the surface of a bat's body after its departure from a cave indicates even more prolonged conidial viability of *P. destructans* at higher temperatures. In vitro conditions are far away from that in nature, where more factors are combined and could have cumulative negative effect on viability of conidia. Thus, we cannot foresee how long conidia of *P. destructans* stay viable on the bat body surface after its departure from cave. However, we can state that conidia of *P. destructans* are much more resilient to harsh environmental conditions than its mycelium. As conidia are the primary dissemination agent of fungi, we wonder if they might be able to survive on the surface of the bat body reaching the next hibernation site.

CONCLUSION

Analyzed cave fungi, despite being phylogenetically unrelated, represent a metabolically well-defined group. Among them, *Pseudogymnoascus destructans* evinces specific physiological profile. We suggest that it is a result of its strong specialization to life on bat skin and pathogenicity. *Pseudogymnoascus destructans* is specific by loss of redundant metabolic variability and production of lipases. We propose that lipases are probably the most important enzymes allowing fungal hyphae to digest and invade the integumentary structures of infected skin. The future investigations of virulence could test our hypothesis by specific knock-out of these genes. *Pseudogymnoascus destructans* conidia show great viability potential under various stressful condition, which offers possibility of their inactive persistence on the body surface of bats during their active season. These resting conidia are maybe able to germinate when bats reach their hibernation sites, where environmental conditions enable the growth of *P. destructans*. This could mean that once infected bats might serve as a reservoir and vector for the spread of the disease to new hibernacula.

METHODS

Fungal material and cultivation

The type strain from the USA and nine European strains of *P. destructans* strains covering different haplotypes and mating types identified according to Zukal et al.⁶ were used. Representatives of typical non-pathogenic cave-inhabiting fungi (8 genera from four Ascomycota orders, 16 strains) and dermatophytes (2 genera, 5 strains) or saprotrophic fungi (2 genera, 3 strains) living outside of caves were chosen for comparison (Tables 3, 4). Relatively low representation of dermatophyte and outside

living saprotrophic strains prevents general conclusion about their physiology. Nevertheless, it was not attempt of our study. Inclusion of these species served us for suggestions of potential selective pressures that could play a role in formation of *P. destructans* physiology. Fungal isolates were identified by ITS rDNA barcoding using the methods of Kolařík et al.⁵⁴, and their sequences were deposited in the EMBL sequence database. Cultures were deposited in the Culture Collection of Fungi (abbreviations CCF or AK) at the Department of Botany, Faculty of Science, Charles University in Prague. *Pseudogymnoascus* species including *P. destructans* were grown in Petri dish containing glucose yeast extract agar (GYEA, 20 g glucose, 5 g yeast extract, 15 g agar, 1 l distilled water) at 10 °C unless stated otherwise. Cave fungi *Trichophyton terrestre* AK44/09, Leotiomycetes sp. CCF6130 (88/11) and *Chrysosporium merdarium* CCF6131 (AK91/11) were grown on 4° malt agar (MA) at 10 °C. Other fungi were cultivated on 4° MA at 25 °C.

Biolog analysis

Biolog MicroPlate for Filamentous Fungi (FF) and Biolog Phenotype Micro-Arrays (PM) (Biolog, Inc., Hayward, CA) were used to evaluate the assimilation profiles of carbon (FF), nitrogen (PM3B), phosphorus, sulphur (PM4A) and nutrient supplements (PM5) according to the manufacturer's instructions. Fungal conidia from grown cultures were transferred into the inoculating fluid (0.25% Phytigel, 0.03% Tween 40) by rolling a swab across sporulating areas to get the final transmittance of $75 \pm 2\%$ or $62 \pm 2\%$ for FF and PM, respectively. Inoculated plates were incubated at convenient temperatures as is described in "Fungal material and cultivation" section, and absorbance at 750 nm was used to measure mycelial growth. Two technical replicates per strain were prepared for the FF plates and one replicate was prepared for the PM plates. The isolates analysed differed in their growth rate. For this reason, the last readings before reaching a growth plateau of substrate utilization were used for analysis.

The absorbance of the negative control was subtracted from all substrates within one plate and negative values were assigned a value of zero⁵⁵. Some substrates were omitted from the analysis due to their low solubility (FF—B1, B3, G2, H10; PM3B—C1, G1; PM4A—A3, B9). Functional diversity was evaluated based on substrate activity (SA), substrate richness (SR)⁵⁶ and the Shannon index (H)⁵⁷. In brief, SA was defined as the sum of the optical densities of all substrates on one plate greater than zero. SR is defined as the number of substrates on a microtitre plate that exhibit an optical density greater than the threshold. The optical density of 0.1 was fixed as the threshold for FF and PM3B plates, and the optical density of 0.01 was fixed for PM4A and PM5 plates⁵⁸.

Table 3. Fungal strains used in this study.

Group	Fungus	Source	Sequence accession number	Reference
<i>Pseudogymnoascus destructans</i> (Leotiomyces)	CCF3938	CZE, Solenice, <i>Myotis myotis</i> , 2010	HM584954	66
	CCF3941	CZE, Bohemian Karst, Malá Amerika mine, <i>Myotis myotis</i> , 2010	HM584956	66
	CCF3943	CZE, Stříbro, <i>Myotis myotis</i> , 2010	HM584957	66
	CCF4103	CZE, Herlíkovice, Krkonoše Mts., <i>Pleurotus auritus</i> , 2011	LN852366	19
	CCF4124	CZE, Horní Albeřice, Krkonoše, <i>Myotis myotis</i> , 2011	KJ938421	9
	CCF4131	CZE, Vyškov u Chodové Plané, <i>Myotis myotis</i> , 2011	KJ938420	9
	CCF4132	CZE, Pernink, <i>Myotis myotis</i> , 2011	nd	9
	CCF4987	CZE, Kašperské Hory, <i>Myotis myotis</i> , 2014	LN871252	6
	CCF4986	Rusia, Ural mts., cave Smolinskaya, <i>Myotis dasycneme</i> , 2014	LN852359	6
	20631-21 ^T	USA, Williams Hotel, NY, <i>Myotis lucifugus</i> , 2008	EU884921	35
Saprotrophic cave fungi	<i>Pseudogymnoascus</i> sp. 1 CCF5025 ¹	CZE, Bohemian Karst, Alkazar tunnel, bat excrement, 2009	LN852360	19
	<i>P. sp. 2</i> CCF5030 ²	CZE, Moravia, <i>Myotis myotis</i> , 2012	LN852361	19
	<i>P. sp. 2</i> CCF5027 ²	CZE, cave sediment, Moravia, Javoříčske Caves, 2012	LN852363	19
	<i>P. sp. 2</i> CCF5029 ²	CZE, Moravia, Javoříčske caves, cave sediment, 2012	LN852364	19
	<i>P. sp. 3</i> CCF5026 ³	CZE, Moravian Karst, Sloupsko-Šošůvké Cave,	LN852365	19

	<i>Rhinolophus hipposideros</i> , 2013		
<i>P. sp. 1</i> AK51/11 ⁴	CZE, Herlíkovice, Krkonoše, <i>Eptesicus nilssonii</i>	LN714595	67
<i>P. sp. 2</i> AK71/11 ⁵	CZE, Velká Amerika mine, sediment, 2011	Submitted to EMBL	This study
<i>P. sp. 4</i> AK87/11 ⁶	CZE, Bohemian Karst, Koněpruské jeskyně caves, sediment, 2011	Submitted to EMBL	This study
<i>P. sp. 2</i> AK 77/11 ⁷	CZE, Bohemian Karst, Velká Amerika mine, sediment, 2011	Submitted to EMBL	This study
<i>Trichophyton terrestre</i> AK44/09 (Onygenales)	CZE, Bohemian Karst, Alkazar tunnel, excrement, 2009	LN714614	67
<i>Myotis cremea</i> CCF5407 (Onygenales)	CZE, Bohemian Karst, Malá Amerika mine, bat excrement, 2009	LT627243	68
<i>Metapochonia suchlasporia</i> CCF6128 (Clavicipitaceae)	CZE, Bohemian Karst, Velká Amerika mine, sediment, 2011	Submitted to EMBL	This study
<i>Leotiomycetes sp.</i> CCF6130 (= AK88/11) ⁸	CZE, Bohemian Karst, Velká Amerika mine, sediment, 2011	Submitted to EMBL	This study
<i>Chrysosporium merdarium</i> CCF6131 (AK 91/11) (Leotiomycetes)	CZE, Karlštejn castle, sediment in the castle well, 2011	Submitted to EMBL	This study
<i>Oidiodendron cerealis</i> CCF3491 (Leotiomycetes)	CZE, Bedřichov, tunnel wall, 2004	ng	This study
<i>Aspergillus askiburgiensis</i> CCF4085 (Eurotiales)	CZE, Bohemian Karst, Malá Amerika mine, WNS positive <i>Myotis myotis</i> , 2010	LN873940	69
Saprotroph from the outside of underground spaces	<i>Aspergillus luchuensis</i> CCF3984 (Eurotiales)	CZE, Praha, tea bag (Yerba maté), 2010	FR727131 V. Hubka, unpublished

	<i>A. flavus</i> CCF3154 (Eurotiales)	Brno ČR, black papper, 1999	ng	
	<i>Penicillium oxalicum</i> 2315 ^T (Eurotiales)	USA, soil, Connecticut, 1914	HE651152	70
Dermatophyte	<i>Microsporum canis</i> CCF3443 (Onygenales)	CZE, Ostrava, human skin, 2003	ng	
	<i>Microsporum gypseum</i> CCF3100 (Onygenales)	CZE, Šumperk, human skin, 1998	ng	
	<i>Arthroderma uncinatum</i> CCF2907 (Onygenales)	CZE, Horní Počaply ČR, soil with industrial ash deposits, 1994	ng	
	<i>Trichophyton mentagrophytes</i> CCF3954 (Onygenales)	CZE, Pardubice, human skin, 2009	ng	
	<i>Trichophyton interdigitale</i> CCF4473 (Onygenales)	CZE, tinea corporis, human skin, 2012	LN736306	71

CZE – Czech Republic. ¹ITS rDNA identical with JX270356, “Clade L” sensu¹, ²ITS rDNA identical with JX845296. “Clade B” sensu¹, ³ITS rDNA identical with JX270432. “Clade J” sensu¹, ⁴ITS rDNA 99% (466/467 bp) similarity with JX270356. “Clade L” sensu¹, ⁵ITS rDNA 99% (570/571 bp) similarity with JX270614. “Clade B” sensu¹, ⁶ITS rDNA 99% (884/894 bp) similarity with JX270621. Phylogenetic position outside of the clades delimited by¹, ⁷ITS rDNA 99% (893/896 bp) similarity with JX270443. “Clade B” sensu¹, ⁸Best BlastN hits (90% for ITS rDNA) are various *Botrytis* species (e.g. *Botrytis cinerea* strain CBS 261.71, MH860108).

Table 4. List of analysed species and used methods.

Group	Fungal strain	Biolog	Extracellular enzymes	pH test	Conidial viability test
<i>Pseudogymnoascus destructans</i>	20631-21 ^T	-	+	+	-
	CCF3938	+	-	-	+
	CCF3941	+	+	+	+
	CCF3943	+	+	+	+
	CCF4103	+	+	+	+
	CCF4124	+	-	-	+
	CCF4131	+	-	-	+
	CCF4132	+	-	-	+
	CCF4986	-	+	+	-
	CCF4987	-	+	+	-
Cave fungi	<i>Aspergillus askiburgiensis</i> CCF4085	+	-	-	-
	<i>Chrysosporium merdarium</i> CCF6131	+	-	-	-
	<i>Leotiomycetes</i> sp. CCF6130	+	-	-	-
	<i>Metapochonia suchlasporia</i> CCF6128	+	-	-	-
	<i>Myotisia cremea</i> CCF5407	+	-	-	-
	<i>Oidiodendron cerealis</i> CCF3491	+	-	-	-
	<i>Pseudogymnoascus</i> sp. 1 AK51/11	+	-	+	+
	<i>P.</i> sp. 1 CCF5025	-	+	+	-
	<i>P.</i> sp. 2 CCF5027	-	+	+	-
	<i>P.</i> sp. 2 CCF5029	-	+	+	-
	<i>P.</i> sp. 2 CCF5030	-	+	+	-
	<i>P.</i> sp. 2 AK71/11	+	-	-	+
	<i>P.</i> sp. 2 AK 77/11	+	-	-	+
	<i>P.</i> sp. 3 CCF5026	-	+	+	-
	<i>P.</i> sp. 4 AK87/11	+	-	-	-
	<i>Trichophyton terrestre</i> AK44/09	+	-	-	-
	Sapro-troph	<i>Aspergillus flavus</i> CCF3154	-	-	+
<i>A. luchuensis</i> CCF3984		-	-	+	+
<i>Penicillium oxalicum</i> 2315 ^T		-	-	+	-
Dermatophyte	<i>Arthroderma uncinatum</i> CCF2907	+	-	+	-
	<i>Microsporum canis</i> CCF3443	+	-	+	-
	<i>M. gypseum</i> CCF3100	+	-	+	-
	<i>T. interdigitale</i> CCF4473	-	-	+	-
<i>T. mentagrophytes</i> CCF3954	+	-	+	-	

+/- Analyses done/not done.

Extracellular enzyme detection

Lipolytic activities were detected using the rhodamine B assay described by⁵⁹. Rhodamine B plates were made using the Czapek substrate as the basal medium with the addition of rhodamine B (0.0001% w/v) and olive oil (1%) as a lipid substrate. Inoculated plates were incubated at 4 °C for three weeks, as this temperature is similar to that in bat hibernacula. Fungal colonies with lipolytic activity showed an orange fluorescent halo under UV light.

For collagenase assays, strains were grown as described by⁶⁰ for two weeks at 4 °C. An adaptation of the double-layer plate assay was employed for the detection of enzymatic activity⁶¹. Briefly, Petri dishes were filled with a bottom layer containing 15 ml of 0.7% (w/v) agarose in 50 mM citric acid/sodium citrate buffer (pH 5.5) and 50 mM phosphate buffer (pH 7 and pH 8), and then overlaid with 5 ml of the same media with the addition of 2% w/v collagen. The plates were then inoculated with 10 µl drops from the cultures of the strains in the Czapek medium supplemented with collagen. Undigested collagen was detected by Coomassie brilliant blue G staining⁶⁰. An identical procedure, in which the collagen was replaced by elastin, was followed to test the production of elastases. Elastin hydrolysis was detected based on the observation of halos⁶².

Medium alkalization by urea degradation

The ability to alkalize the growth medium by the degradation of urea was investigated by comparison of pH changes during cultivation on a liquid Sabouraud medium (40 g glucose, 10 g pepton, 1 l distilled water) versus a liquid Sabouraud medium supplemented with 50 mM of filter sterilised urea. Erlenmeyer flasks containing 150 ml of the medium were inoculated by fungal strains and pH was measured by a digital pH meter until the maximum value was reached. Non-inoculated sterile media were used as a control. *Penicillium oxalicum* CCF2315 served as a negative control because of its known acidification ability. *Pseudogymnoascus* species were cultivated at 15 °C for up to 5 weeks, dermatophytes and outdoor saprotrophs were cultivated at 25 °C for up to 3 weeks.

Conidial survival under stressful conditions

We compared the conidial viability of *P. destructans* under stressful conditions with that of several non-pathogenic *Pseudogymnoascus* species living in caves and two airborne *Aspergillus* saprotrophic species. The fungi were grown under their optimal growth conditions to attain sufficient conidial production. Petri dishes (one replication for each set of conditions) with well-established fungal cultures were exposed for up to six weeks to ten sets of physical conditions: in the dark at 25 °C, 30 °C, 34 °C and 37 °C; at 25 °C with white light, UVA, UVA plus UVB radiation, and in dryness (dark). UVA and UVB radiation, and white light was administered by a fluorescent tube lamp UV 11 W/G23-DZ (11 W, 350–410 nm), a fluorescent tube lamp Repti Glo 10.0 (20 W, T8, 10% UVB and 33% UVA) and a white light bulb (Philips, LUX BL, 11 W, 230–240 V, ~ 50/60 Hz, 2700 K), respectively. The influence of dryness was tested on conidia obtained by rolling a swab across a well-established culture. Swabs with conidia were then placed into glass jars containing silica gel and sealed with Parafilm to keep humidity below 20%. Conidial viability was evaluated weekly. The next experiment traced conidial viability of *P. destructans* strains during a 12 h period of repeated temperature switches from 20 to 34 °C for 85 days in the dark, by which we simulated temperature changes during the day and night on the body surface of bats after their departure from a cave, i.e. temperatures of homeothermy and daily torpor during the bats' active season⁶³.

Evaluation of conidial viability by flow cytometry

Conidia from stressed cultures were collected using a cotton swab into a 10 × phosphate-buffered saline solution (PBS, 1.370 M NaCl, 27 mM KCl, 0.1 M Na₂PO₄, 18 mM KH₂PO₄), pH 7.4, and their concentration was adjusted to 5–7 × 10⁶ conidia/ml. Propidium iodide (PI) was added to attain the final concentration of 2 µg/ml. Samples were incubated with PI for 30 min at room temperature. Three technical replicates per sample were measured using an LSRII (Becton Dickinson, New Jersey, USA) flow cytometer equipped with FACSdiva 6 Software at the Service Centre for Cytometry and Microscopy at the Institute of Microbiology of the Czech Academy of Sciences. Excitation was performed using a Melles Griot 85-YCA-025 laser (23 mW) with a wavelength of 561 nm. Fluorescence was collected through a 590 LP filter and a 610/20 BP filter. Data were analysed in FlowJo 7.6.1 (Tree Star, Inc., Ashland, USA). We verified the precision of this method by testing the viability test of conidia (1) obtained from a non-stressed culture grown under convenient conditions, (2) conidia fixed with 70% ethanol, and (3) a mixture of non-stressed and fixed conidia in various proportions. The mean percentages of viable conidia from untreated and fixed cultures were 90% and 3.8%, respectively. The detected percentages of viable conidia corresponded to the predefined proportions of non-stressed and fixed conidia. We therefore consider flow cytometry with PI staining a suitable method for testing conidial viability. As the viability does not mean germinability, we also cultivated these samples on GYEA for 14 days. Each sample was cultivated at three different conidial concentrations in three replications. Linear Regression Analysis revealed strong correlation between the mean proportions of germinating conidia and proportions of viable conidia detected by FCM (Fig. 5), $R^2 = 9.3$. The proportion of germinated conidia was lower than proportion of viable conidia detected by FCM, only 36% of non-stressed conidia are able to germinate. Thus, *P. destructans* conidia have relatively low natural germinability or they need specific cultivation conditions for germination. The germination process is a complex result of environmental and physiological factors⁶⁴. Thus, we cannot foresee the germination efficiency of stressed conidia in nature. However, observed correlation between conidial in vitro germination and conidial viability tests enables insight into approximate germination potential of conidia. Data analysis and gating strategy is presented in Supplementary Figure S1 online.

Statistics

Biolog data were visualized using PCA (Principal Component Analysis) in PAST⁶⁵. The statistical significance of the type of ecology was evaluated by one-way NPMANOVA with Bonferroni-corrected *p*-values using Bray–Curtis distance and 9,999 permutations. Differences in SA, SR and H between ecological groups were evaluated using Kruskal–Wallis statistics supplemented with Mann–Whitney pairwise comparison and Bonferroni correction. Significance of medium alkalization by urea degradation was computed by permutation test using 9,999 permutations.

Figure 5. Strong correlation between proportion of germinated conidia on GYEA and proportion of viable conidia detected by FCM. Mean values with standard deviations of proportions of germinated conidia are presented. Linear Regression curve is marked in red, $R^2 = 9.3$.

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SUPPLEMENTARY INFORMATION

Figure S1: Data analyses from flow cytometry – gating strategy.

Data was first checked on FSC-A – FSC-H plot to gate population “singlet” which ensures that only separated conidia will be analyzed and all conidial clusters will be omitted.

All events in “singlet” population with PI fluorescence under threshold (defined by measurements of unlabeled conidia) were gated to population “Live” which contains living conidia with negative PI fluorescence.

All events with higher fluorescence intensities than defined threshold represent dead conidia, as PI can stain only dead cells.

Table S1: The most utilised nutrient sources on each Biolog MicroPlates tested.

Nutrient sources	<i>P. destructans</i>	Cave fungi	Dermatophytes
Carbon	Tween 80	D-Trehalose	L-Phenylalanine
	D-Mannose	Gentibiose	L-Glutamic Acid
	Gentibiose	α -D-Glucose	L-Alanine
	D-Trehalose	D-Fructose	Glycyl-L-Glutamic Acid
	D-Fructose	N-Acetyl-D-Glucosamine	N-Acetyl-D-Glucosamine
	α -D-Glucose	Maltose	L-Analyl-Glycine
	Glycogen	D-Mannose	L-Ornithine
	L-Glutamic Acid	D-Psicose	α -D-Glucose D-Mannose
	Turanose	Sucrose	Alaninamid
	D-Psicose	Glycerol	L-Phenylalanine
	Nitrogen	Gly-Gln	Guanosine
Urea		L-Arginine	Gly-Glu
Guanosine		Urea	L-Citrulline
Gly-Asn		Gly-Asn	Ala-Gln
Gly-Glu		Ala-Gly	Gly-Gln
allantoin		Gly-Gln	Ala-Leu
Ala-Gly		L-Alanine	Ala-Gly
L-Glutamine		Uric Acid	L-Ornithine
Ammonia		Ala-Leu	L-Arginine
Uric Acid		N-Acetyl-D-Glucosamine	L-Glutamine
Sulphur + Phosphorus		Cytidine-2-Monophosphate	Cytidine-2-Monophosphate
	O-PhosphorylEthanolamine	O-Phosphoryl-Ethanolamine	O-Phospho-L-Tyrosine
	O-Phospho-L-Serine	Thymidine-3-Monophosphate	Tripolyphosphate
	6-Phospho-Gluonic Acid	Guanosine-2-Monophosphate	Cytidine-2-Monophosphate
	Guanosine-2-Monophosphate	Adenosine-5-Monophosphate	O-Phospho-L-Serine
	2-Deoxy-D-Glucose 6-Phosphate	Guanosine-5-Monophosphate	Phosphoenol Pyruvate
	D-3-Phospho-Glyceric Acid	Cytidine-5-Monophosphate	Guanosine-2-Monophosphate
	Carbamyl Phosphate	Phosphocreatine	Guanosine-5-Monophosphate
	Uridine-5-Monophosphate	D-2-Phospho-Glyceric Acid	Adenosine-2-Monophosphate
	Guanosine-5-Monophosphate	Cytidine-3-Monophosphate	Guanosine-2-,3-Cyclic
	Nutrient Supplements	L-Lysine	Orotic Acid
L-Leucine		Pyridoxal	D,L-Mevalonic Acid β -Nicotinamide Adenine
L-Valine		D-Alanine	Dinucleotide
Orotic Acid		D-Glutamic Acid	Folic Acid
L-Isoleucine + L-Valine		L-Cysteine	D-(+)-Glucose
D,L- α , δ -Diamino-Pimelic Acid		Pyridoxamine	Menadlone
D-Alanine		Adenine	(δ) 4-Amino-Imidazole-4(5)Carboxamide
L-Tyrosine		Phenylalanine	Inosine + Thiamine
L-Cysteine		L-Methionine	p-Amino-Benzoic Acid
Trans-4-Hydroxy L-Proline		L-Valine	Orotic Acid

Table S2. Medium alkalisation by urea degradation.

Fungal strains	Sabouraud medium			Sabouraud medium with urea		
	A	B	C	A	B	C
<i>Pseudogymnoascus destructans</i> 20631-21	6.04	5.87	6.04	8.26	8.29	8.41
<i>P. destructans</i> CCF3941	4.98	4.86	4.86	7.85	7.94	7.38
<i>P. destructans</i> CCF3943	5.78	5.66	6.21	7.53	7.26	7.6
<i>P. destructans</i> CCF4103	5.4	5.32	5.3	8.04	7.86	7.72
<i>P. destructans</i> CCF4986	6.69	6.54	6.39	8.77	8.35	8.75
<i>P. destructans</i> CCF4987	5.52	5.71	5.71	7.43	7.19	7.51
<i>P. sp. 1</i> CCF5025	5.67	5.56	5.81	7.9	8.54	8.55
<i>P. sp. 1</i> AK51/11	5.95	6.00	5.96	8.89	8.75	8.74
<i>P. sp. 2</i> CCF5027	5.05	5.07	5.06	8.84	8.83	8.89
<i>P. sp. 2</i> CCF5029	4.39	5.4	5.29	8.89	8.92	8.83
<i>P. sp. 2</i> CCF5030	6.06	5.29	5.41	8.84	8.84	8.84
<i>P. sp. 3</i> CCF5026	5.7	5.66	5.8	8.75	8.79	8.74
<i>Aspergillus flavus</i> CCF3154	8.52	8.52	7.59	8.39	8.37	8.25
<i>A. luchvensis</i> CCF3984	6.66	6.61	6.54	8.13	7.89	8.1
<i>P. oxalicum</i> 2315T	4.46	4.5	4.5	5.36	5.65	5.67
<i>Arthroderma uncinatum</i> CCF2907	7.74	7.5	7.79	5.46	5.37	5.13
<i>Microsporum canis</i> PL1077/16	7.26	7.37	7.44	9.01	8.14	8.99
<i>M. gypseum</i> CCF4749	7.82	7.54	7.55	9.08	9.09	8.96
<i>Trichophyton interdigitale</i> CCF4473	8.31	8.35	8.38	8.58	7.54	8.5
<i>T. terrestre</i> DMF3040/13	7.61	7.67	7.67	8.75	8.28	9.03
Sterile media	5.58	5.6	5.61	5.78	5.72	5.74

A, B, C – three replication for each strain analysed.

Table S3. Percentage of viable conidia for *Pseudogymnoascus destructans*, other cave *P.* species, and outdoor saprotroph *Aspergillus* species.

stressful condition	days	<i>Pseudogymnoascus destructans</i> strains									<i>Pseudogymnoascus</i> species					<i>Aspergillus</i> species				
		CCF 3938	CCF 3941	CCF 3943	CCF 4103	CCF 4124	CCF 4129	CCF 4131	CCF 4132	Mean	SD	AK 77.11	AK 51.11	AK 71.11	Mean	SD	CCF 3154	CCF 3984	Mean	SD
non-stressed	2	90.0	91.0	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	92.0	91.0	1.0	94.5	78.3	95.0	89.3	9.5	90.1	93.0	91.6	1.5
	7	88.9	77.3	81.1	84.7	86.8	85.3	86.8	86.2	84.6	3.7	94.0	76.4	91.6	87.3	9.5	87.4	91.2	89.3	1.9
	14	78.9	82.6	78.5	82.9	86.3	85.8	84.4	76.2	81.9	3.7	76.1	78.9	93.0	82.7	9.1	70.2	93.6	81.9	11.7
	21	85.4	84.6	78.6	80.2	82.5	70.8	84.2	85.6	81.5	5.0	88.9	69.7	80.0	79.5	9.6	88.7	90.3	89.5	0.8
	28	84.9	74.3	80.9	81.6	88.3	79.4	84.4	80.8	81.8	4.2	72.9	67.8	93.8	78.2	13.7	89.9	93.2	91.6	1.7
	35	83.5	68.0	78.5	80.2	88.4	77.4	79.9	74.4	78.8	6.0	77.2	67.3	95.8	80.1	14.5	89.4	76.5	82.9	6.5
	42	86.6	72.1	79.1	76.6	83.2	83.2	82.1	86.5	81.2	5.0	63.6	57.1	94.8	71.8	20.1	69.9	89.4	79.6	9.7
UVA.B	2	76.1	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	86.2	81.2	7.1	88.1	53.5	92.7	78.1	21.4	81.5	92.6	87.1	5.5
	7	74.1	NA	85.7	73.3	89.5	NA	82.4	84.4	81.6	6.5	89.6	75.6	86.9	84.0	7.5	86.3	87.6	87.0	0.6
	14	70.9	NA	43.7	53.0	77.3	NA	43.8	72.5	60.2	15.2	86.6	38.2	85.7	70.2	27.7	85.0	85.1	85.0	0.1
	21	69.3	NA	54.5	32.2	57.7	NA	56.6	81.3	58.6	16.4	58.9	34.3	76.2	56.5	21.0	91.2	86.1	88.7	2.6
	28	74.0	NA	59.8	40.8	81.1	NA	69.3	82.0	67.8	15.6	76.9	40.7	84.0	67.2	23.2	75.6	93.7	84.7	9.0
	35	65.7	NA	44.7	25.2	48.3	NA	38.4	57.8	46.7	14.3	75.4	30.5	80.4	62.1	27.5	80.5	94.2	87.4	6.9
	42	76.5	NA	8.1	38.8	NA	NA	46.0	79.6	49.8	29.5	64.2	55.6	88.8	69.5	17.2	75.5	87.1	81.3	5.8
light	2	82.0	76.5	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	90.2	82.9	6.9	67.0	70.3	96.2	77.8	13.0	84.4	94.5	89.4	5.1
	7	93.5	74.3	52.5	NA	87.0	89.1	87.6	89.1	81.9	14.2	82.2	76.8	92.5	83.9	6.5	84.5	88.3	86.4	1.9
	14	91.9	76.2	66.3	NA	87.5	86.2	83.7	67.9	80.0	10.0	88.4	75.4	92.7	85.5	7.3	76.1	72.8	74.5	1.7
	21	86.3	54.7	76.6	NA	75.3	76.7	77.0	88.2	76.4	10.9	84.1	79.9	89.2	84.4	3.8	90.8	87.3	89.1	1.7
	28	83.3	48.2	76.0	NA	73.1	84.2	81.0	84.8	75.8	12.9	74.0	69.4	94.4	79.3	10.9	87.3	94.2	90.8	3.5
	35	87.4	36.1	71.2	NA	28.6	82.6	72.8	61.8	62.9	22.5	86.3	50.0	95.0	77.1	19.5	70.7	91.6	81.2	10.4
	42	86.4	27.3	71.4	NA	63.1	61.9	64.3	76.5	64.4	18.6	87.6	80.6	77.3	81.8	4.3	78.7	91.8	85.3	6.6
UVA	2	82.5	65.3	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	87.7	78.5	11.7	93.5	72.7	94.7	87.0	10.1	84.2	95.5	89.8	5.7
	7	93.2	67.9	71.0	92.7	92.4	90.9	86.5	84.3	84.9	10.1	86.5	71.0	89.5	82.3	8.1	87.3	92.5	89.9	2.6
	14	88.6	32.5	52.2	41.9	78.0	81.8	80.3	65.4	65.1	20.7	91.1	82.6	91.8	88.5	4.2	74.7	86.6	80.6	6.0
	21	79.5	22.8	54.8	10.2	67.3	71.2	48.8	74.6	53.6	25.2	75.8	71.5	83.6	77.0	5.0	86.4	82.9	84.6	1.8

	28	70.7	19.4	60.3	72.2	50.1	83.9	48.6	78.8	60.5	20.9	84.6	42.7	92.6	73.3	21.9	89.8	92.8	91.3	1.5
	35	69.8	2.6	58.8	50.9		58.3	44.4	58.6	49.1	21.9	59.3	23.8	90.5	57.9	27.2	84.9	85.5	85.2	0.3
	42	60.8	14.2	57.9	73.5	70.1	43.5	77.4	71.5	58.6	21.0	81.9	10.8	76.1	56.3	32.2	75.4	91.4	83.4	8.0
30 °C	2	73.3	73.7	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	86.3	77.8	7.4	91.5	78.7	95.9	88.7	7.3	88.8	94.1	91.5	2.7
	7	89.0	65.9	81.1	69.3	82.4	77.1	68.6	83.2	77.1	8.3	89.3	67.9	91.9	83.0	10.8	81.1	77.1	79.1	2.0
	14	92.1	58.9	61.2	67.4	80.2	79.5	76.7	57.8	71.7	12.3	77.0	74.5	81.9	77.8	3.1	79.3	78.7	79.0	0.3
	21	91.1	50.6	67.0	87.3	47.0	79.5	72.2	69.9	70.6	15.8	53.2	70.5	77.8	67.2	10.3	88.1	87.8	88.0	0.1
	28	80.4	34.6	72.2	85.0	77.0	83.5	64.9	79.6	72.2	16.5	57.1	3.3	79.5	46.7	32.0	88.6	95.4	92.0	3.4
	35	82.3	42.1	76.6	72.4	77.9	78.3	60.4	73.2	70.4	13.1	48.0	2.5	84.4	45.0	33.5	84.3	85.0	84.6	0.4
	42	86.1	18.1	39.2	46.9	68.1	53.1	53.1	67.1	53.9	20.6	47.2	7.0	78.1	44.1	29.1	79.2	92.4	85.8	6.6
37 °C	2	81.1	81.1	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	88.2	83.5	4.1	78.4	70.7	95.6	81.6	10.4	95.2	95.4	95.3	0.1
	7	78.1	78.1	80.2	NA	37.4	73.9	NA	83.2	71.8	17.1	41.8	76.8	92.7	70.4	21.3	82.8	93.3	88.1	5.3
	14	37.5	37.5	52.9	NA	31.9	31.2	NA	26.0	36.2	9.3	61.1	12.0	23.7	32.2	20.9	81.4	83.1	82.3	0.8
	21	1.6	1.6	7.1	NA	3.9	3.2	NA	2.9	3.4	2.1	0.7	3.3	2.9	2.3	1.1	81.2	88.6	84.9	3.7
	28	1.0	1.0	9.0	NA	9.5	5.5	NA	6.2	5.4	3.7	2.1	3.3	4.3	3.2	0.9	90.4	94.7	92.5	2.2
	35	1.2	1.2	3.5	NA	6.3	4.8	NA	2.8	3.3	2.0	7.8	2.1	2.7	4.2	2.5	77.7	94.0	85.8	8.1
	42	1.0	1.0	2.0	NA	9.5	3.0	NA	6.4	3.8	3.4	7.5	3.9	7.5	6.3	1.7	75.8	91.3	83.5	7.7
dryness	2	71.1	63.1	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	87.6	73.9	12.5	46.4	52.8	92.4	63.9	20.4	69.6	93.1	81.4	11.8
	7	84.2	21.3	63.5	80.6	71.3	79.5	60.2	74.3	66.9	20.2	77.0	59.7	89.5	75.4	12.2	80.3	93.8	87.0	6.7
	14	86.0	18.4	53.5	80.6	71.4	66.9	65.1	71.4	64.2	20.9	71.5	64.6	85.1	73.8	8.5	66.1	83.1	74.6	8.5
	21	69.3	6.8	51.4	87.8	28.8	79.1	45.3	77.3	55.7	28.0	63.5	53.7	85.7	67.7	13.4	79.3	84.8	82.1	2.8
	28	80.3	7.3	46.6	76.8	62.1	72.2	65.2	73.7	60.5	24.0	78.4	49.8	93.0	73.7	18.0	91.1	91.2	91.2	0.0
	35	76.1	15.7	50.1	71.8	40.3	73.8	60.6	84.2	59.1	22.7	68.7	64.1	89.6	74.1	11.1	81.2	92.8	87.0	5.8
	42	72.0	7.4	46.9	76.8	74.2	67.7	61.7	78.3	60.6	23.8	71.1	70.8	87.0	76.3	7.6	62.5	88.7	75.6	13.1
25 °C	2	84.5	73.6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	91.3	83.1	8.9	94.0	72.9	95.0	87.3	10.2	84.5	90.5	87.5	3.0
	7	87.3	64.0	NA	77.1	92.7	92.6	71.8	85.9	81.6	11.0	85.6	73.1	87.2	82.0	6.3	87.8	93.3	90.5	2.8
	14	89.0	62.0	NA	83.2	76.6	87.7	52.1	75.2	75.1	13.7	88.2	77.5	92.9	86.2	6.5	79.4	84.6	82.0	2.6
	21	89.0	79.4	NA	82.0	90.9	84.4	71.0	85.8	83.2	6.7	82.9	77.0	91.9	83.9	6.1	92.7	86.1	89.4	3.3

	28	66.1	73.1	NA	69.1	91.2	89.2	76.2	84.9	78.5	9.9	79.3	71.8	95.0	82.0	9.7	94.8	93.0	93.9	0.9
	35	80.9	48.9	NA	68.1	87.3	83.2	64.3	67.9	71.5	13.3	80.6	59.6	94.0	78.1	14.2	74.6	92.9	83.8	9.1
	42	90.7	58.5	NA	76.8	87.7	84.8	71.4	83.2	79.0	11.2	83.3	72.1	92.9	82.8	8.5	74.6	89.7	82.1	7.5
34 °C	2	NA	NA																	
	7	88.9	58.0	70.5	83.1	82.8	80.4	51.9	77.6	74.1	13.0	NA	NA							
	14	51.7	20.1	86.0	81.7	83.0	85.8	82.0	35.0	65.7	26.3	NA	NA							
	21	36.9	9.0	62.9	59.2	52.3	58.7	69.9	10.5	44.9	23.7	NA	NA							
	28	30.9	3.8	27.6	38.6	24.7	11.5	19.7	6.0	20.3	12.4	NA	NA							
	35	4.1	8.5	9.5	14.4	16.6	4.3	18.4	2.9	9.8	6.0	NA	NA							
	42	1.8	6.1	4.6	1.7	3.4	2.2	1.7	5.5	3.4	1.8	NA	NA							
34/20 °C	2	NA	NA																	
	7	88.2	NA	62.5	88.7	78.4	81.9	57.8	89.6	78.1	13.0	NA	NA							
	14	86.4	NA	46.2	91.9	83.5	89.0	83.3	78.6	79.8	15.4	NA	NA							
	21	76.6	NA	86.4	73.7	63.0	83.9	70.2	46.2	71.4	13.7	NA	NA							
	28	67.2	NA	83.0	88.5	82.1	77.8	68.9	53.3	74.4	12.1	NA	NA							
	35	81.1	NA	75.5	78.0	75.2	73.5	55.5	45.7	69.2	13.3	NA	NA							
	42	83.3	NA	77.4	87.2	61.7	82.2	63.5	26.7	68.8	21.0	NA	NA							

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4. General discussion

The comparative approach was used to study adaptive traits of fungal pathogens and mutualists belonging to the fungal genera *Geosmithia* and *Pseudogymnoascus*. Outbreaks of infectious fungal diseases are often associated with the introduction of fungal pathogens, largely as a result of human activities, into new areas and their subsequent jump to a new host (Slippers, Stenlid et al. 2005). In their original range, both *G. morbida* and *P. destructans* behave as mild pathogens, due to their long co-evolution with their hosts. After their introduction outside their native ranges, they encountered naive host populations and became the cause of their dieback. The natural phenotypic variability of the individuals present among host species could mediate their innate resistance to disease (Lilley, Johnson et al. 2016). Otherwise, host species may develop resistance or tolerance to the disease under strong selection pressure (Langwig, Hoyt et al. 2017). However, excessively strong selection pressure can also lead to the extinction of the affected species, which calls for the intensive study of interactions between the pathogen and the host. During the necrotic growth phase of plant pathogens, plant tissues are degraded (Meinhardt, Costa et al. 2014; Broberg, Doonan et al. 2018; Ibarra Caballero, Jeon et al. 2019). Analysis of *G. morbida* genome did not show an increase in CAZymes compared to the non-pathogenic species *G. flava* and *G. putterillii* (Schuelke, Wu et al. 2017). However, during growth on a semi-natural medium (Veselská, Skelton et al. 2019), *G. morbida* produced a unique composition of extracellular enzymes that modify all structural components of the plant cell wall (cellulose, hemicellulose, and lignin), by which *G. morbida* differed from other *Geosmithia* species. Therefore, we assume that this unique enzymatic combination reflects its pathogenic abilities. Laccase production by some conifer specialists may reflect their need to detoxify plant tissues (Ibarra Caballero, Jeon et al. 2019).

Our *in vitro* experiments revealed that *P. destructans* is able to degrade urea, by which the fungus can decrease the pH of the surrounding environment. Upregulation of urease was detected in transcriptome analysis of *P. destructans* during its pathogenic growth on bats (Field, Johnson et al. 2015). Given that increasing pH through urease activity is one of the dual-used virulence factors (Vylkova 2017) used by ready-made pathogens, it is possible that it also applies to WNS. However, further experiments are needed to test this hypothesis.

An interesting result is that in both pathogenic fungi, *G. morbida* and *P. destructans*, we detected a significant loss of metabolic pathways compared to their related saprotrophic species. The results of our *in vitro* analyses are in agreement with available data obtained by genome sequencing, which revealed significant losses of genes in both species (Schuelke, Wu et al. 2017; Palmer, Drees et al. 2018). Therefore, we can assume that the results of our *in vitro* analyzes were not significantly skewed by the removal of fungi from their natural environment, for example, by the absence of associated microbes that can supply them with essential substances for growth. *Geosmithia* specialists to the plant family Pinaceae also have a similarly narrowed metabolic apparatus. In this case, the loss of enzymatic pathways probably occurred because of their long co-evolution with bark beetles (Kolařík and Jankowiak 2013). To conclude, the narrowing of the enzymatic potential in the genus *Geosmithia* and in the genus *Pseudogymnoascus* is supposed to be the result of long-term specialization to a limited diversity of available nutrients. By contrast, the metabolic diversity of the obligatory mutualistic ambrosia *Geosmithia* species was not reduced in comparison to saprotrophic species. Our findings correspond to the results of Huang, Skelton et al. (2018), where the enzymatic profiles of ambrosia fungi were explained by their phylogenetic history rather than by ecology. Ambrosia fungi

are obligatory symbionts of specific beetles, but at the same time, they are often generalists in their association with plants as they can colonize a broad spectrum of plant species. For this reason, the enzymatic equipment of the ambrosial *Geosmithia* species probably reflects the diverse spectrum of substrates on which they grow. Similarly to other ambrosia fungi, ambrosial *Geosmithia* species cannot degrade lignocellulose. Recent studies suggest that yeast and bacteria are the first colonizers of ambrosia beetle galleries. These microorganisms synergistically prepare galleries for the growth of ambrosial fungi by release of nutrients bound in structural plant tissues (Barcoto, Carlos-Shanley et al. 2020; Ibarra-Juarez, Burton et al. 2020; Joseph and Keyhani 2021).

The reduction in metabolic diversity was not associated with a decrease in genome size in *P. destructans* or conifer specialists of the genus *Geosmithia*. On the contrary, the genome size of these species has increased. In the case of *P. destructans*, the genome increased in size via the replication of repetitive sequences (Palmer, Drees et al. 2018), whereas in the genus *Geosmithia* it is probably increased by diploidization or aneuploidization of the conidial genome (Veselská and Kolařík 2015). We did not observe enlargement of the genome size in the necrotrophic pathogen *G. morbida*, which targets the plant family Juglandaceae. Similarly to likewise specialized *Fusarium* species (Ma, van der Does et al. 2010), the genome of *G. morbida* is shaped by gene losses without any apparent spreading of repetitive sequences, which Schuelke, Wu et al. (2017) consider an adaptive response. We suppose that the genome evolution of specialized necrotrophic plant species is subject to different selective pressures than the genome evolution of biotrophic pathogens, the genomes of which are affected by massive proliferation of repetitive sequences and effector genes necessary for fungal-plant communication. The main advantage of having a small genome possibly resides in more efficient metabolism or saving of available nutrient sources (Morris, Lenski et al. 2012); however, this requires irreversible specialization on the substrate (Kelley and Farrell 1998).

Genome size affects the physiology and ecology of eukaryotic organisms (Gregory 2001; Gregory 2005). In fungi, the effect of genome size on ecophysiology has so far been studied only sporadically. However, these rare studies reveal a positive correlation between genome and cell size even in fungi (Jorgensen, Edgington et al. 2007), and that change in genome size can be adaptive (Todd, Forche et al. 2017). In plants and animals, we observe a 'trade-off' between the production of small offspring or the investment into larger offspring. Larger offspring tend to have higher viability; however, more energy is required for their production. In fungi, this dependence is not so straightforward, since fungal spores usually spread by wind, so their size and shape are limited. Larger spores tend to be more spherical (Kausrud, Colman et al. 2008), the potential distance they travel decreases, and the likelihood that they might get caught by obstacles increases. Therefore, it is not surprising that approximately 75% of anemochoric fungi studied show only a small (up to 1%) deviation from the presumed optimal spore shape, which is an ellipsoid, for wind propagation (Roper, Pepper et al. 2008). By contrast, fungi that have escaped aerodynamic constraints because they use other means to spread spores, such as by insect, can afford to form large spores of various shapes. Large spores carry more nutrients and water needed for germination and are thus more resistant to stressful conditions, such as higher temperatures or lower precipitation, which expands their potential niche in time and space (Kausrud, Heegaard et al. 2011). Our study (Veselská and Kolařík 2015) is one of the first to link a positive correlation between genome and conidia size to fungal ecology. However, in our study we did not measure the size of the genome in the mycelium. It is therefore not clear whether intra-strain variability in the genome size of conifer specialists is maintained during vegetative growth,

or whether aneuploidization/diploidization of the genome is linked only to conidia formation. In the case of *G. eupagioceri*, the multiplication of nuclei in the cells is probably bound only to conidia, which indicates a controlled mechanism of their formation. If the increases in genomes in *Geosmithia* specialists are associated only with conidia, it may suggest that these species combine the advantages of r- and K-strategists. During vegetative growth, they take advantage of r-strategists (i.e., faster mitotic division), and during generative growth, they take advantage of K-strategists, (i.e., investment into progeny by forming nutrient-rich conidia).

5. Conclusion

Every pathogen and its host undergo co-evolution, in which the virulence of the pathogen is reduced due to the adaptive responses of its host, a so-called arms race. The jump of a pathogen to a new host that has not undergone an arms race is often associated with the development of a new infectious disease, which emphasizes the need to understand the interactions between the pathogen and the host. One striking adaptation identified during my research is the enzymatic losses of fungal specialists, which allow them to utilize available resources efficiently. Another significant adaptation is the modulation of genome size in response to species ecology. So far, we have only sparse information about the influence of genome size on physiology, and thus also the ecology and evolution of fungi. From the knowledge obtained from the world of plants and animals; however, it is clear that the size of the genome is one of the important features determining the development and life of an individual. Further studies will show how genome size manifests itself in the fungal world.

6. Appendix

6.1. Appendix 1: In situ tissue pH measurement by fluorescent dyes

These experiments were part of the response to the reviewers' comments during the review process of publication P5. The results of the experiments were not published.

We selected two fluorescent dyes: SNARF-1 (sensitivity between pH of 6 and 9) and the pHrodo Red AM intercellular pH indicator (pH 4–8) for pH measurements. Pieces of bat wings membranes were cut from living and dead bats (kept in a freezer) using a razor blade. Necrotic sites were detected based on autofluorescence at 520 nm and their specific morphology.

METHODS

SNARF-1

The samples were stained with 0.1 mM SNARF-1 (Molecular Probes) in distilled water for 30 min. A standard curve for pH calibration was prepared by incubation of 0.7% agar in phosphate buffers with desired pH (6.0, 7.0, 7.3, 7.5, 7.6, 8.0) containing 0.1 mM SNARF-1. SNARF-1 is a fluorescent pH indicator that undergoes a pH-dependent wavelength shift. The standard method is based on excitation between 488 and 530 nm and dual emission detection at 580 and 640 nm. If a standard pH curve is established, the ratio of detected fluorescence intensities at respective wavelengths allows for accurate determination of the pH of the sample. We used a confocal microscope, Olympus FV1000 TIRF, for pH detection at the Cytometry and Microscopy Core Facility of the Institute of Microbiology of the CAS with a 20×/0.75 objective. The dye was excited at 473 nm and a lambda scan was used for the detection of emitted light. Lambda scans were performed using a 5-nm spectral window shifted continuously from 550 to 650 nm through the spectrum in 21 steps.

The pHrodo Red AM intercellular pH indicator

The samples were washed in HEPES buffer pH 7.5 and then stained in HEPES with pHrodo Red AM (Molecular Probes) dissolved in the PowerLoad solution for 30 min at 37 °C following the manufacturer's protocol. We used the Intercellular pH calibration kit (Molecular Probes) for pH quantification. For this purpose, pieces of the wing membrane were labelled in the same way as previously and then washed twice with HEPES buffer of pH 7.5. Finally, the HEPES buffer was replaced by the desired cellular pH calibration buffer (pH 4.5, 5.5, 6.5 and 7.5) containing 10 µM Valinomycin and 10 µM Nigericin and incubated at 37 °C for 15 min. The samples were analyzed under an Olympus FV1000 TIRF confocal microscope. The fluorescent dye pHrodo Red AM was excited at 559 nm and emission at 580 nm was captured using a BA 575-620 bandpass filter.

Results and discussion

We did not detect any difference in pH between healthy and necrotic wing tissue using SNARF-1 (Fig. 1), which suggests that fungal growth was not accompanied by strong tissue alkalization. Both healthy and necrotic tissues had a pH of 6, which is at the lower bound of the pH sensitivity range of SNARF-1. Therefore, we cannot exclude a change in pH in necrotic tissues, as both healthy and necrotic tissue can have a pH of less than 6, which cannot be detected by SNARF-1. Because of that, we selected the fluorescent dyes pHrodo Red AM with a pH range of down to pH 4.

We plotted a standard curve using the pHrodo Red AM probe with intracellular pH calibration, which contains four buffers with different pH: 4.5, 5.5, 6.5 and 7.5. Median values of fluorescence intensities (for at least 12 measurements) were plotted and a linear trend line was fitted to obtain a standard curve (Fig. 2). The pH of healthy and necrotic tissue was calculated from a linear equation. The pH of healthy tissue was close to 4, which is at lower range detected for the human skin surface (Schmid-Wendtner and Korting 2006), whereas the pH of necrotic spots was 0.9. It is obvious that such a low pH value is an artefact possibly caused by the non-linear response of the pHrodo Red AM probe to tissue pH beyond its declared sensitivity to pH change (4–8). Therefore, it seems that pH at necrotic sites is somehow lower than that of healthy tissue, but there are too many discrepancies to draw any conclusions.

Figure 1. Lambda scan of necrotic and healthy tissue of the bat wing membrane. Peak at 580 and 620 nm was used to pH measurements. The ratio of fluorescent intensity of 620 nm to 580 nm was similar between healthy and necrotic tissue, 1.8 versus 1.7, respectively.

Figure 2. In situ tissue pH measurement with the pHrodo Red AM Intercellular pH indicator.

a – Linear fit was obtained from the median of fluorescence intensities of wing membrane samples incubated at desired cellular pH calibration buffer pH 4.5, 5.5, 6.5, and 7.5; pH of healthy and necrotic tissue was calculated from linear equation. b – Wing labelled with pHrodo Red AM intercellular pH indicator. Circles 1 and 2 – necrotic sites; autofluorescence at 520 nm is co-localized with brighter fluorescence of the pH indicator, indicating acidification of necrosis. Circles 3 and 4 – healthy wing tissue; autofluorescence at 520 nm is absent.

7. References

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